

**EFFECTS OF SQUAT EXERCISES INVOLVING WHOLE BODY
VIBRATION STIMULI AND HIP ADDUCTION ON ACUTE
NEUROMUSCULAR RESPONSES OF QUADRICEPS MUSCLE IN
HEALTHY AND PATELLOFEMORAL PAIN SYNDROME
POPULATIONS.**

By

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Abstract

Background: Whole body vibration (WBV) platforms produce oscillatory waves to stimulate neuromuscular activity during strength exercises. Patellofemoral Pain Syndrome (PFPS) is pain in the anterior part of the knee during daily activities. Static and dynamic exercises to strengthen the quadriceps muscle are recommended for individuals with PFPS. However, there is still no optimal exercise approach and new exercise interventions should be sought. **Aims:** (1) to determine the validity and reliability of WBV platform outputs, Thera-Band force and the Delsys Trigno Avanti electromyography (EMG) System (2) to evaluate the inter-day reliability of possible individualised WBV stimuli on acute VM activity during static squat in healthy individuals; (3) to evaluate different static squats involving WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction on acute quadriceps neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals; and in individuals with PFPS. **Method:** All participants in this thesis were healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS. Platform output was assessed using accelerometers. Acute neuromuscular activity of vastus medialis (VM) and vastus lateralis (VL) was measured using EMG during static squat exercises with and without resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli. Normalised maximum amplitude of VM, VL and VM/VL was compared between exercise conditions. **Results:** WBV platform outputs were reliable but not valid, Thera-Band forces were valid and reliable, and the EMG system was reliable. Little evidence for an individualised WBV stimuli response was found. There was no significant effect of WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction on acute VM and VL activity in healthy individuals or those with PFPS. However, squat exercise alone and squat exercise with WBV stimuli increased VM/VL ratio in individuals with PFPS. **Conclusions:** Static squat exercises with resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli alternately can be used on acute quadriceps neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS. Squat exercise alone and squat exercise with WBV stimuli can be used alternately to increase VM/VL ratio in individuals with PFPS during rehabilitation programmes. The chronic effects of these exercises should be further evaluated in healthy and PFPS to provide evidence-based practice in a clinical setting.

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Abbreviations

CKC - Closed Kinetic-Chain

EMG - Electromyography

FFT - Fast Fourier Transform

GTO - Golgi Tendon Organ

Hz - Hertz

kg - Kilograms

m - metres

ms - Milliseconds

MVC - Maximal Voluntary Contraction

OKC - Open Kinetic-Chain

PFPS - Patellofemoral Pain Syndrome

P-to-p displacement - Peak to peak displacement

RMS - Root Mean Squared

s - Second

SD - Standard Deviation

SEM - Standard Error of Measurement

TVR - Tonic Vibration Reflex

WBV - Whole body vibration

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Conference Presentations

Alqaseer, D., Baker, J. S, Valentin, S. and Sanderson, M. F., A systematic review and meta-analysis on the effect of novel knee rehabilitation techniques during squatting on acute Vastus Medialis muscle activity in healthy individuals: implications for Patellofemoral Pain Syndrome (PFPS) patients. ECSS Conference, July 2018 (Oral Presentation).

Alqaseer, D. A., Baker, J. S, Valentin, S. and Sanderson, M. F., A systematic review and meta-analysis on the effect of novel knee rehabilitation techniques during squatting on acute Vastus Medialis muscle activity in healthy individuals: implications for Patellofemoral Pain Syndrome (PFPS) patients. UWS Conference, July 2018 (Poster).

Statement of Originality

The work in this thesis has been done by myself under the supervision of Dr. Mark Sanderson and Dr. Stephanie Valentin. This thesis contains no material that has been previously published by another person except where due reference is made in the thesis itself. This work has not been previously submitted for award at any other institution.

Dalal Abdullah Alqaseer, 2021

Chapter 1

Introduction and Literature Review

1.0 Introduction

Resistance exercises can increase muscle strength and the performance of the human body (Nordlund and Thorstensson, 2007; Eftekhari et al., 2012). Resistance in such exercises can be created by external forces, such as whole body vibration (WBV) platforms, elastic Thera-Bands, or by body weight which can affect the neuromuscular response by increasing muscle activity or muscle force (Awan, Khan and Perveen, 2017; Dionello et al., 2017). Over the past few decades, the role of WBV and Thera-Band as potential equipment for use in resistance exercise has been evaluated (Nordlund and Thorstensson, 2007; Awan, Khan and Perveen, 2017; Jakobsen et al., 2012). Both healthy individuals and clinical populations can benefit from WBV stimuli during their rehabilitation programs either in a hospital setting or a fitness centre (e.g. the gym) (Mileva, Bowtell and Kossev, 2009; Eftekhari et al., 2012). WBV stimuli and Thera-Band can be applied via acute exposure (Lee et al., 2016; Pojskic et al., 2015) or long-time training programmes (Biçer et al., 2015; Stania et al., 2017; Park et al., 2013).

WBV stimuli are mechanical oscillatory waves which can be controlled by parameters that include frequency and peak-to-peak displacement; the frequency is defined as the number of oscillation cycles that occur over a set length of time, while the peak-to-peak displacement is the range of movement of the vibration between positive and negative values (Rauch et al., 2010a). The WBV platform acceleration is defined as the change in velocity level during a wave cycle; this can be assessed by both frequency and peak-to-peak displacement. Evaluation the effect of these parameters is essential for rehabilitation programs, to establish the potential benefits of WBV

stimuli in patient treatment programmes (Dionello et al., 2017). Also, evaluating the reliability and validity of WBV outputs is necessary, before being used in practical application for medical conditions including neuromuscular injuries, neurological injuries, and joint injuries (Eftekhari et al., 2012; Dionello et al., 2017).

WBV stimulation is considered a possible treatment option for neuromuscular conditions, to improve muscle activity, joint range of motion, and balance (Osawa, Oguma and Ishii, 2013; Awan, Khan and Perveen, 2017). These effects of WBV stimuli have been determined using subjective and objective outcome measures in relation to conditions that include osteoarthritis, stroke, Parkinson's disease, patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS), and multiple sclerosis (Madou and Cronin, 2008; Eftekhari et al., 2012; Park et al., 2013; Corum et al., 2018; Fischer et al., 2019; Huang and Pang, 2019). Also, WBV stimuli can stimulate the neuromuscular activity which evaluated using electromyography (EMG) where the WBV stimuli can be applied in order to improve the neuromuscular activity of lower limb muscles such as the quadriceps, in healthy individuals and in clinical populations (Krol et al., 2011; Park et al., 2013; Biçer et al., 2015).

The evaluation of the quadriceps' muscle activity can be obtained via EMG during strength exercises such as a static or dynamic squat (Earl, Schmitz and Arnold, 2001; Felicio et al., 2019). The quadriceps' muscle activity during squat positions can be affected by injuries in the knee joints, such as PFPS (also known as a runner's knee). PFPS which is a multifactorial condition, is commonly developed during squatting or running and can be presented due to a quadricep's muscle weakness and result in pain at the anterior part of the knee. The treatment protocol for PFPS should be tailored on the patient symptoms. However, quadriceps exercises are counted as the first treatment option for PFPS treatment protocol. Therefore, this thesis will investigate the

effect of various squat exercises for quadriceps muscle in individuals with PFPS. The following workflow diagram will illustrate this thesis design.

1.1 Thesis Workflow Diagram

1.2 Anatomy structures for hip and knee joints

The structures for hip and knee joints will be discussed in the following.

1.2.1 Hip joint

The femoral head articulates with the acetabulum in the pelvic bone forming the hip joint, and this allows the hip joint to engage in movements of flexion, extension, abduction, adduction, medial rotation, lateral rotation, and circumduction (Tortora and Derrickson, 2017) (Figure 1.1).

1.2.2 Knee joint

The knee joint consists of three joints, including the lateral tibiofemoral joint, which is located between the lateral condyle of the femur and the lateral condyle of the tibia; the medial tibiofemoral joint, which is located between medial condyle of the femur and the medial condyle of the tibia; and the patellofemoral joint, which is located between the patella and the patella surface of the femur (Figure 1.1) (Tortora and Derrickson, 2017).

Figure 1.1: Bones of the proximal leg; a) anterior view, b) posterior view (Tortora and Derrickson, 2017). Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

The main movements of the knee joint are flexion and extension. The four main ligaments that surround the knee joint include; anterior cruciate ligament which limits anterior sliding of the tibia on the femur and hyperextension; posterior cruciate ligament limits posterior sliding of the tibia during knee flexion; medial and lateral collateral ligaments which restrict the lateral and medial

movement of the knee joint respectively. The knee joint includes two fibrocartilage discs called the medial and lateral meniscus which circulate synovial fluid (Tortora and Derrickson, 2017).

1.2.3 Muscles around the hip and knee joints

Muscles are attached to bone via tendon or aponeurosis in order to facilitate the movements of the limbs (Tortora and Derrickson, 2017). The thigh muscles (see Figure 1.2 for anterior and posterior view) are divided by deep fascia into anterior, medial, lateral and posterior compartments. The hip anterior compartment is involved in hip flexion and knee extension, while the hip medial compartment is involved in adducting the leg and medially rotating the thigh; the hip lateral compartment is involved in hip abduction and laterally rotating the leg; the hip posterior compartment facilitates hip extension and knee flexion (Table 1).

a) Anterior view

b) Posterior view

Figure 1.2: Medial, anterior and posterior compartments of the thigh muscles: a) anterior view, b) posterior view (Tortora and Derrickson, 2017). Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Table 1. Medial, anterior, lateral, and posterior compartments of the thigh (Tortora & Derrickson, 2017; Gilroy, 2020).

Muscle compartment	Origin	Insertion	Action	Innervation
Medial compartment of thigh				
Adductor magnus	Inferior pubis and ischial tuberosity	Linea aspera of femur	Adduct and rotate thigh, flex and extend hip joint	Obturator and sciatic nerves
Adductor longus	Pubic crest and pubic symphysis	Linea aspera of femur	Adduct and flex hip joint, rotate thigh	Obturator nerve
Adductor brevis	Inferior ramus of pubis	Superior linea a aspera of femur	Adduct, flex and rotate thigh	Obturator nerve
Pectineus	Superior ramus of pubis	Pectineal line of femur	Flexes and adducts thigh at hip joint	Femoral nerve
Gracilis	Inferior pubis	Medial tibia	Hip adduction, medial rotation and leg flex at knee joint	Obturator nerve
Anterior compartment of thigh				
Rectus femoris	Anterior inferior iliac spine	Patella by quadriceps tendon and tibial tuberosity via patellar ligament	Extend the knee, flex thigh	Femoral nerve
Vastus lateralis	Greater trochanter and linea aspera of femur	Patella by quadriceps tendon and tibial tuberosity via patellar ligament	Extend the knee	Femoral nerve
Vastus medialis	Linea aspera of femur	Patella by quadriceps tendon and tibial tuberosity via patellar ligament	Extend the knee	Femoral nerve
Vastus intermedius	Anterior and lateral surfaces of femur	Patella by quadriceps tendon and tibial tuberosity via patellar ligament	Extend the knee	Femoral nerve
Sartorius	Anterior and superior iliac spine	Medial surface of tibia	Weakly flex leg at knee joint; weakly flex, abduct, and laterally rotate thigh at hip joint	Femoral nerve
Lateral compartment of thigh				
Iliopsoas	Transverse processes and bodies of lumbar vertebrae	With iliacus into lesser trochanter of femur	Flex thigh at hip joint, rotate thigh laterally, and flex trunk	Lumbar spinal nerves
Iliacus	Iliac fossa and sacrum	With psoas major into lesser trochanter of femur	Flex thigh at hip joint, rotate thigh laterally	Femoral nerve
Gluteus maximus	Iliac crest, sacrum, coccyx, and aponeurosis of sacrospinalis.	Iliotibial tract of fascia lata and superior lateral part of linea aspera	Extends thigh at hip joint and laterally rotates thigh	Inferior gluteal nerve
Gluteus medius	Ilium	Greater trochanter of femur	Abducts thigh at hip joint and medially rotates thigh	Superior gluteal nerve

Gluteus minimus	Ilium	Greater trochanter of femur	Abducts thigh at hip joint and medially rotates thigh	Superior gluteal nerve
Tensor fascia latae	Iliac crest	Tibia by way of iliotibial tract	Flexes and abducts thigh at hip joint	Superior gluteal nerve
Piriformis	Anterior sacrum	Superior border of greater trochanter of femur.	Laterally rotates and abducts thigh at hip joint	Sacral spinal nerves
Obturator internus	Inner surface of obturator foramen, pubis, and ischium	Medial surface of greater trochanter of femur	Laterally rotates and abducts thigh at hip joint	Nerve to obturator internus
Obturator externus	Outer surface of obturator membrane	Deep depression inferior to greater trochanter of femur	Laterally rotates and abducts thigh at hip joint. Obturator	Obturator nerve
Superior gemellus	Ischial spine	Medial surface of greater trochanter of femur	Laterally rotates and abducts thigh at hip joint	Nerve to obturator internus
Inferior gemellus	Ischial tuberosity	Medial surface of greater trochanter of femur	Laterally rotates and abducts thigh at hip joint	Nerve to quadratus femoris
Quadratus femoris	Ischial tuberosity	Elevation superior to midportion of intertrochanteric crest (quadrate tubercle) on posterior femur	Laterally rotates and stabilizes hip joint	Nerve to quadratus femoris
Posterior compartment of thigh				
Biceps femoris	Ischial tuberosity and linea aspera of femur	Head of fibula and lateral condyle of tibia	Flex leg at knee joint and extend thigh at hip joint	Tibial and fibular nerves
Semitendinosus	Ischial tuberosity	Medial surface of tibia	Flex leg at knee joint and extend thigh at hip joint	Tibial nerve
Semimembranosus	Ischial tuberosity	Medial condyle of tibia	Flex leg at knee joint and extend thigh at hip joint	Tibial nerve

1.2.4 Electromyography (EMG)

EMG is a tool which can be used to evaluate neuromuscular function for diagnostic purpose or rehabilitation programmes (Massó et al., 2010). This evaluation can be performed on time activation (Lee, Lee and Lee, 2014b), muscle fatigue (Rathey et al., 2006) and muscle force (Besier et al., 2009). These analyses can be used according to the purpose of the research. The EMG signals can be collected by EMG surface electrode (non-invasive) or by a needle electrode (invasive) (Pattichis et al., 1999). These surface electrodes are used on superficial large muscles with no pain of needle insertion as they are commonly placed on the surface of the skin. However, the needle electrodes have been found to be accurate in recording signals with high frequency (spontaneous activity), and can be used for small superficial or deep muscles (Zhang et al., 2003; Konrad, 2006; Turker, 1993). They are by nature invasive and can be associated with participant discomfort and pain. Although surface electrodes are commonly used, they are highly susceptible to movement artifacts and resistance conditions that may disturb the sensor EMG signal (Wu, Martinez Martinez and Orizaola Balaguer, 2013). Multiple EMG surface electrodes can be used on a muscle; monopolar, bipolar, or more electrodes. The monopolar surface electrodes collect EMG signals may also include the electromagnetic noise (Turker, 1993). In bipolar surface electrodes, the potential signal between electrodes is recorded and the possibility of electromagnetic noise will be minimised. Also, the bipolar surface electrodes are preferred to be used in literature (Turker, 1993). EMG systems with bipolar surface electrodes found to be reliable on neuromuscular activity of quadriceps and biceps brachii muscles (Bolgia et al., 2010; McKenzie et al., 2010; Ollivier et al., 2005). For reliability of the current EMG system please refer to section 4.5.

1.3 The patella's role in the knee joint

The patella is the largest sesamoid bone in the human body, located in the anterior part of the knee. The patella is attached distally to the patellar tendon and connected proximally to the femur during knee flexion. The patella increases knee stability and extension range in the last degrees of extension (Tecklenburg et al., 2006). The patella protects the anterior part of the knee and distributes force by surface contacting between the posterior part of the patella to the femur, termed the patellar groove (Tecklenburg et al., 2006). The patella facilitates knee joint extension through quadriceps muscle activity by raising the patellar tendon moment arm and absorbing the force generated from the surrounding tissues by transmission the force from the femur to the patella tendon.

The patellofemoral joint acts a stabiliser during knee flexion. During knee extension, the tension in the patellofemoral joint decreases, whereas during flexion, the tension in the patellofemoral joint increases compared to the patellar ligament tension (Mills and Hunter, 2014). This process can produce pain in positions involving knee flexion such as squatting, prolong sitting and running, and referred to as movie sign (van Linschoten et al., 2011). Moreover, during knee flexion, the patellofemoral contact area increases, resulting in small changes in the contact pressure in the cartilage (Mostamand, Bader and Hudson, 2010; Bai et al., 2012). Also, during knee flexion, the first contact for the patella occurs via contact between the distal part of the patella and the femoral trochlea groove. This contact area increases in the distal part of the patella, distributing the force onto a larger area so that the stress on the patella is decreased. The contact area increases as the knee flexion angle becomes larger (Salsich et al., 2003; Besier et al., 200). This increase in contact area occurs before weight-bearing via contact between the lateral facet of the patella and the lateral condyle of the femur. During the weight-bearing in knee flexion, the patella contact area moves

medially to the medial condyle of the femur, which illustrates the increased contact area and distributes the pressure on a wider surface (Besier et al., 2005). Specifically, contact area can increase by 24% during weight bearing compared to the unloaded position (Besier et al., 2005). Furthermore, a 60° knee flexion angle significantly increases the contact area and the load in the knee joint compared to 0° and 30° angles of knee flexion (Besier et al., 2005). In addition, the contact area can be affected by the unequal distribution of quadriceps force, resulting in an altered stress distribution in the knee joint and causing knee joint pathologies. Therefore, quadriceps exercises can help to minimise the stress in the patellofemoral joint (Powers et al., 2014). Increases in quadriceps muscle force/tension (Hungerford and Barr, 1979), the abnormal distribution of the femur-patella contact area (Bai et al., 2012) and hamstring shortening (White, Dolphin and Dixon, 2009) can all be possible risk factors for patellofemoral joint pain which may further discuss in section 1.4.1.

1.4 Patellofemoral pain syndrome

In 1928, scholars began to refer to PFPS as ‘chondromalacia patellae’ (Sandow and Goodfellow, 1985). The condition can be seen by deteriorating in the patellar cartilage and patellofemoral joint pain, and it was thought that greater levels of joint pain were associated with greater cartilage changes. Arthroscopy was one of the methods that was used to evaluate the PFPS condition when surgeons found that this supposed link does not exist, because not all patients diagnosed with ‘chondromalacia patellae’ displayed pain in the patellofemoral joint, and vice versa (Abernethy et al., 1978). Thereafter, the term ‘chondromalacia patellae’ has rarely been used; instead, the terms ‘anterior knee pain’ and ‘patellofemoral syndrome’ are now used (Sandow and Goodfellow, 1985; Waryasz and Mcdermott, 2008). Other terms linking the condition’s aetiology with its name in the literature include ‘patellofemoral malalignment’ (Guzzanti et al., 1994), ‘idiopathic anterior knee

pain' (Patil et al., 2010) and 'retro-patellar pain syndrome' (Alba-Martín et al., 2015). However, the terms 'anterior knee pain' and 'patellofemoral syndrome' are most commonly seen. 'Anterior knee pain' is the general term for pain that involves more complex symptoms than pain limited to the patellofemoral joint (Sandow and Goodfellow, 1985); therefore, for this thesis, the term 'patellofemoral pain syndrome', or 'PFPS', is used throughout.

PFPS accounts for 25% of all knee injuries in sports clinics in United States of America (Nar, 2013). The incidence of PFPS is up to 25 % of sport injuries (Manske and Davies, 2016) and the percentage of history of PFPS in females is 25% higher than males (Boling et al., 2010). In the United Kingdom, the prevalence of PFPS in 2016 was 22% as 25 out of 110 participants developed PFPS condition (Smith et al., 2018). In the United States, it was analysed in 2010 to be 22 out of 1000 person per years (Boling et al., 2010). In addition, 40% of clinical visits for knee complaints are related to PFPS (Myer et al., 2010). Individuals over the age of 50 have the highest risk of developing PFPS (Glaviano et al., 2015), and runners are the most affected individuals, often developing 'runner's knee'. Standardisation across different countries of the evaluation of incidence and prevalence for PFPS condition is required to allow for consistent comparison.

1.4.1 Characteristics of PFPS

PFPS displays multiple characteristics. The first is pain in the anterior part of the knee - this excludes other knee pathologies such as meniscal lesion or ligaments injuries (Şahin et al., 2016; Al-Hakim et al., 2012). This can either be acute pain caused by trauma, which lasts for less than three months, or chronic pain that occurs consistently during daily life, lasting for more than three months (Halabchi et al., 2017; Fox et al., 2018). Chronic PFPS pain can be defined as an acute re-exacerbation of the chronic condition (Manske and Davies, 2016). Another characteristic found in individuals with PFPS is knee joint crepitation, indicating cartilage damage (Schiphof et al., 2014).

Therefore, determining when crepitus occurs during available motion and in which direction (knee flexion or extension), can help to identify the exercises (such as weight bearing exercise or squat) required to best address the symptoms (Manske and Davies, 2016).

Joint inflammation may also be observed in acute and chronic PFPS. Such inflammation can be caused by increased stress on the patellofemoral joint, either sustained during activities involving compression of the joint (e.g., ascending/descending stairs, running), or static positions such as prolonged sitting (Brechtler and Powers, 2002; Boling et al., 2010; (Stefanyshyn et al., 2006). The occurrence of pain for individuals with PFPS can significantly impact their quality of life.

PFPS is a multifactorial condition that has sub-classification levels, with surgeons classifying the condition according to stages or anatomical alignment changes in the patella or femur. These classification methods depend on the surgeon's medical investigation; physiotherapists cannot detect these changes through clinical examinations alone (Callaghan, 2012). The PFPS condition can be determined based on the individual symptoms and limitations in an individual's physical activity level and as a result, all the pathological diagnosis characteristics of PFPS may not reflect the patient's impairments.

PFPS classifications have also been established based on the patient's muscle dysfunction and lower-limb malalignment (Witvrouw et al., 2005; Callaghan, 2012). Details on the most common PFPS classifications according to Witvrouw et al. (2005) are focused on lower limb neuromuscular system (illustrated in Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3: PFPS characteristics according to Witvrouw et al. (2005)

The process of diagnosing PFPS is carried out by excluding other knee conditions, rather than identifying the causes, and this method of classification can be the treatment protocol for all PFPS conditions. Another classification which has six categories is based on clusters impairment depending on the level of constraint in the patella, with the subsequent treatment plan assigned to various categories (Callaghan, 2012). These six classifications are; muscle dysfunction, gait abnormalities, patellar malalignment, proprioceptive factors, ischaemia and psychological factors (Callaghan, 2012). In the previous classifications, the physiotherapists should attempt to identify PFPS classifications depending on the patient's impairment (Willy et al., 2019). Although the classifications of muscle dysfunction and lower-limb malalignment are recommended by the European Rehabilitation Panel, the differences in the previous classification systems suggest there is a need to evaluate additional possible classification systems.

In 2010, the 2nd retreat for PFPS promoted the division of the condition into three categories (Powers et al., 2012): local factors, proximal factors, and distal/ combined factors. The local factors

concern the patellofemoral joint and the tissue around it; the proximal factors focus on the hip and pelvis; and the distal factors relate to the foot and ankle.

In contrast, Willy et al. (2019) classified PFPS according to function, disability and health - these subcategories define a patient's impairments. The three categories are: overuse without impairment, muscle deficits and coordination deficits (Willy et al., 2019). Overuse without impairment, evaluation of which is based on individual pain, can be examined using either the anterior knee pain scale or the visual analogue scale (VAS). Assessment of lower limb function, as well as mobility, strength and length of the hip and quadriceps, would target muscle performance deficit and mobility impairment. Finally, limb coordination can be examined during static and dynamic squatting, as well as when ascending and descending stairs (Willy et al., 2019). A review conducted by Fagan and Delahunt, (2008) illustrated that pain level has been investigated during strength deficit, VM/VL ratio and hip muscle in individuals with PFPS. In that review, the pain level decreased with the exercises targeted the muscle strength, VM/VL ratio and hip muscle strength. Therefore, all the following possible causes related to PFPS may indicate pain with functional limitation.

1.4.1.1 Strength deficits

According to Witvrouw et al. (2005), strength deficit is primarily observed in the quadriceps muscle in PFPS, specifically in the VM muscle. Volume and torque in the quadriceps muscle were assessed in 24 women with unilateral PFPS by MRI and dynamometer respectively (Kaya et al., 2011). Comparing the symptomatic limb with the asymptomatic limb, that study found muscle torque and volume significantly decreased in the symptomatic limb compared to the asymptomatic limb. Also, quadriceps muscle strength was evaluated using a dynamometer at 20° and 60° knee flexion angles in 46 females with unilateral PFPS by Guney et al. (2016) who found quadriceps

strength to be consistently lower in the symptomatic limb compared to the asymptomatic limb. Moreover, the quadriceps muscle deficits before and after squat exercise were evaluated by comparing the transverse relaxation time of VM muscle recruitment to evaluate the muscle metabolic reactions via MRI in 46 individuals with PFPS, compared to 30 healthy individuals (Pattyn et al., 2013). No significant difference was found in quadriceps' recruitment time between the two groups. Toumi et al. (2013) recruited 32 patients to evaluate quadriceps muscle strength by measuring force with strap attached to force transducer and individual's lower limb. However, quadriceps strength decreased after maximum isometric and squat exercise in only 12 of the 32 individuals compared to their asymptomatic limb (Toumi et al., 2013). Also, individuals with unilateral PFPS displayed reduced VM muscle thickness which assessed by ultrasound, compared to the same individuals' asymptomatic limb (Giles et al., 2015). This reveals there are only singular studies on each of these outcomes, suggesting strong conclusions cannot be made on differences between healthy and PFPS, or at least careful interpretations are needed. However, according to most studies quadriceps muscle weakness is certainly the most common risk factor (Waryasz and Mcdermott, 2008; Papadopoulos, Stasinopoulos and Ganchev, 2015). Thus, further research is required to fully determine the mechanism and possible causes of quadriceps muscle deficits in PFPS.

1.4.1.2 Knee angle (quadriceps angle)

The quadriceps angle (Q angle) is defined as the angle between the direction of the quadriceps muscle (taken from frontal plane between the line from the anterior superior iliac spine to the centre of the patella and the line from the middle of the patella to the tibial tubercle) (Herrington, 2013). Q angle can evaluate the alignment of the hip (femur) and patella (Emami et al., 2007; Lee, Lee and Lee, 2014). An increased Q angle can indicate an increase in tracking the patella laterally

and raise the risk of injury in the lower limb. In men, Q angle is considered too great when it exceeds 15° , whereas in women this is 20° (Herrington, 2013). Q angle in the PFPS population during natural stance was found to be large, which can be related to knee pathologies such as patellofemoral pain syndrome. Lee, Lee and Lee, (2014) assessed static and dynamic Q angle in individuals with PFPS during evaluation of sling and Thera-Band exercises in supine, side lying and sitting positions. In that study, dynamic Q angle was significantly decreased during Thera-Band exercise in individuals with PFPS compared to the sling exercise (Lee, Lee and Lee, 2014). However, there is a lack of consensus whether a large Q angle is a risk factor in individuals with PFPS. A study conducted by Caylor, Fites and Worrell, (1993) reported no effect of the Q angle on PFPS compared to healthy individuals, and no difference was found also when comparing the Q angle during quadriceps isometric contraction in the supine position to the standing position (Guerra, Arnold and Gajdosik, 1994). A large Q angle may influence the role of the VM muscle which can be identified as a medial stabiliser in the patellofemoral joint (Waryasz and Mcdermott, 2008); therefore weakness in the VM muscle (evaluated by EMG signals) may affect patella stability, which can result in patella mal-tracking (Goh., Lee. and Bose, 1995), and therefore possibly lead to the development of PFPS (Papadopoulos, Stasinopoulos and Ganchev, 2015).

In addition, it is necessary to further evaluate the effect of knee angle on quadriceps' muscle balance in static and dynamic movement, as well as in both supine and standing positions in clinical populations. More research is also needed regarding the effectiveness of tailored exercises that address the VM muscle in individuals with PFPS. The characteristics of PFPS - its causes, symptoms, treatment and prevention - will be discussed further in this Chapter.

1.4.1.3 VM:VL ratio

The VM:VL ratio which is referred to the ratio between VM and VL muscle activity, can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of exercise on quadriceps muscle activity. A VM:VL ratio of 1:1 is considered normal in healthy individuals (Smith et al., 2009). However, delays in the VM muscle activation resulted in altering the ratio to e.g. 1:2, which indicates the amplitude and timing of activation of the VL muscle before the VM muscle (Owings and Grabiner, 2002). Dysfunction of the VM:VL ratio has been investigated using EMG during squatting, standing and supine positions (Davlin, Holcomb and Guadagnoli, 1999; Pal et al., 2012; Jaberzadeh, Yeo and Zoghi, 2016). In a study by Nar, (2013), the relationship between the VM:VL ratio and the static/dynamic quadriceps angle (Q angle) were evaluated during isometric, eccentric and concentric exercise in both healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS. In that study, individuals with PFPS were found to have lower VM:VL ratios and higher Q angles compared to healthy individuals. Also, VM:VL activation onset was evaluated in 43 women with PFPS during the ascent of a seven-step staircase, compared to the same activity performed by 38 healthy women (Briani et al., 2016). Each participant group was categorised in two groups based on their level of physical activity from moderate to intense levels. The PFPS participants who were generally engaged in intense physical activity showed a delay in VM onset related to VL as determined by EMG, when compared to PFPS participants with moderate physical activity levels (Briani et al., 2016). However, evaluation of the VM:VL ratio during a rehabilitation programme with exercises include Thera-Band and sling-based tools in the PFPS population, performed three times a week, for a period of eight weeks, found Thera-Band significantly decreased the VM:VL timing ratio, compared to sling and the control group who did not perform any therapeutic exercise results (Lee, Lee and Lee, 2014). Therefore, exercise involving Thera-Band may not be effective on addressing the VM:VL timing ratio. In contrast, Toumi et al. (2013) found that the VM:VL ratio in the symptomatic limb in

individuals with PFPS did not significantly differ compared to the asymptomatic limb. A lack of consensus still remains in the literature; therefore, the role of VM muscle delay in PFPS continues to require further investigation.

1.4.1.4 Hip abductor muscles

The hip abductor muscles are counted as possible risk factor for PFPS (Papadopoulos, Stasinopoulos and Ganchev, 2015; Willy et al., 2019). Malalignment of the hip joint by excessive hip adduction and internal rotation is also considered to be a relevant coordination impairment (Dolak et al., 2011); patients with PFPS generally exhibit less torque in hip external rotation and hip abduction (Bolgia et al., 2008). A meta-analysis conducted by Rathleff et al. (2014) found moderate evidence that individuals with PFPS display decreased hip strength compared to healthy individuals. Therefore, there is thought to be a relationship between the presence of PFPS and strength reduction (Rathleff et al., 2014). When hip and knee malalignment occur, changes in knee joint articulation may be affected by a decrease in hip strength, thus leading to a build-up of pressure within the patellofemoral joint.

Razeghi et al. (2010) evaluated four weeks of resistive hip and quadriceps exercises including hip flexion, abduction, external rotation and knee extension in individuals with PFPS on their pain levels and in control group participants who only performed knee extensor exercises. The resistive hip and quadriceps exercises found to decrease the pain scale by 15% in individuals with PFPS compared to knee extensor exercises. Dolak et al. (2011) agreed on the effectiveness of hip exercises in treating individuals with PFPS. In total, 33 individuals with PFPS performed either quadriceps group exercises or hip muscle exercises for eight weeks. In the group that performed hip exercises, the pain was reduced by half, compared to the group that only performed quadriceps exercises. Furthermore, hip strengthening exercises improved the strength of the hip abductor

muscle, whereas no change occurred in the quadriceps group (Dolak et al., 2011). Although the treatment programme for individuals with PFPS should focus on strengthening of the hip muscles alongside knee strengthening exercises, further research is necessary to investigate whether the lack of hip strength is a risk factor or a result of PFPS by investigating the role of the hip mechanism in classifying PFPS. Although the role of hip muscles in PFPS which will be described in section 2.2, the present thesis is focus on the acute quadriceps neuromuscular activity during various squatting exercises.

1.4.2 PFPS interventions

Treatment protocols for PFPS can include non-surgical and surgical interventions. The conservative (non-surgical) treatment illustrated by Dixit et al. (2007) outlines the importance of avoiding sudden, intense movements of the knee joint, as well as taking rest from activities require loading on patellofemoral joint to prevent the occurrence of pain. Exercises can be a primary intervention for individuals with PFPS (Santos et al., 2015; Alrshood et al., 2017). Exercises such as swimming can be used during rest periods to sustain the individual's fitness, as well as the application of an ice pack (Dixit et al., 2007).

As mentioned previously PFPS is a multifactorial condition, therefore PFPS treatment should be tailored to the potential sources of the pain/risk factors. The core treatment for individuals with PFPS should be implemented after the assessment the main cause for pain which influence individual functional activities. The 2016 and 2018 PFPS Consensuses recommended physiotherapy hip and knee exercises as the primary intervention that should be used in treating PFPS (Crossley et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2018). This should involve hamstring and quadriceps exercises in closed and open kinetic chains (Harvie, O'leary and Kumar, 2011; Clijsen, Fuchs and Taeymans, 2014; Adel amongoush, Adel alwani, Amira alrshood, Mussa almughrabi, 2017; Vora

et al., 2017; Elliott et al., 2018). Moreover, Elliott et al. (2018) emphasised the importance of hip-strengthening exercises for individuals with PFPS, although only five studies were included in their review. It is clear that management of PFPS should be tailored according to an individual's symptoms and indications. PFPS treatment varies widely, and physiotherapists should adjust their approaches taking both short- and long-term goals into account. Also, further investigation is required due to the inconsistency in the previous studies' methodologies. Despite there being evidence for exercise programmes (Kooiker et al., 2014; Elliott et al., 2018; Alrshood et al., 2017), there are still no optimal exercise programmes for all individuals with PFPS and there are other approaches of new interventions that have not been explored yet.

Anti-inflammatory drugs have been shown to be effective in alleviating PFPS, particularly when combined with other treatments, such as exercise or therapeutic modalities including cold packs, electrical stimulation, ultrasound and laser (in cases of pain proving intolerable) (Al-Hakim et al., 2012; Halabchi et al., 2017). However, knee and patellar bracing are recommended, because they can reduce pain and correct knee malalignment (Bolgla and Boling, 2011). Additionally, patellar taping can be used to correct patella malalignment (Puddu, Giombini and Selvanetti, 2013). Foot orthoses can correct lower limb malalignment, and these were shown to have a significant effect in pain reduction when patients with PFPS performed squats (Barton, Menz and Crossley, 2011). The 2018 PFPS consensus recommended using patellar taping, bracing and foot orthosis for PFPS (not, however, as primary interventions), and these should be combined with exercises to reduce individuals' pain (Collins et al., 2018).

Surgical intervention should be the last option after conservative physiotherapy in PFPS treatment has failed (Fulkerson, 2002). Surgery is typically used for malalignment correction, or if the patient continues to display consistent symptoms for 6–12 months after undergoing conservative treatment

(Vora et al., 2017). Surgical options include realignment of the patella and patellectomy (Vora et al., 2017).

There is no perfect treatment yet for PFPS and a little is known about newer interventions like whole-body vibration (WBV) on PFPS population symptoms during PFPS rehabilitation programs, therefore further research is required to investigate the role of this equipment on PFPS. Thus, WBV will be explored in the following section.

1.5 The background of whole-body vibration (WBV)

In 1970, Nasarov and Spivak first introduced the technique of WBV stimuli of 23 Hertz (Hz) combined with a small amplitude to training programmes in athletes, with the goal of enhancing the muscle strength and power of the Soviet athletes during the Olympic Games (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010). By 1994, the training programme used vibration stimuli of 44 Hz combined with an amplitude of 3 millimetres (mm), applied three times per week for a total of three weeks. This programme was used in conjunction with resistance exercises in static standing positions and it was found to increase maximal strength and flexibility by 49%, whereas the resistance exercise alone showed only a 16% increase in maximal muscle strength (Issurin, Liebermann and Tenebaum, 1994). Four years later, in 1998, WBV platforms were first advertised on the market with range of amplitudes (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010). Subsequently, WBV stimuli were increasingly used with the aim of increasing muscle strength during rehabilitation programmes (Machado et al., 2010), joint range of motion, functional movement e.g. sit to stand test and reaching test (Games, Sefton and Wilson, 2015; Hawkey et al., 2016; Jacobs and Burns, 2009), blood flow (Games, Sefton and Wilson, 2015) and muscle power in musculoskeletal conditions (Osawa, Oguma and Ishii, 2013). WBV stimuli could trigger the activation of motor unit integration by mechanical vibration waves, thereby increasing the human body's range of motion (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010). Moreover, researchers have investigated the effect of vibration on pain perception, joint stability, flexibility (Hawkey et al., 2016), bone intensity (Marín-Cascales et al., 2018) and hormone responses (Rittweger, 2010; Eftekhari et al., 2014; Games, Sefton and Wilson, 2015; Hawkey et al., 2016). The findings of these studies showed that WBV stimuli can reduce pain level, delay the decline in joint flexibility, improve Vertebrae

density in females under 65 years, and increase the levels of testosterone and prolactin in individuals with multiple sclerosis. However, those areas are not the focus of this thesis.

A vibration platform is an oscillating platform that transfers vibration waves to the human body. WBV can be transmitted in side-alternating (e.g. Power Maxx), which is displaced in the horizontal axis and the synchronous transmitted in vertical axis. There are three primary directions of oscillation: vertical, rotational and tri-planar. The vertical platforms, such as the neuromechanical stimulation (NEMES) oscillate in a vertical direction only. The rotational platforms oscillate in rotational direction around the axis, such as the Galileo platform. The tri-planar platforms on the other hand, oscillate in both horizontal directions including backward and forward, right and left and vertical directions such as Power Plate and VibraMachine platforms (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010).

The use of resistance exercises that target neuromuscular activity has been established in both strengthening and rehabilitation programmes (Tang et al., 2001; Tagesson et al., 2008; Chang et al., 2014). Resistance exercises can be used to improve an individual's neuromuscular performance and muscle strength by activating a higher number of muscle fibres. These resistance exercises increase the generated muscle force by adding heavy loads of more than 70–80% of individuals' maximum voluntary contraction (MVC) (Pinto et al., 2013). These exercises can be achieved by using weights or external loads. Although traditional bodyweight resistance exercises are typically used in rehabilitation programmes, they can result in small effect on muscle function, due to the absence of significant training loads. Vibration stimuli are now used as external loads as part of resistance training programmes in healthy individuals (Delecluse, Roelants and Verschueren, 2003; Zago et al., 2018). The use of vibration exercises in increasing neuromuscular performance has been investigated in healthy individuals by Zaidell et al. (2013), who identified the mechanism

of vibration via tonic vibration reflex (TVR). However, researchers have debated the effectiveness of vibration stimuli in exercises targeting neuromuscular conditions (Brogårdh, Flansbjerg and Lexell, 2012; Abbasi et al., 2017; Corum et al., 2018; Huang and Pang, 2019). The human body transmits the vibration during muscle spindles contraction and relaxation (Rittweger, 2010), and the vibrations in the muscle and tendon structures begin to alternately elongate and shorten the fibres. Although researchers have studied the use of WBV platforms in increasing neuromuscular performance and muscle power (Osawa, Oguma and Ishii, 2013), the platforms used vary in terms of their parameter settings. It is therefore necessary to further examine the reliability of these platforms' outputs, as well as the effects of platform variables and different exposure times on neuromuscular performance.

1.5.1 WBV parameters

1.5.1.1 Frequency

WBV frequency which is known as the number of oscillation cycles occur over a specific time, typically range from 15 to 60 Hz (Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005). The safety of this range for the human body has been sufficiently investigated (Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005), however there is a distinct lack of evidence detailing the effectiveness of these frequencies' impact on neuromuscular performance (Giombini et al., 2013; Lienhard et al. 2014; Zaidell et al., 2019). EMG signals have been used to evaluate the effects of these frequencies during various body postures on muscle activity by calculating the root mean square (RMS) (Di Giminiani et al., 2013; Carlucci et al., 2016). Krol et al. (2011) found that in squatting positions, higher WBV frequencies significantly increased the VM and VL neuromuscular activity compared to low WBV frequencies however, in other studies, no significant difference in effect was found between frequencies of 30 and 50 Hz (Borges et al., 2017). However, validity of these frequencies was not evaluated and

compared to theoretical values. Therefore, the results regarding the effect of frequency on neuromuscular activity are, at best, inconsistent, and researchers have recommended further study on the validity of these frequencies and effects that various frequencies have on individual muscles (Cardinale and Lim, 2003).

The individualised WBV frequency is a specific frequency that elicit individual's muscle activity higher compared to other frequencies. Although the concept of the individualised frequency has not been assessed in all muscles generally, the individualised frequency which was evaluated on VL muscle activity, found the presence of individualised frequency increases VL muscle activity in healthy participants in the squatting position (Di Giminiani et al., 2010). However, the literature lacks conclusive evaluations of (a) WBV stimuli reliability and validity at particular frequencies, and (b) individualised frequencies in rehabilitation programmes intended for clinical populations. Therefore, these evaluations will be discussed further in Chapters 4 and 5.

1.5.1.2 Peak-to-peak displacement

Peak-to-peak displacement of platforms is the magnitude of change in oscillation wave between positive and negative values, usually ranges from 1-10 mm (Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005). However, most WBV studies included a lower range with a peak-to-peak displacement of 1-4 mm. Studies typically use the manufacturer parameters without comparison to theoretical values. Krol et al. (2011) illustrated the effects of such parameters like peak-to-peak displacements of 2 mm to 4 mm on VL muscle activity during a static squat position. In that study, VL had a significant increase in activation at a displacement of 4 mm compared to 2 mm. The relationships between peak-to-peak displacement, frequency and resultant muscle power were investigated by measuring countermovement jumps, performed by healthy individuals in intervals of sixty seconds to ten minutes, after immediate exposure to WBV stimuli (Adams et al., 2009). In that study, combined

high frequency (40-50 Hz) with low displacement (2-4 mm) and low frequency (30-35 Hz) with high displacement (4-6 mm) showed a significant increase in muscle power during countermovement jumps, however the parameters were not compared to theoretical values. The muscle strength performed through knee flexion and extension using an isokinetic dynamometer were evaluated by Stania et al. (2017), after the exposure to acute WBV stimuli consisting of frequencies of 20-60 Hz combined with peak-to-peak displacement of 2-4 mm. These were conducted three times per week for four weeks (Stania et al., 2017). It was found that a frequency of 60 Hz, paired with a peak-to-peak displacement of 4 mm, elicited a significant increase in muscle strength compared to frequencies of 20 and 40 Hz combined with a displacement of 2 mm (Stania et al., 2017). Moreover, when displacements of 2 and 4 mm were combined with low and high WBV frequencies of 30 and 50 Hz respectively, findings indicated that the 30 Hz frequency showed a higher impact on knee muscle strength compared to 50 Hz (Esmailzadeh et al., 2015). There was no difference in the effect of varying displacements over an eight-week period (Esmailzadeh et al., 2015). The vast majority of literature lacked the evaluation of the actual WBV output parameter values and comparison to theoretical values. Therefore, further evaluation is required for the validity of WBV platform parameters (Chapter 4). Also, it is clear that the effects of manipulating different WBV parameters, such as frequency and peak-to-peak displacement, on muscle strength and power still require further investigation both in healthy individuals and clinical populations.

1.5.1.3 Acceleration

WBV platform acceleration, which is calculated via WBV frequency and peak to peak displacement, can be presented as $Acceleration = 2\pi^2 F^2 D$ (F = frequency, D = peak to peak displacement). This formula can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of WBV outputs by

comparing the resultant acceleration to the theoretical values, (Rauch et al., 2010a). Accelerometers can be placed in the centre of vibration platforms in order to calculate acceleration movement by directly measuring resultant peak acceleration in g units, (1 g being equal to 9.81 m.s⁻² of Earth's gravitational pull) (will be discussed in section 4.2.2.2). Platform acceleration is the key factor in the evaluation of the platform's outputs because the acceleration reflects the platform wave delivery, and therefore researchers use platform acceleration to evaluate both the WBV stimuli and the platform's performance (Rauch et al., 2010; Lienhard et al., 2015). However, few studies evaluate the validity of WBV parameter outputs and comparing it to their theoretical values. Although the WBV acceleration output is recommended to be at a minimum of 18 m.s⁻² for rehabilitation programmes, the vibration acceleration output differs across platforms, according to the respective manufacturer (Lienhard, Vienneau, Nigg, et al., 2015).

The link between the acceleration outputs, frequency and direction of WBV platform needs further evaluation as the direction of WBV platform waves can affect these parameters. The acceleration outputs of both rotational and vertical vibration platforms, when set at frequencies of 20, 25 and 30 Hz, were investigated by Zaidell et al. (2019). In this study, the acceleration output of the vertical platform at 20 Hz (used only in the squatting position to avoid vertical wave transmission to the head) was higher in comparison to the rotational platform (used in both positions as recommended for use in training programmes to obtain the optimal platform outputs), while the acceleration outputs of a rotational platform at 25 and 30 Hz was higher in comparison to vertical platform. However, the calculated accelerations for both platforms did not compare to their theoretical values. Marín and Hazell (2014) found low calculated peak-to-peak displacement, namely 1.07 mm at 50 Hz, compared with readings of 1.54 mm at 30 Hz (Marín and Hazell, 2014). One can conclude, therefore, any investigation into the validity of WBV parameters needs to be

consistent in comparing the calculated acceleration values to their theoretical values for various platform types. Other vibration platforms should also be included in order to facilitate more detailed comparison, for better determining of how efficiently the platform types operate.

1.6 Types of vibration platform

There are three types of WBV platform currently in the market. The first is the rotational (e.g. Galileo) platform, which displaces in the medial-to-distal direction and uses a frequency range of 5-30 Hz, with peak to peak displacement of 1-6 mm. It is thought that Galileo platform causes muscle contraction and relaxation in physiological training (Rittweger, Mutschelknauss and Felsenberg, 2003), therefore side-alternating oscillation is better at increasing muscle power during gait training exercise than all others. Moreover, the Galileo platform produces zero peak to peak displacement in the middle of the platform and increases laterally (both right and left), therefore the vibration waves and displacement can be influenced by the position of the feet (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010). Thus, allowing individuals to vary the amplitude while maintaining the same exposure time.

The second WBV platform type is vertical (e.g. NEMES), which produces vertical mechanical vibrations ranging from 30-50 Hz. The NEMES platform, which is controlled by an external computer. This type of platform is thought to be suitable for improving muscle weakness by increasing the muscle activation to 200% compared to maximum muscle activation with no vibration (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010), although it should not be used for treating neurological conditions because it can increase the susceptibility of muscle fatigue. The third platform type is the tri-planar (e.g. Power Plate and VibraMachine), which predominantly produces waves in the vertical direction, but can also operate horizontally. Developed in the

Netherlands, the Power Plate uses vibration frequencies between 30 and 50 Hz in 5 Hz increments; because of vibration wave directions, the Power Plate platform is most often used for strengthening exercises (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010).

The Galileo and Power Plate platforms have maximum vertical acceleration values of 15 and 8 g units respectively during unloaded condition, measured in frequencies ranged from 5 Hz to 50 Hz, by the researcher accelerometer (Pel et al., 2009). Pel et al. (2009) evaluated the vibration outputs of these platforms according to the direction of the platform waves; the Galileo and Power Plate platforms showed significantly higher vertical direction waves compared to the Power Maxx platforms. Therefore, the Galileo and Power plate platforms mainly vibrate in the vertical direction, whereas the Power Maxx platform mainly vibrates on the horizontal plane (Pel et al., 2009). Also, the acceleration transmissions in ankle joint (closer to WBV platform) for Galileo and Power plate platforms (vertical direction) are higher compared to the knee and hip joints for the same WBV platforms. So far, few studies have investigated the differences between these vibration platforms (Abercromby et al., 2007; Pel et al., 2009; Zaidell et al., 2019). Research evidence focussed on investigation the vibration parameters that control the WBV outputs, such as frequency, acceleration, peak-to-peak displacement, body position and exposure time of each WBV platform without comparing the WBV platforms outputs between different platforms (Stania et al., 2017; Zaidell et al., 2019).

1.7 WBV mechanisms

WBV stimuli mechanisms focus on how the physiological effects of WBV stimuli have been investigated frequently in the literature, however there is no consistency in this physiological effect of WBV mechanism. The most commonly featured mechanism is the TVR, which uses the primary

and secondary muscle spindle endings to transmit the WBV stimuli through muscles (Cardinale and Bosco, 2003; Musumeci, 2017). This functions by stimulating the muscle sensory spindle endings through vibration stimuli and thereby activating the alpha-motoneurons, resulting in the muscle reflex contraction process termed TVR. This increases muscle activation via a rapid change in muscle length, when the muscle is introduced to vibration waves. Both high and low frequencies activate the TVR (Zaidell et al., 2013) by stimulating the muscle spindles, however general consensus suggested that the direct application of the vibration to muscles or tendons shows more effective implications (Bosco, Cardinale and Tsarpela, 1999; McBride, Porcari and Scheunke, 2004; Jones et al., 2017).

Vibration stimuli can also influence different mechanoreceptors on the skin's surface, such as Meissner and Pacinian corpuscles, as well as joint receptors and thermal sensors (Zaidell et al., 2013). These receptors are activated at the beginning of stimulation (Tair et al., 2018). The Meissner corpuscles respond to low vibration frequencies, whereas the Pacinian corpuscles respond to high vibration frequencies above 150 Hz (Tair et al., 2018). In addition to these mechanoreceptors, Merkel cell-neurite complexes and Ruffini endings are steady receptors that require long exposure times in order to activate.

1.7.1 Muscle contraction: muscle spindles

Vibration stimuli affect muscle fibres by influencing the muscle spindles. Stimuli are transmitted to the central nervous system through the afferent motor fibres (Ia afferent and II afferent), thus lengthening the muscle and changing the fibre velocity of muscle spindles which collect the motor signals from the brain through alpha (α) and gamma (γ) motor neurons (Li et al., 2015) The α motor neurons supply skeletal muscle fibres (extrafusal muscle) to produce the required force in the joint, and the γ motor neurons supply the muscle spindle fibres (intrafusal muscle) in order to

send feedback to the muscle during the motor control process. This mechanism indicates the direct implication of WBV stimuli on muscle or tendon. Also, the required stimulus for muscle contraction can be varied according to muscle volume and distance from the stimulus. Figure 1.4 shows the alpha (α) and gamma (γ) motor neurons' muscle contraction process.

Figure 1.4: Muscle contraction process during vibration stimulus (GTO: Golgi tendon organs (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010). Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

1.7.2 Stretch reflex

The process of TVR depends on the stretch reflex which is the common cited in the literature during WBV exercises evaluation. When muscle fibres stretch, the muscle spindle is activated by sending an afferent signal to the spinal cord. If the stimulus is sufficient to activate the muscle spindle, the efferent neurons send a response to the required muscle to contract, and thus alter (or inhibit) the muscle stretch (Zaidell et al., 2013). Additionally, the afferent motor neurons can be sent to the antagonist muscle to relax it and complete the task. This mechanism indicated the direct application of WBV stimuli on muscle or tendon.

There are three types of stretch reflexes. The first is the short-latency response, which is activated after 30 milliseconds (ms) by homonymous Ia and II afferent muscle spindles. The second type is the medium-latency response that occurs after 50–60 ms. The final type is the long latency response, which takes place after 90–100 ms (Petersen et al., 1998; Corden et al., 2000). The TVR is stimulated during the contraction and stretching of the muscle spindle. The spinal cord releases the efferent neurons in order to contract the agonist muscle and inhibit the antagonist, to complete the process of muscle activity. This process is referred to as a reciprocal inhibition reflex (Di Giminiani et al., 2010; Li et al., 2015).

1.7.3 Hoffmann reflex

In 1910, Paul Hoffmann defined the Hoffmann reflex (H-reflex), in which electrical stimulation activates during muscle twitches, through monosynaptic activity in the spinal cord (Palmieri, Ingersoll and Hoffman, 2004). This reflex has been mainly studied in soleus and quadriceps muscles. The H-reflex can be stimulated by the vibration stimuli. This reflex transmits the stimulus (e.g. WBV) directly to the spinal cord without passing through the muscle spindle. The H-reflex mechanism occurs through the Ia afferent axons in the muscle spindle by detecting the low intensity in a short time, before the α motor neurons transmit the response to the muscle. When the stimulus intensity becomes higher than the Ia sensory afferent excitation threshold, the α motor neurons are stimulated directly and cause the muscle fibres to respond to the muscle, an action termed an M-wave (Palmieri, Ingersoll and Hoffman, 2004). The process of evaluating this excitability is conducted through the Ia afferent axons, whereas examining the response from the spinal cord occurs through action potentials via efferent (motor) fibres for the same stimulated muscle (Palmieri, Ingersoll and Hoffman, 2004). The H-reflex amplitude may be sensitive to the environment noise and body position, therefore these factors need to be controlled. WBV stimuli

produce electromagnetic noise which can be counted as the main limitation for H-reflex during evaluating the mechanism of WBV stimuli (Palmieri, Ingersoll and Hoffman, 2004). Figure 1.5 shows the H-reflex mechanism.

Figure 1.5: Hoffmann reflex mechanism (Palmieri, Ingersoll and Hoffman, 2004). Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

1.7.4 Golgi tendon organ

The Golgi tendon organ (GTO) which is found between the muscle and tendon junction, can be sensitive to vibration waves. The function of GTO is to allow transmission vibration wave through muscle fibres. These mechanoreceptors are activated by stretching the tendon and squeezing the collagen fibres during muscle contraction (Pollock et al., 2012). The GTO consists of Ib afferent fibres, which transmit the sensory signal from the muscle fibres to the spine, respond to change at high-threshold levels of muscle tension and connective tissues of the spinal cord. The GTO prevents the maximum potential tension during muscle stretch, thus avoiding injury (Moore, 1984). In addition, the organs respond by contracting to low response levels, when compared with muscle contraction (Brooke and Zehr, 2006). During the response of the tendon organ reflex, the muscle spindle inhibits force production in the agonist muscle and contracts the antagonist muscle

(Moore, 1984; Tortora and Derrickson, 2017). The GTO is slightly less sensitive to local applied vibration than primary and secondary muscle endings (Pollock et al., 2012).

1.7.5 Damping effect

The evaluation of WBV stimuli on muscle fibres can be conducted via the examination of EMG signals (Nigg and Wakeling, 2001; Abercromby et al., 2007). One of the WBV mechanisms is the damping effect, which stimulates muscle contraction and relaxation mechanism. Soft tissues typically oscillate continuously, referred to as the natural frequency (Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005; Rittweger, 2010). The vibration platform produces a contained frequency, while stiffness and body mass are variables that can influence the natural frequency in soft tissues. Furthermore, the body resonator produces a higher vibration amplitude than the platform amplitude, or actuator. This process is called the resonance catastrophe (Rittweger, 2010) and leads to a decrease in the vibration amplitude through the damping of soft tissue (Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005). This damping effect is influenced by stiffness, and the human body's natural frequency which increases as the vibration amplitude rises. The commercial platforms available on the market utilise a range of frequencies that produce a damping effect close to the human body's natural frequency. Also, the damping effect can be influenced by the human muscle size which affects the ability of the muscle absorption of WBV stimuli.

To conclude, WBV mechanisms include involvement of muscle spindles; GTO which are less sensitive to local WBV stimuli; and stretch reflexes. These mechanisms justify the direct use of WBV stimuli applied on muscle or tendon. A further mechanism involving a damping effect can be influenced by human muscles size. All of these mechanisms are thought to increase muscle activity during exposure to vibration stimuli.

1.8 WBV stimuli and exercise (the role of vibration in exercises)

Vibration exercises can either be applied directly to specific muscles or tendons (Jones et al., 2017), or indirectly to a group of muscles via series transmission through muscles, tendons or joints (Lienhard et al., 2017). Indirect vibration stimuli are applied to whole-body structures through the usage of WBV platforms, where individuals stand or squat on the equipment. The main aim of these vibration exercises is to improve lower-limb neuromuscular performance.

An acute effect can be defined as exposure to the WBV for ten minutes or less (Bosco et al., 1999). The WBV stimuli possibly take time up to 10 s to develop when the machine switches on, and this time should be considered in evaluating the acute effects. Furthermore, this short ten-minute exposure period can be divided up to avoid muscle fatigue. This acute exposure to WBV leads to an increase in neuromuscular activity (Krol et al., 2011), and therefore when Roelants et al. (2006) investigated the effect of acute WBV stimuli of 15 and 60 s continuously, individuals rested before exposing themselves to another episode of WBV stimuli. The difference in the acute exposure time across the literature resulted in difficulty in comparing the results between studies.

WBV training is defined as a programme either involving WBV stimuli alone or implemented alongside other strengthening exercises (Abbasi et al., 2017). Training programs include WBV stimuli were investigated by subjective and objective outcome measures in clinical populations (Corum et al., 2018; Fischer et al., 2019). These programs were recommended to be implemented in rehabilitation programs for some clinical populations. Moreover, these programs can be introduced either as a single intervention or in combination with strengthening exercises. The effect of WBV training including static and dynamic squats on ankle plantar flexor strength and power in healthy individuals was compared to exercise training alone including calf raises exercise and static and dynamic squat during eight weeks program (Rees, Murphy and Watsford, 2008). In

that study, the effect of WBV training which assessed by isokinetic dynamometer, increased the ankle plantar flexor strength and power compared to exercise training alone. However, further research is required to evaluate WBV training programs on quadriceps strength compared to other strength exercises alone. Moreover, WBV stimuli showed significant increase in the lower limb muscles activity including tibialis anterior, peroneus longus and gastrocnemius during squatting with high frequency (60 Hz) compared to low frequency (20 Hz) (Tor et al., 2019). The study lacked the evaluation of neuromuscular activity in the quadriceps muscle, and reliability and the validity of the WBV platform parameter outputs. The single/acute intervention session illustrated by Roelants et al. (2006) and Marín et al. (2012) showed that the acute WBV stimuli increased VM muscle activity during a static squat position in healthy individuals without evaluation the WBV platform outputs validity. However, Corum et al. (2018) evaluated the effectiveness of WBV stimuli combined with home exercises including knee extensions and double-legged wall squat, compared to programmes solely utilising home exercises in individuals with PFPS. After eight weeks of exposure to vibration stimuli, participants' muscle strength significantly increased, and pain levels decreased compared to the group who only participated in an exercise programme (Corum et al., 2018), however the quadriceps muscle activity was not evaluated and a fixed frequency of 30 Hz has been applied. Previous work had examined the effect of exercise programmes incorporating vibration stimuli of 40 Hz on balance performance during a period of four weeks (Ritzmann et al., 2014). This was achieved by examining the balance control in healthy participants compared to members of a control group, who participated in the same programme without vibration stimuli (Ritzmann et al., 2014). After the four-week intervention, the training programme including vibration stimuli showed an increase in balance control of 13% (pre and post), compared with an increase of only 6% in the controlled group. There was no justification

for selecting frequency of 40 Hz during exercise and the possible effect of others WBV frequencies on individuals balance control needs further investigation. Also, a systematic review conducted by Awan, Khan and Perveen, (2017), investigated the effect of WBV stimuli on the balance of elderly individuals compared to a control group performed exercises only. In that study, the WBV stimuli of five weeks training significantly increased the elderly individuals balance compared to control group perform exercises only. Therefore, vibration stimuli can be used effectively either during acute exposure or long-term training on muscle strength and power (Abercromby et al., 2007; Corum et al., 2018). However, more investigation is required to evaluate the effectiveness of combining acute WBV stimuli or training with strengthening exercises as part of rehabilitative programmes in patient population.

1.9 Quadriceps Muscle activity during acute WBV

Since vibration stimuli influence the muscle spindles, EMG measurements can be used to evaluate the effect of acute vibration stimuli on muscle activity (Muñoz et al., 2006; Abercromby et al., 2007; Hazell, Jakobi and Kenno, 2007). Di Giminiani et al. (2015) found EMG signals to be a reliable tool in determining the effectiveness of acute exposure of WBV stimuli on quadriceps muscle activity in the static squatting position. So far, the research evidence highlighted the acute effect of WBV stimuli on quadriceps muscle in healthy individuals by acute neuromuscular activity (Krol et al., 2011, Hazell, Kenno and Jakobi, 2015). However, the methodologies of these studies have not been assessed yet to synthesise the effectiveness of WBV stimuli on quadriceps muscle activity in healthy individuals by EMG system which is the focus of this research. Also, the difference in these research methods may give an insight into how WBV stimuli influence quadriceps muscle activity during exercise for possible implications in clinical populations with quadriceps muscle weakness. The following table details various studies that have evaluated the

effects of WBV stimuli on the neuromuscular activity of the quadriceps in healthy individuals (Table 2).

Table 2. Studies investigated the effect of WBV stimuli on quadriceps neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals. VM: vastus medialis. VL: vastus lateralis, RF: rectus femoris, EMG: electromyography.

Author(s), year	Participant details	Platform type	Acute exposure of	Outcome measures	Results
Abercromby et al., 2007	16 healthy; (9 male and 7 female)	Power Plate and Galileo	15 s (total 3 min) during static and dynamic unloaded squats	EMG of VL muscle	EMG increase in tested muscle in static > dynamic squat ($p < 0.05$)
Avelar et al., 2013	34 healthy participants	Vertical platform	10 s (two tests with WBV and two tests without WBV) during static squats	EMG of VL muscle	No significant differences in VL EMG between vibration and no vibration ($p > 0.05$)
Borges et al., 2017	40 healthy individuals	Power Plate	15 s (frequency 30 Hz and 50 Hz) during static squats	EMG of VL muscle	EMG increase in all tested frequencies ($p < 0.05$)
Cardinale and Lim, 2003	16 healthy participants	NEMES platform	60 (frequency 30 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) during static squats	EMG of VL muscle	EMG increase in all tested frequencies ($p < 0.05$)
Cochrane et al., 2009	9 healthy participants	Galileo	15 s (6 Hz) during static squats	EMG of VL muscle	EMG increase in vibration compared to 0 Hz ($p < 0.05$)
Di Giminiani et al., 2013	20 healthy participants	NEMES platform	20 s (20 Hz to 55 Hz) during static squats	EMG of VL muscle	EMG increase in all tested frequencies compared to baseline 0 Hz ($p < 0.05$)
Di Giminiani et al., 2015	25 healthy participants	NEMES vertical platform	20 s (frequency from 20 Hz to 55 Hz) during static squats	EMG of VM and VL muscles	EMG increase in all tested muscles compared to baseline 0 Hz ($p < 0.05$)
Fratini et al., 2009	15 healthy participants	TSEM vertical	20 s (frequency 12.8, 17.9, 23.3, 28.5, 33.9, 39.2 and 44.5 Hz)	EMG of VM, RF and VL muscles	EMG increase in VM and VL tested muscles compared to baseline 0 Hz ($p < 0.05$)
Hazell, Jakobi and Kenno, 2007	10 healthy participants	Vertical oscillations (WAVE)	30 s (10 trials total with frequencies 25 Hz, 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) during 5 trials in static squat and 5 trials during dynamic squats	EMG of VL muscle	EMG increase in all tested frequencies compared to baseline 0 Hz in both static and dynamic squats ($p < 0.05$)
Hazell, Kenno and Jakobi, 2015	13 healthy individuals	Vertical oscillations (WAVE)	A total of 2 s of dynamic squatting (8 sets of squats) 4 loaded and 4 unloaded x frequency 0Hz, 25 Hz, 35 Hz and 45 Hz	EMG of VL	EMG increase at tested frequency of 45 Hz compared to baseline 0 Hz in both loaded and unloaded dynamic squats ($p < 0.05$)
Krol et al., 2011	29 healthy individuals	Fitvibe 600 platform vertical platform	30 s (total trials 8 trials 6 trials with frequency 20 Hz, 40 Hz and 60 Hz, 2 without vibration)	EMG of VM and VL muscles	EMG increase for VM and VL in all vibration frequencies compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Lee, 2017	10 healthy participants	Vibration exercise machines (TT2590P)	10 s (frequency 10Hz, 25 Hz and 40 Hz)	EMG of VL	EMG increase for VL in all vibration frequencies compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)

Lienhard et al., 2014	18 participants	Power Plate platform	30 s (25, 30, 35 and 40 Hz)	EMG of RF, VM and VL muscles	EMG increase for VM at frequency 25 and 35 Hz, and VL increase at frequency 30, 35 and 40 Hz compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Lienhard, Vienneau, Friesenbichler, et al., 2015	58 healthy participants	Side-alternating platform (TBS 100 A)	20 s (ranges from 6 to 16 Hz) during static squats	EMG of VM and VL muscles	EMG increase for VM and VL in all vibration platforms (vibration mode) when compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Lienhard, Vienneau, Nigg, et al., 2015	30 healthy individuals	Side-alternating platform (TBS 100 A)	20 s (frequency 6 Hz, 14 Hz and 16 Hz) during static squats	EMG of VM and VL muscles	EMG increase for VM and VL in all vibration platforms (vibration mode) when compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Marín and Hazell, 2014	28 healthy individuals	Power Plate platform	30 s (total of 4 exercises involved vibration (frequency 30 and 50 Hz) and unstable surface) during static squats	EMG of VM and VL muscles.	EMG increase VM muscle in vibration with 30 Hz compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Marin et al., 2009	10 healthy participants	Vertical platform (Free-Motion Fitness iTonic)	30 s (4 with 30 Hz vibration and 1 isometric without vibration) during static squats	EMG of VL muscle	EMG increase in vibration compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Marin et al., 2012	20 healthy adults	Vertical platform Fitvibe	15 s (total 6 trials; frequency from 25 Hz, 35 Hz and 45 Hz low and high amplitude) during static squats	EMG of VM and VL muscles	EMG increase in all muscles during vibration, not mentioned compared to EMG signals at rest time ($p < 0.05$)
Marín et al., 2012	14 healthy adults	Power Plate platform	15 s (total of 12 tests; frequency 0, 30 Hz and 46 Hz with low and high amplitude) during static squats	EMG of VL muscle	EMG increase in vibration compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Muñoz et al., 2006)	16 healthy individuals	Vertical sinusoidal vibration with Power Plate	10 s (30Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) during static squats	EMG of VM, VL and RF muscles	EMG increase in all muscles compared to no vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Perchthaler, Horstmann and Grau, 2013	51 healthy individuals	Side-alternating vibration platform (Galileo Fitness)	15 s (total 15 static squats; frequency 6 Hz, 12 Hz, 18 Hz, 24 Hz and 30 Hz x 3 amplitudes)	EMG of RF, VM and VL muscles	EMG increase in all muscles during vibration, compared to MVC ($p < 0.05$)
Pollock et al., 2010	12 healthy individuals	RV platform (Galileo 2000)	7 s (frequency from 5 Hz to 30 Hz with low and high amplitude) in the standing position	EMG of RF muscle	EMG increase in RF muscle compared to MVC ($p < 0.05$)
Ritzmann, Gollhofer and Kramer, 2013	18 healthy participants	Side-alternating synchronous vibration platform (Power Plate)	10 s (frequency ranged from 5 Hz to 30 Hz and two amplitude) during static squats	EMG of RF and VM muscles.	EMG increase in both platforms (side-alternating > vertical compared to 0 Hz vibration ($p < 0.05$))

Roelants et al., 2006	15 healthy participants	Power Plate platform vertical vibration	20 s (frequency 35 Hz)	EMG of RF, VM and VL muscles.	EMG increase in all muscles increase compared to 0 Hz vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Tankisheva et al., 2013	8 healthy participants	Power Plate platform	30 s (3 trial for each frequency; 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz with low and high amplitude) during static exercises	EMG of VM and RF muscles	EMG increase in VM muscle at frequency 30 Hz with high amplitude and RF muscle at frequency 30 with high and low amplitude, compared to 0 Hz vibration ($p < 0.05$)
Zaidell et al., 2019	20 healthy participants	Rotational V Galileo and Vertical V (Fit- vibe Medical)	20 s (frequency; 20, 25, and 30 Hz) during standing and squat positions.	EMG of RF muscle	EMG increase in RF 30 Hz compared to 0 Hz vibration ($p < 0.05$)

1.10 WBV contraindication and possible side effects

Although positive effects of WBV on neuromuscular performance (such as muscle strength and power performance) have been demonstrated, possible side-effects have also been identified, such as hearing loss or vestibular damage (Pettersson et al., 2012; Najarkola et al., 2013). The use of WBV stimuli in individuals with the following conditions are contraindicated, according to Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, (2010):

- acute hernias,
- discopathy,
- spondylolysis,
- severe diabetes,
- epilepsy,
- recent infections,
- severe migraines,
- tumours,
- recently placed intrauterine devices,
- metal pins or plates,
- kidney stones,
- organ failure,
- clinical conditions in which WBV is not indicated.

Possible side effects including decrease in blood pressure, hypoglycaemia in individuals with diabetes, nausea, dizziness, and itching can indicate the using of inappropriate or high WBV training intensity (Albasini, Krause and Rembitzki, 2010). However, other side effects are generally stated from the manufacturer and overall very little research has been completed on investigating commonly used WBV parameters (i.e. relatively low frequency & low peak-to-peak displacement). Often the details of side effects during typical WBV programmes are not

stated. This indicates the side effects for WBV stimuli should be investigated with regards to typical exposure time and WBV parameters. Although it is important to highlight possible side effects of WBV, the vast majority of studies using WBV did not report any side effects (Roelants et al., 2006; Wilcock et al., 2009; Marin et al., 2012). However, nine articles evaluating WBV programmes have been analysed in review conducted by Wilcock et al., (2009). The findings of these nine studies concluded one participant developed pain in the tibia and dropped out of the study during the second week out of 11 weeks. The WBV programme including squatting on the WBV platform with frequency of 30 Hz and 16 mm peak to peak displacement (16mm p-t-p displacement assumed from the stated 8mm amplitude) (de Ruiter et al., 2003). The one reported side effect suggested from a WBV programme which is higher than other typical WBV parameters.

Therefore, a safe and appropriate protocol should be identified before being implemented in rehabilitation programmes, in order to avoid the risk of further injury. The effectiveness of these vibration-based exercises also depends on the parameters of the vibration platform used and WBV platform type, which would affect the amount of muscle force generated. Another point discussed in the literature was the effect of standing with full knee extension which may increase the transmit of WBV stimuli to the brain (Dolny and Reyes, 2008). Also, isometric contractions were found to increase vibration transmission during increases in knee angle (Abercromby et al., 2007). Therefore, the recommended position should include ankle, knee and hip flexion, or if standing with heels off or only the forefoot in contact to decrease the transmission of WBV to the head (Dolny and Reyes, 2008). Moreover, the WBV stimuli was recommended to be higher than 20 Hz frequency, low peak-to-peak displacement (2-4mm),

short exposure time 20-60 s, and should be avoided for individuals with hypertension (Mester, Kleinöder and Yue, 2006)

1.11 Summary

PFPS which is characterised by anterior knee pain, is a multifactorial condition which can be strength deficits, or lower limb malalignment. PFPS can be treated by non-surgical and surgical interventions. The primary non-surgical intervention is physiotherapy rehabilitation which includes hip and knee motor control exercises. However, the optimal exercise programme for individuals with PFPS needs further investigation. Also, the role of new interventions such as WBV in PFPS requires further evaluation. WBV stimuli treatment is being increasingly employed in rehabilitation programmes. Various mechanisms have been outlined explaining the effects of vibrations on the human body, although consensus regarding the superiority of one mechanism over another does not yet exist. Certain vibration parameters have been proven to be effective on the human body, particularly on the lower limbs, evidenced through research on healthy individuals and clinical populations. Therefore, it would be of substantial benefit to investigate the reliability and validity of the available WBV parameter outputs in order to obtain a clear comparison between WBV platform types. This would then help to determine the platform most relevant to each training purpose. However, the influence of body weight on vibration platform parameters requires further evaluation, so that it can be fully taken into account when coordinating programmes. Nevertheless, WBV has been found effective in its effects on neuromuscular activity, in both healthy individuals and clinical populations, particularly regarding the quadriceps muscles. The role of the VM muscle has been assessed in relation to the VM:VL ratio and the possible implications of that imbalance in the identification of PFPS characteristics, risk factors and

management strategies. Although the reliability of WBV outputs has been investigated on healthy individuals by neuromuscular activities, determining the effectiveness of acute WBV stimuli requires further study amongst healthy people and individuals with PFPS. Answering these questions will help to establish WBV training protocols focusing on neuromuscular activity in lower-limb muscles, for the benefit of both healthy individuals and clinical populations. In order to fully explore the implications of WBV stimuli further regarding these variables, the following aims have been formulated.

1.12 Research aims

The goal of this thesis is to investigate the function of WBV parameter outputs during static double-leg squats performed by healthy individuals, as well as to determine the role of WBV stimuli in increasing quadriceps neuromuscular activity. Additional areas of evaluation include comparing the effects of squatting position exercises involving WBV stimuli on quadriceps muscle activity in healthy individuals and a clinical population.

This thesis consists of seven studies. The first four are experimental, determining the validity and reliability of WBV platform parameters, resistance Thera-Bands and the EMG neuromuscular system. Study 5 is also experimental, evaluating the reliability of individualised WBV stimuli on neuromuscular activity. Studies 6 and 7 are both examining the effect of acute WBV stimuli on neuromuscular activity during rehabilitation exercises.

The research aims of this study are as follows:

- 1- To evaluate the effect of various squatting exercises on acute VM muscle activity in healthy individuals and patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS) populations; systematic review and meta-analysis;

- 2- To determine the validity and reliability of two whole-body vibration (WBV) platform outputs, using different body weights and force outputs produced from standard blue and green Thera-Bands;
- 3- To determine the inter-day reliability of the Delsys Trigno Avanti electromyography (EMG) system during acute WBV stimuli;
- 4- To assess the inter-day reliability of individualised WBV stimuli on acute VM neuromuscular activity during static double-leg squats in healthy individuals;
- 5- To examine different static double-leg squats involving WBV stimuli with evaluated individualised frequencies and resisted hip adduction with Thera-Bands, on acute VM and VL neuromuscular activities in healthy individuals;
- 6- To evaluate different static double-leg squats involving WBV stimuli set at 40 Hz and resisted hip adduction with Thera-Bands, on acute VM and VL neuromuscular activity in individuals with PFPS.

Chapter 2

The effect of variations of static double leg squat exercises on VM neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals and patellofemoral pain syndrome populations: A systematic review and meta-analysis.

2.1 Abstract

Objective: The imbalance between vastus medialis (VM) and vastus lateralis (VL) muscle activity is a major cause of patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS). Static double leg squats are commonly used in strengthening programs targeting VM but the effects of variants of this exercise (e.g. unstable surfaces, hip adduction) are less well known. The aim of this meta-analysis was to evaluate variants of static double leg squat exercises on acute VM neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS.

Methods: CINAHL, PubMed, Science Direct, Web of Science and Medline were searched in February 2020 for studies investigating the effect of static double leg exercises with unstable surfaces including whole body vibration (WBV) or hip adduction on VM activation. Two independent reviewers assessed studies for inclusion criteria, Risk of Bias and PEDro scale. Effect sizes of all included studies was calculated by extracting the mean and standard deviation.

Results: A total of 286 participants were included across 12 studies. There is moderate to strong evidence that: 1) WBV positively affects VM activation in healthy individuals $d = 1.76$ (95% confidence interval (CI) [0.11 – 3.40], $p = 0.004$) but no similar studies in PFPS populations are available; and 2) resisted hip adduction in squatting has a positive effect on VM activation in individuals with PFPS ($d = 0.52$, 95% CI [0.07, 0.97], $p = 0.02$) but not in healthy individuals ($d = 0.31$, 95% CI [-0.28, 0.89], $p = 0.3$).

Conclusions: The beneficial effects of WBV in healthy individuals and resisted hip adduction in individuals with PFPS on acute VM neuromuscular activation during static double leg squatting are evidenced. These exercises should be further evaluated in PFPS to provide evidence-based practice in a clinical setting.

Keywords: Patellofemoral pain syndrome, Vastus Medialis Muscle, Whole Body Vibration, Resisted Hip Adduction.

2.2 Introduction

Patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS, also known as ‘Runner’s knee’) is a primary cause of severe knee pain and debilitation (Dixit et al., 2007). The condition is very common globally and affects tens of millions annually. In the United Kingdom, PFPS prevalence among the general population is 23% (Smith et al., 2018). Furthermore, PFPS accounts for between 11–17% of all knee pain presentations, and 25–40% of all clinical knee complaints in total (Crossley et al., 2016). Individuals aged between 50-59 are thought to be most at risk of developing PFPS (Glaviano et al., 2015). PFPS is a multifactorial condition; Merchant and colleagues (2017) introduced seven possible abnormalities observed in PFPS (Vastus Medialis Obliquus deficiency, medial patellofemoral ligament laxity, lateral retinaculum tightness, increased quadriceps (Q) angle, hip abductor weakness, patella alta and trochlear dysplasia) which should be evaluated in patients with PFPS symptoms. Moreover, quadriceps strength deficits and dynamic lower limb malalignment were defined as consistent evidence-based risk factors (Papadopoulos, Stasinopoulos and Ganchev, 2015). This is particularly relevant as numerous studies have shown that an imbalance or dysfunction in vastus medialis (VM) relative to vastus lateralis (VL) muscle activation can result in patella maltracking, namely a lateral maltracking due to VL over-activation and/or VM under-activation (Emami et al., 2007; Fagan and Delahunt, 2008; Ng, Zhang and Li, 2008). Therefore, aberrant VM activation is hypothesised to be linked with PFPS. In addition to these risk factors for PFPS, a recent systematic review and meta-analysis (Neal et al., 2019) also identified higher hip abduction strength as a risk factor in adolescents. To date, several physiotherapy interventions have been evaluated and reviewed previously to evaluate the efficacy of physiotherapy-based interventions in PFPS populations (Ryan and Rowe, 2006; Dixit et al., 2007; Fagan and Delahunt, 2008; Ng, Zhang and Li, 2008; Park and Stefanyshyn, 2011; Crossley et al., 2016). The most

common physiotherapy-based interventions for individuals with PFPS include muscle strengthening exercises which aim to ensure optimal hip and knee motor control (Bolgla et al., 2011). Particularly, through targeting the Gluteus Medius (GM) and Vastus Medialis (VM) muscles respectively by exercises significantly enhance individuals with PFPS function activities (Hamada et al., 2017). Straight leg raising, knee extensions (either as weight-bearing or non-weight-bearing exercises), and different depths of squatting depending on knee flexion angle are traditional exercises that have been suggested to be efficacious in increasing VM activation and correcting patella malalignment (Bolgla, Shaffer and Malone, 2008; Marín and Hazell, 2014; Collins et al., 2018). There is evidence to suggest that squatting with 60-90° knee flexion angles positively activates VM (Tang et al., 2001; Marchetti et al., 2016). Furthermore, hip and knee strengthening exercises in individuals with PFPS were shown to reduce pain more effectively than exercise programmes containing knee exercise only (Razeghi et al., 2010). The 2016 and 2018 consensuses and a systematic review by Elliott et al. (2018) recommended combined hip and knee exercise in PFPS rehabilitation programmes (Crossley et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2018; Elliott et al., 2018). There is a plethora of evidence on the role of hip motor control, in particular around activating GM in individuals with PFPS (e.g. Santos et al., 2015; Azizi et al., 2019), however the evidence for motor control exercises of the knee only, such as exercises to activate VM remains inconclusive. Importantly, it is suggested that the various evidence-based treatments for VM muscle strengthening in PFPS may only be temporary, as pain manifests when patients resume their normal activities (Petersen et al., 2014; RA et al., 2015; Crossley et al., 2016). Therefore, the efficacy of modified variations of traditional VM exercises should be explored.

Currently, there are several studies which have evaluated variations of the static squat exercise including WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction in individuals with PFPS (Coqueiro et al., 2005;

Miao et al., 2015; Corum et al., 2018) and squat exercise unstable surfaces in healthy individuals (Hyong and Ho, 2013; Parekh and Gaur, 2015). Once emerging area is the use of whole body vibration (WBV) in a clinical setting. WBV is defined as oscillatory stimuli often transmitted to user on a platform, and the user may be either holding a static position or perform a dynamic movement (Bidonde et al., 2017). WBV stimuli typically uses a frequency of 15–60 Hz and peak to peak displacement of 1–10 mm (Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005; Marín and Hazell, 2014, Stania et al., 2017) and is thought to elicit increased muscle activity (Roelants et al., 2006; Perchthaler, Horstmann and Grau, 2013; Lienhard et al., 2015). WBV stimuli used recently in strengthen the VM muscle during static squatting while the resisted adduction and unstable surfaces are knee motor control exercises used for long time in physiotherapy clinical practice to elicit VM muscle despite the fact that these exercises have not been sufficiently supported scientifically and required further evaluation.

A meta-analysis provides a robust method to summarize and evaluate evidence-based practice and allows health care professionals to make informed decisions on the efficacy of interventions (Ganeshkumar and Gopalakrishnan, 2013). Therefore, this meta-analysis will focus on studies which have evaluated variations of the traditional static double leg squat exercise that target VM, these being WBV stimuli, squats on unstable surfaces and resisted adduction. Studies in healthy individuals free from knee pain and individuals with PFPS will be considered. The potential impact of these different static squat exercises may reduce the incidence of PFPS, improve treatment outcomes in individuals with PFPS, increase the prospects of recovery and successful return to activities of daily living for general populations or return to performance sports in athletes.

Therefore, the objective of this analysis was to determine whether VM neuromuscular activity during squatting could be significantly increased in healthy individuals and PFPS populations with

the introduction of the following variations of the static double leg squat exercise (as defined in the subsequent methods section):

- WBV stimuli.
- Unstable surfaces.
- Resisted hip adduction.

2.3 Methods

This meta-analysis was completed in accordance with evidence-based Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis “PRISMA” guidelines, which seek to ensure the robustness of such systematic and meta-analytical investigations (Liberati et al., 2009).

2.3.1 PICO

The specific study characteristics are shown in the Table 3, PICO model helps to identify the search terms in literature.

Table 3. Study PICO, including the identification of PICO that was used in the meta-analysis.

Population (P)	Healthy (free from knee pain) and/or PFPS cohorts
Intervention (I)	Static double leg squat exercises with either (1) Whole Body Vibration (WBV), (2) other unstable surfaces (3) resisted hip adduction.
Comparison (C)	Acute neuromuscular activity of VM muscle during standard conventional squat against the intervention conditions.
Outcome measures (O)	Electromyographic data of VM normalised against a maximum voluntary contraction and non-normalised VM signal.

For this meta-analysis, the following electronic databases were surveyed; CINAHL, PubMed, Science Direct, Web of Science and Medline. The search was completed in February 2020 using keyword combinations as described in Box 1.

Box1. Search strategy
PFPS OR Patellofemoral pain syndrome OR patellar tracking
AND
EMG OR Electromyography OR electrical activity OR onset of Activation
AND
Vastus medialis OR VM muscle OR quadriceps imbalance
AND
Squat OR squatting OR double leg squat OR double leg semi squat OR static squat

2.3.2 Inclusion Criteria

According to the search parameters described, the following inclusion criteria was utilised: Randomised control trials (RCTs) and cross-sectional studies investigating acute VM neuromuscular activation in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS were included with a specific focus on the effect of static double leg squat exercises techniques (for example a pre- and post-intervention comparison at least one of the following:

- A comparison between static double leg squat exercises with either (1) Whole Body Vibration (WBV), (2) other unstable surfaces (3) resisted hip adduction.
- Evaluation of the above static double leg squat exercises between healthy individuals and PFPS populations during squatting.

Furthermore, all articles included in this meta-analysis were available in full text and in English.

2.3.3 Exclusion criteria

- Studies which included participants diagnosed with PFPS symptoms combined with other pathological conditions (for example, osteoarthritis, ligament pathologies; anterior or posterior cruciate ligament injuries, patella subluxation).
- Studies which included children under 18 years old or older participants above 70 years.

- Studies which included exercises with multi-modal interventions (for example, WBV or uneven surface with electrical modalities).
- Articles published in a language other than English or prior to the year 2000 (given that the evaluated exercises pertain to be recently published articles).
- The article full text could not be obtained after contacting authors (by email).
- Studies including subjective outcome measures only, or studies which did not evaluate neuromuscular outcome measures.
- Studies which did not evaluate VM neuromuscular activation during the specified variations of the static double leg squat.

2.3.4 Data Extraction and Statistical Analysis

The review process was performed in two separate stages. The first stage comprised the assessment of article titles by the primary researcher (DQ) and was carried out between 1/11/2019 to 29/2/2020 using the aforementioned databases. Details of the included studies are illustrated in Appendix 1 (including publication title, date of publication, journal, study design, participants, intervention, outcome measures, and results). The random effects model was used to evaluate differences between all continuous pooled data by calculating standardised difference and effect size for each exercise. This was based on the assumption that the real difference between studies is not by coincidence, and due to small sample size in included studies. Increase VM muscle activity showed a positive effect in effect size, while the negative effect indicated decrease in VM muscle activity.

2.3.5 Study methodological quality assessment

Study methodologies were assessed via a Risk of Bias (ROB) table in Review Manager (software version 5.3). The ROB table included 6 main sections; evaluated participant allocation, intervention randomization, investigator and participant blinding to procedure and to outcome measures, and whether the results of the research were clearly delivered.

Secondly, the PEDro scale also was used to assess the methods quality of the studies included. The PEDro scale consists of 11 questions and each question is scored as 0 or 1. Question 1 assessed study eligibility criteria, and although this was evaluated, it was not included in the final score (PEDro scale, 1999). Therefore, a maximum score of 10 was possible for any one study. A PEDro score of at least 6/10 was considered high methodological quality (Ferreira, Resende and Roriz, 2017).

2.4 Results

2.4.1 Study characteristics

Studies included in this meta-analysis were cross sectional studies or of a repeated measures study design, which evaluated either Whole Body Vibration (WBV), other unstable surfaces and resisted hip adduction exercise during static double leg squat. This search yielded 9165 articles as well as 4 articles which were identified through cited references during the eligibility stage. The final set of 12 studies included in this meta-analysis included 10 studies investigated WBV and unstable surfaces exercises in healthy individuals and 2 studies evaluated resisted hip adduction exercise in individuals with PFPS and healthy individuals. The sample sizes of these 12 studies ranged between 8 and 30 individuals. A total of 286 participants were included across all studies with a mean age of 24.18 (± 3.9) years.

2.4.2 Search Outcome

Therefore, a total of 9169 potentially relevant articles were identified through the initial database search (Figure 2.1). After duplicates were removed, this number was reduced to 630 articles. Then, the second stage of review process completed independently by the primary researcher (DQ) and a second reviewer (MS). 491 articles were removed, including review articles ($n = 98$); combined pathologies or combined interventions ($n = 383$), participants younger than 18 or older than 70

years (n = 2), not in English or prior to the year 2000 (n = 3), or full article text not available after contacting authors (by email) (n = 5). A total of 139 of these articles met the inclusion criteria following abstract screening. From 139 articles, only those 46 articles with full-text availability, objective outcomes measures and static double leg squat exercises were assessed for inclusion. Further eligibility testing based on the assessed outcomes and participant's inclusion criteria reduced the number of articles to a total of 12. These 12 studies were subsequently included in the quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis) (Figure 2.1). Reviewers independently assessed the abstracts and full-text of all articles included and article inclusion / exclusion was via agreement. A third reviewer was available if the two reviewers could not reach consensus on any article, however the third reviewer process was used on one article only (Sian Irish et al. 2010).

Figure 2.1: Flow-chart of the process of the selected studies, including the identification of potential studies, the screening steps, eligibility testing and identification of the studies that were included in the meta-analysis.

2.4.3 ROB assessment and PEDro scale

Table 4 displays the final 12 studies included in the meta-analysis and which were subjected to ROB assessment and allocated low, unclear or high risk of bias.

Table 5 displays the PEDro scale for included 12 studies. For both the quality assessment, two independent reviewers evaluated the included study methodologies.

Table 4. Methodological quality of the 12 included studies. Rows represent included studies from the analysis. Columns represent the 7 different quality considerations made during the risk of bias assessment.

	Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias)	Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Other bias
Coqueiro et al., 2005 (healthy+ PFPS)	?	?	?	?	+	-	+
Hertel et al., 2004	?	?	-	?	?	-	+
Hyong and Ho, 2013 (healthy)	?	?	-	?	?	+	-
Krol K. et al. 2011 (healthy)	?	?	?	?	+	+	-
Lee et al., 2016 (healthy)	?	?	?	?	+	-	-
Marín & Hazell, 2014 (healthy)	?	?	?	?	+	+	-
Miao et al., 2015 (healthy + PFPS)	?	?	?	?	+	-	-
Parekh and Gaur, 2015	?	?	?	?	+	-	-
Park et al., 2015 (healthy)	?	?	?	?	+	?	-
Roelants et al, 2006 (healthy)	?	?	?	?	+	+	-
Saeterbakken and Fimland, 2013 (Healthy)	?	?	?	?	+	-	+
Sian e. Irish et al., 2010 (Healthy)	?	?	?	?	+	+	+

‘Other Bias’ is defined as publication bias due to significant positive results.

Table 5. PEDro scale methodological quality for 12 included studies (PEDro scale, 1999).

Study	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Total PEDro score
Coquerio et al. (2005)	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	4
Hertel et al. (2004)	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	6
Hyong and Ho. (2013)	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	6
Krol et al. (2011)	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5
Lee et al. (2016)	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	6
Marin & Hazell (2014)	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5
Miao et al. (2015)	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	4
Parekh and Gaur. (2015)	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	6
Park et al. (2015)	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5
Roelants et al. (2006)	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5
Saeterbakken and Fimland. (2013)	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5
Sian Irish et al. (2010)	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5

2.4.4. Squatting with WBV increases neuromuscular activity of VM muscle in healthy individuals.

Three studies (totalling 72 participants) evaluated the effect of acute WBV stimuli on VM activation (Figure 2.2). The standard mean difference effect size (d) found for all WBV studies on VM muscle activity was 1.76 (95% confidence interval (CI) [0.11 – 3.40]).

Figure 2.2: Comparison of WBV stimuli effect on vastus medialis muscle activity in healthy individuals.

Furthermore, an overall positive effect of WBV on VM muscle activity was observed by the application of a random effects model. Marín and Hazell (2014) and Krol et al. (2011) investigated the effect of different vibration frequencies on electromyography (EMG) signals during double squatting. Marín and Hazell (2014) evaluated the VM neuromuscular activity during double leg half squat for 30 s each trial in squat on stable surface with no WBV stimuli, unstable surface with 30 Hz WBV and squat on unstable surface with 50 Hz WBV. There was no change in VM muscle activity found during using an unstable surface above the WBV platform with a 30 Hz or 60 Hz frequency compared to squat with no WBV stimuli ($d = 0.19$, 95% [-0.34 to 0.72]). Krol and colleagues (2011) concluded that squat with WBV stimuli with a frequency of 60 Hz resulted in the highest levels of VM activation compared to the same position without WBV stimuli ($d = 1.10$, 95% [0.55 to 1.66]), but this study did not use an additional unstable surface on the WBV platform. Roelants et al. (2006) found that a single-leg squat is the preferred squat position to adopt on a WBV platform to increase VM activity compared to squat with no vibration stimuli ($d = 4.48$, 95% [3.07 to 5.89]). The heterogeneity (I^2) and variation between studies was significant ($I^2 = 94\%$, $p =$

0.04). No studies investigated the effect of different WBV stimuli on VM neuromuscular activation in PFPS populations.

2.4.5 Unstable surfaces do not increase VM muscle neuromuscular activity during squatting in healthy individuals.

A total of five studies (n= 186 participants) were included which investigated the use of different uneven surfaces (for example: rubber plate, foam surface and balance core) during squatting in healthy populations. The uneven surfaces were found to be not effective in elicit the VM activity in healthy individuals (d = 0.25, 95% CI [-0.14 to 0.65], $p = 0.20$). The differences between the studies were considered low ($I^2 = 71%$) (Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.3: Comparison of unstable surface exercises effect on vastus medialis muscle activity in healthy individuals.

Saeterbakken and Fimland (2013) examined 3 unstable surfaces: balance core, Bosu Ball and Power Board. None these three exercises were found to have significant effects on VM muscle activity compared to squat alone. In contrast, in other studies, the static double leg squat on rubber plate surfaces resulted in a significant increase in VM activity (d= 1.39, 95% [0.55 to 2.23]) (Hyong and Ho, 2013) and (d= 1.09, 95% [0.54 to 1.63]) (Parekh and Gaur, 2015) compared to

hard plate surface and concrete floor. Marín and Hazell (2014) found no significant difference in normalised VM neuromuscular activity during static double leg squat for 30 s when comparing unstable surface to stable surface (floor) ($d = -0.39$, a 95% CI $[-0.92, 0.14]$). The last pooled study compared squatting on an unstable surface comparing eyes open with eyes closed, and a non-significant increase in VM activation was identified when the exercise was performed with the eyes open ($d = 0.30$, a 95% CI $[-0.26, 0.86]$) (Park et al., 2015). The effect of different unstable surfaces has not been examined on VM neuromuscular activation in individuals with PFPS.

2.4.6 Resisted hip adduction exercise does not induce acute VM muscle neuromuscular activity during squatting in healthy individuals.

Five studies (totalling 90 participants) evaluated the effect of resisted hip adduction exercises during squatting in healthy individuals. Resisted hip adduction exercises were found not to be effective (Figure 2.4; $d = 0.31$, 95% CI $[-0.28, 0.89]$, $p = 0.30$). The differences between the studies were considered high ($I^2 = 70\%$). Coqueiro and colleagues (2005) used a mechanical resistance device to obtain a hip adduction position during double leg semi-squat while Hertel et al. (2004) and Irish et al. (2010), used isometric hip resisted exercise with a pillow between the thighs. VM muscle activity in healthy individuals was significantly higher during squat with resisted hip adduction compared to squat alone in Coqueiro et al. (2005) and Irish et al. (2010), while no significant difference found between squat with resisted hip adduction and squat alone in Hertel et al. (2004). Two studies used Thera-Band to obtain resisted hip adduction exercise during double leg semi-squatting (Miao et al., 2015, Lee et al., 2016). In both previous studies, resisted hip adduction by elastic band did not significantly increase VM muscle activity compared to squat alone.

Figure 2.4: Comparison of resisted hip adduction exercise effect on vastus medialis muscle activity in healthy individuals.

2.4.7 Resisted hip adduction exercise is beneficial for acute VM muscle neuromuscular activity during squatting in individuals with PFPS.

Two studies (totalling 40 participants) investigated the effect of resisted hip adduction exercises in individuals with PFPS (Coqueiro et al., 2005; Miao et al., 2015). Pooled data showed a total significant effect of resisted hip adduction exercise during squatting in these patients ($d = 0.52$, 95% CI [0.07, 0.97], $p = 0.02$). There was no significant difference found for resisted hip adduction compared to squat alone on VM muscle activity in individuals with PFPS (Coqueiro et al., 2005; Miao et al., 2015). There was no evidence of heterogeneity between the studies when a random effects model was applied ($I^2 = 0\%$). This indicates that the variation between these studies is due to chance rather than heterogeneity, particularly with the small sample sizes across the included studies. The resisted hip adduction interventions appeared to increase VM activity in the PFPS population as summarised in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Comparison of resisted hip adduction exercise effect on vastus medialis muscle activity in PFPS.

2.5 Discussion

The aim of this meta-analysis was to evaluate the effectiveness of static double leg squat exercises with WBV, unstable surfaces and resisted hip adduction in increasing acute neuromuscular activity in the VM muscle in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS. Based on the results of this meta-analysis, the evaluated squat exercises (WBV, use of different unstable surfaces and resisted hip adduction exercise) were found to have divergent effects on eliciting acute VM activation in healthy individuals and/or individuals with PFPS.

2.5.1 Whole Body Vibration stimuli during squatting in healthy individuals.

Analysis of the influence of WBV stimuli was based on three previous studies (Roelants et al., 2006; Krol et al., 2011; Marín and Hazell, 2014). Marín and Hazell (2014) examined the effects of WBV stimuli utilising both stable and unstable surfaces during alternating frequencies. In that study, they examined the effect of WBV stimuli with frequencies of 30 Hz and 50 Hz, and peak-to-peak displacement of 1.54mm and 1.07mm respectively. The unstable surface that was placed above the platform resulted in significantly lower VM activation during WBV stimuli of 50 Hz and 1.07mm versus WBV of 30 Hz and 1.54mm (Marín and Hazell, 2014). The results of this study indicate that acute VM muscle activity is decreased on WBV platforms with 50 Hz frequency and 1.07mm peak-to-peak displacement compared to squat on stable surfaces due to the high

frequency and low peak-to-peak displacement (Marín and Hazell, 2014). This research found that VM as well as gastrocnemius medialis were highly activated when specific combinations of WBV settings (30 Hz frequency and 1.54 mm peak-to-peak displacement) were used (Marín and Hazell, 2014).

Krol et al. (2011) demonstrated that VM and VL activity significantly increased with increasing WBV platform parameters of frequency and peak-to-peak displacement in healthy individuals. A frequency of between 20 and 60 Hz and peak-to-peak displacement of between 2 and 4 mm when WBV platforms are used are deemed safe for human use (Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005). Although Krol and colleagues (2011) conducted their study in healthy individuals, the precise and optimal WBV frequencies and peak-to-peak displacements that may result in optimal VM activation in individuals with PFPS, remains to be determined with guidelines yet to be defined.

WBV stimuli has been used with positive effects on muscle activation and strength in healthy populations (Roelants et al., 2006; Krol et al., 2011; Marín and Hazell, 2014). Roelants and colleagues (2006) reported that on a WBV platform, acute VM activation was significantly higher when comparing a single-leg squat to a low double leg squat (knee and hip angles 90°) or high double leg squat (knee angle 125°, hip angle 140°). This is not surprising as single-leg squatting requires increased leg muscle activation in this position to support an individual's body mass. Nonetheless these results suggest that WBV platforms may be beneficial for increasing VM activity, particularly when performing single- leg squatting exercises. However, given the variability in an individuals' EMG response to variations in WBV frequency, peak-to-peak displacement (Krol et al., 2011) and surfaces used (Marín and Hazell, 2014), a requirement for individualised WBV stimuli regimens is clearly needed to optimise the efficacy of this intervention (Di Giminiani et al., 2009). Overall, the evidence suggests that WBV can have a significant

positive effect on muscle activation among healthy individuals, therefore, research determining the optimal protocols for WBV as an intervention in PFPS populations is warranted.

2.5.2 Different unstable surfaces during squatting in healthy individuals.

The analysis of results from several studies which investigated the use of unstable surfaces during squatting reveal negative effect on acute VM activation (Hyong and Ho, 2013; Saeterbakken and Fimland, 2013; Marín and Hazell, 2014; Parekh and Gaur, 2015; Park et al., 2015). In addition, squatting on a rubber plate significantly increased VM activation (Hyong and Ho, 2013; Park et al., 2015). Unstable surfaces were investigated as they have been previously shown to increase muscle recruitment and enhance muscle activity (Kim, Oh and Yoo, 2014). This can be explained by the fact that using unstable surfaces e.g. rubber, or air disc; requires a higher amount of muscle activation to stabilise the lower limb and ankle on the platform. As a result, the individual requires greater effort to maintain a controlled upright posture (Hyong and Ho, 2013; Parekh and Gaur, 2015). Based on this analysis, a new approach to be considered and examined in individuals with PFPS is squatting with rubber plate placed on the WBV platform as a combined intervention.

2.5.3 Resisted hip adduction during squatting in healthy individuals.

The effect of resisted hip adduction during squatting were evaluated in this review. The findings suggested that resisted hip adduction during squatting failed to significantly increase VM activation in healthy individuals when compared with squatting alone (Hertel et al., 2004; Coqueiro et al., 2005; Irish et al., 2010; Miao et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2016). This may indicate that the VM muscle is sufficiently recruited during squatting in healthy individuals thus there is no requirement for an additional resisted hip adduction component. Moreover, individuals who do not present with PFPS symptoms may not exhibit VM weakness (Miao et al., 2015). Hertel et al. (2004) and Miao et al. (2015) did not normalised EMG signal to any maximum voluntary contraction (MVC). Therefore, an additional study in healthy individuals with normalised EMG

signal to be standardised within literature would be beneficial in determining the role of resisted hip adduction in healthy individuals. Indeed, it is important to find a satisfactory result in healthy individuals in the first instance to minimise the risk of adverse effects to affected joints in individuals with PFPS.

2.5.4 Resisted hip adduction during squatting in PFPS patients.

In contrast to the results arising from resisted hip adduction exercises during squatting in healthy individuals, resisted hip adduction exercise in individuals with PFPS was found to be an effective method for increasing VM muscle activation. Two published studies were identified which tested such approaches in individuals with PFPS (Coqueiro et al., 2005; Miao et al., 2015). Despite relatively small sample sizes in both studies, these studies reported a significant increase in acute VM activation (29% and 23% respectively compared to squatting alone). The main conclusion of these findings was that individuals with PFPS showed decreased in VM EMG activity, thus small changes in muscle activation can be interpreted as significant.

A systematic review by Meira and Brumitt (2011) suggested that resistance exercises should be used as advanced exercises in individuals with PFPS to enhance recovery during rehabilitation programmes. Based on their analyses, excessive dynamic hip adduction and VM muscle weakness can both resulted from the lateral patella tracking in individuals with PFPS, which disturbs joint congruity under motion or strain during weight bearing or non-weight bearing activities (Meira and Brumitt, 2011). Excessive hip adduction and VM weakness as a result of patella maltracking in individuals with PFPS has been described in a subsequent review (Kim, Oh and Yoo, 2014). Moreover, the results of this meta-analysis highlight that resisted hip adduction exercises may be a useful way to target VM muscle weakness in individuals with PFPS (Coqueiro et al., 2005; Miao et al., 2015). A rehabilitation programme aimed to expedite a patients' return to full functionality

has been recommended to include a combination of interventions (Crossley et al., 2016). Perhaps combining the interventions of WBV stimuli with e.g. resisted hip adduction during squatting is a new approach which should be further investigated for future patient benefit. These interventions may provide a new methodology for reducing PFPS severity, while aiding recovery.

2.5.5 Study limitations

2.5.5.1 Risk of Bias (ROB)

The risk of bias (ROB) is an important consideration when study limitations are investigated (Higgins and Altman, 2008; Viswanathan et al., 2008). A number of the studies included in this meta-analysis did not explicitly outline how the participants were randomly assigned into groups. Furthermore, a number of the studies did not describe the intervention blinding design procedure for both participants and investigators. Data analysis performed by a researcher in an un-blinded fashion may contribute to the generation of statistical testing biases. The majority of the included studies had a relatively high ROB (summarised in Table 2). This further highlights the need for high quality research studies using physiotherapy interventions involving healthy volunteers and patient cohorts. The PEDro scale ranged between low to moderate between studies, only five studies stated the concealed allocation.

2.5.5.2 Sample sizes

For all studies included in this meta-analysis, the sample sizes investigated were relatively small. The maximum number of participants in any of the studies was 30 and the minimum 8. Given these numbers, it is not unexpected to encounter discrepancies and a lack of consensus between studies, particularly given the number of variables being evaluated in experimental protocols (such as exercises in individuals of a different age, sex, weight, and EMG outcomes). The sample size

is particularly important for meta-analyses, where underpowered studies have been found to provide little or no useful information (Turner, Bird and Higgins, 2013). It has been suggested that such studies be excluded from analysis altogether. This is despite the fact that underpowered studies make up the entirety of evidence in most reviews (Turner, Bird and Higgins, 2013). In this review, study sample sizes were small (section 2.5.5.2) and some of these comparisons were underpowered, therefore the random effects model was used. The comparisons with studies mentioned more than once in data analysis, for example: Parekh and Gaur, 2015, mean that risk of bias is a possible limitation of this meta-analysis. Moreover, methods concerning participant recruitment was generally not well defined, which is another potential avenue for the introduction of bias and could reduce power due to the presence of confounders. In addition, researchers did not carry out longitudinal follow-up studies on participants in a post-interventional manner to investigate longer-term efficacy, or whether any side effects were observed post-treatment.

The search strategy for this review was deliberately focused which provided only 12 studies matching the strict inclusion criteria and high heterogeneity between studies challenged the meta-analysis results. Therefore, additional studies are needed to further demonstrate some of the reported associations, allowing pathological mechanisms to be understood and treatments tailored to patients.

2.6 Conclusions

Despite the limited available literature, this meta-analysis has provided evidence to suggest that VM activation appears to be enhanced following acute WBV stimuli within healthy individuals. This intervention needs to be expanded in the context of PFPS populations in future studies, where additional novel exercises using the WBV platform should be analysed to determine the most

efficacious protocols and methodologies. Furthermore, squatting with resisted hip adduction was found to increase acute VM neuromuscular activity in individuals with PFPS but not healthy individuals, suggesting that when VM dysfunctions are present, these exercises can help enhance VM muscle activation. Additional studies are required to determine the optimal protocols in healthy individuals and PFPS populations. The use of different unstable surfaces without WBV platform does not appear to influence VM activation. These results depend heavily on the individual's ability to carry out complex balancing exercises and again highlighting the need for further exploratory research in larger sample sizes. As previously highlighted, the diverse evidence of the effect of different squat exercises on neuromuscular activity means further research is urgently required to determine the most effective treatment protocols include squat for VM muscle weakness in healthy individuals and VM dysfunction and patella malalignment in individuals with PFPS.

Chapter 3

3. General methods

This chapter describes the common methods employed throughout subsequent chapters to minimise repetition.

3.1 Study participants

All participants included in studies 1 to 4 (pilots), and studies 5 and 6 (main studies) were healthy individuals aged 18-years old and above. Participants were recruited from students and staff at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) through word of mouth and posters and leaflets distributed throughout the Lanarkshire campus of the University (Appendix 2). In addition, staff were recruited via advertisements placed in the 'UWS eBulletin', a platform where staff can share events and news. Inclusion criteria were adults aged 18 or over without history of an acute hernia, epilepsy, gallstones, kidney stones, stroke, serious heart illness, implant, bypass, stent, knee surgery, or knee, hip or ankle injury in the previous 12 weeks.

Participants in study 7 were individuals diagnosed with patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS) by physicians. They were recruited through flyers and posters left in the waiting area of private physiotherapy clinics in South Lanarkshire, Scotland. Physiotherapy and reception staff at these clinics were not actively involved in the recruitment process. In addition, UWS students and staff with PFPS were recruited as per the local strategy explained earlier. Inclusion criteria for this study were adults aged 18 or older, body Mass Index (BMI) less than $< 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$ and who reported pain in the anterior aspect of the knee with score 3-6 on the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) in the last 3 months. They should also have experienced pain during at least two of the following activities during the last 3 months: prolonged sitting, squatting, ascending or descending stairs, running, kneeling, or jumping. Exclusion criteria were acute hernia, epilepsy, gallstones, kidney stones,

stroke, serious heart illness, having an implant, bypass, stent, or knee surgery, or of knee, hip, or ankle injury in the previous 12 weeks.

Participants in all studies confirmed that they did not have any allergies to shavers, alcohol wipes, permanent ink, hypoallergenic adhesive tape, or micropore tape. They were requested to avoid intense physical activity for 72 hours prior to all visits.

Ethical approval was obtained from the UWS School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee (Ethics application 1090 and 6348) for the studies described in Chapters 4 - 6 (Ethics application 1090, see Appendix 3 for approval) and for the study described in Chapter 7 (Ethics application 6348, see Appendix 7 for approval). All data were collected at the UWS Biomechanics Laboratory, Lanarkshire. Characteristics of study participants are illustrated in Table 6.

In study 4 (pilot) and study 5, the same participants were recruited for two sessions. In addition, the same participants attended a third session for recording data during exercise implementation (Chapter 6).

Table 6. Participant characteristics of all (mean \pm SD) across all studies. N: number of participants, M: male, F: female, BMI: body mass index.

Chapter	Chapter 4		Chapter 5	Chapter 6	Chapter 7
Study	Study 2 (pilot)	Study 4 (pilot)	Study 5	Study 6	Study 7
N	11	26	26	26	16
M:F	8:3	11:15	11:15	11:15	11:5
Age (years)	33.3 \pm 6.1	35.1 \pm 8.3	35.1 \pm 8.3	35.1 \pm 8.3	35.1 \pm 14
Height (cm)	173.2 \pm 10.1	172.4 \pm 6.9	172.4 \pm 6.9	172.4 \pm 6.9	173.3 \pm 10.2
Weight (kg)	75.9 \pm 10.4	74.5 \pm 13.5	74.5 \pm 13.5	74.5 \pm 13.5	72.6 \pm 9.6
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.5 \pm 4.4	25.1 \pm 4.4	25.1 \pm 4.4	25.1 \pm 4.4	24.3 \pm 3.0

3.2 Procedure outline

All participants read the participant information sheet, signed the consent form and answered the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) questionnaire. Demographic data were collected (height, weight, defined dominant leg). Height was determined using a stadiometer (Leicester Height Measure – Seca, Ltd, Birmingham, UK) and weight recorded using (Omron Digital Weight Scale HN-286, Japan). The dominant leg was identified as the leg used to kick a ball (Beling et al., 1998). A warm-up was performed (described in section 3.2.1). For study 4 (pilot), and studies 5 to 7 (main studies), the participant was prepared for electrodes placement on the VM and VL muscles (see section 3.3.2). A maximum voluntary isometric contraction (MVIC) of the left and right quadriceps muscles was performed in a sitting position during an open kinetic-chain exercise (OKC) exercise (see section 3.2.2) whilst EMG signals were recorded. Then EMG data were collected during a static squat on a vibration platform operating at varying frequencies (see section 3.3.1). All EMG data recorded for VM and VL muscles for the dominant and non-dominant legs (see section 3.3.2) were filtered by band-pass and notch filters during all vibration stimuli (see section 3.5.1).

3.2.1 Warm-up

The warm-up included cycling for 3 min on a cycle ergometer (Stania et al., 2017) and 10 squats in front of the mirror with verbal feedback to correct squatting position and angles (Marín and Hazell, 2014). For Chapter 7, which involved individuals with PFPS, the warm-up included an extended period of cycling (5 min) to ensure the muscles were sufficiently prepared for exercises and to avoid induction of pain (Lee, Lee and Lee, 2014; Chen et al., 2018), in addition to the 10 squat repetitions. Cycling was performed at a comfortable speed with a 1.0 kg load. The warm-up was standardised across all participants and all sessions within each individual chapter.

3.2.2 Maximum Voluntary Isometric Contraction (MVIC)

To obtain the MVIC, participants were asked to sit at the edge of a plinth with hips flexed at 90° and with a straight back. The plinth height was adjusted so that the participant's feet did not touch the ground. Two metal chains were fixed to the plinth (one for the right leg and one for the left leg) as shown in Figure 3.1. The chains were linked to an adjustable foam strap, which was attached around the lower limb just above the malleoli. The metal chain was adjusted to obtain a knee flexion angle of between 60° and 65° and the angle confirmed using a 360° manual goniometer (RBMS, USA) (Perchthaler, Horstmann and Grau, 2013; Ritzmann, Gollhofer and Kramer, 2013; Mullaney and Fukunaga, 2016). Knee angle was measured using the goniometer before each MVIC trial in all conducted sessions.

Figure 3.1: Maximum voluntary isometric contraction positioning and measurement: a) resting position (90° hip flexion and 90° knee flexion). b) MVIC obtained position (90° hip flexion and $60\text{--}65^\circ$ knee flexion).

The start position of the MVIC was as follows: hands on the sides of the plinth, a straight back, and knee extended to take up the slack of the chain (hence end range knee flexed at $60\text{--}65^\circ$). To perform the MVIC, participants were asked to extend their knee against the chain as hard as

possible for 3 s. The researcher verbally encouraged the participant to pull as hard as possible. The MVIC trial was repeated three times per leg with a resting time of 10 s between each trial. The order of left or right leg testing was randomised by random number generator. After data processing, the highest MVIC value for each leg separately was selected for normalisation of squat EMG data (see section 3.2.2).

3.3 Equipment used

3.3.1 Whole Body Vibration (WBV) platforms

Two WBV platforms were evaluated in studies 1 and 2 (pilots): the Vibe plate platform (Vibe Plate, Lincoln, US) and the VibraMachine platform (VibraMachines Ltd., Ledborough, UK). The Vibe plate platform (vertical vibration) has dimensions of 76.2 cm × 182.8 cm, a frequency range of 10–60 Hz, peak-to-peak displacement of 4 mm (Figure 3.2). The second WBV platform was a VibraMachine (vertical vibration) with dimensions of 92 cm × 85 cm × 144 cm, frequency range of 30–50 Hz, peak-to-peak displacement of 3 mm (low setting) or 6 mm (high setting) (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Whole-body vibration platforms. a) Vibe plate platform. b) VibraMachine platform.

The VibraMachine platform does not require calibration (Power, 2019). The theoretical acceleration and g force values for the two vibration platforms were calculated for frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz as illustrated in Table 7, and as previously described (Rauch et al., 2010) using the following equation:

$$\text{Acceleration} = 2 \times \pi^2 \times \text{Frequency}^2 \times \text{Peak-to-Peak Displacement}$$

Table 7. Theoretical acceleration values (m.s^{-2}) and gravity force (g) (for Vibe plate and VibraMachine platforms) for frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz.

Frequency (Hz)	Vibe plate platform acceleration (m.s^{-2})/ g -force (g)	VibraMachine platform acceleration (m.s^{-2})/ g -force (g)
30	71.1/7.2	53.3/5.4
35	96.7/9.8	72.5/7.4
40	126.3/12.9	94.7/9.7
50	197.4/20.1	148/15.1

3.3.2 EMG system

The Delsys Trigno Avanti EMG System (Delsys, Inc, Boston, USA) was used to record EMG signals for analysis in Chapters 4, 5, 6 and 7. The Delsys system contains a base station for placing and recharging the cradle for 16 sensors with wireless connection and high-speed USB communication with a PC. Summary sensor characteristics are as follows:

- Size: 27 mm \times 37 mm \times 13 mm
- Weight: 14 g
- EMG contact dimensions: 5 mm \times 1 mm
- Sensor skin contacts: pure silver (99.9%)
- Sensor resolution: 16 bits.

Four sensors were used to record data from the following locations: left VM, right VM, left VL, and right VL.

EMG sensors were placed according to the SENIAM Guidelines (Hermens et al., 2000; Lienhard, Vienneau, Friesenbichler, et al., 2015): EMG sensors for the VM muscle were placed perpendicularly at 80% of the distance from the anterior spina iliac superior (ASIS) to anterior border of the medial ligament. The EMG sensor for the VL muscle was placed in parallel with the muscle and approximately two-thirds of the distance on the line from ASIS to the lateral side of the patella (Figure 3.3). The anatomical location of VM and VL muscles are also described in Figure 3.3. After marking the muscle location on the participant's skin using pen, a pillow was placed below the knee joint and the participant was asked to press downwards against the pillow to palpate the required muscle and compare the location to the marked area. The areas were shaved and prepared with sandpaper and alcohol wipes before EMG sensors were placed on the skin.

EMG sensor placement for VM muscle: 80% on the line from a) anterior superior iliac spine to b) anterior border of the medial ligament.

EMG sensor placement for VL muscle: 2/3 on the line from: a) anterior superior iliac spine to b) lateral side of the patella.

Figure 3.3: Upper panel: Vastus medialis (VM) and Lower panel: Vastus lateralis (VL) EMG sensor placement (Hermens et al., 2000; Azar et al., 2013). EMG sensors were attached between points a and b.

The EMG system data sampling which obtained via an analogue-to-digital converter (A/D) system, can be affected by sample rate and resolution (Clancy, Morin and Merletti, 2002). Due to the Nyquist Theorem, EMG signals should be acquired at a sample rate of not less than double the

highest frequency or harmonics applied to recover the complete signal. Data acquisition may be lost if the sample rate does not follow this guideline, referred to as ‘aliasing’ (Luca, 2003). The selection range for the band-width filter was obtained to identify the minimum sampling rate. The sample resolution was determined by a 16-bit A/D converter to avoid the necessity of modifying gain, thereby helping improve noise rejection (Clancy, Morin and Merletti, 2002). Thus, the 1,100 Hz sample rate was selected and 1,000 gain with 16-bit A/D resolution during EMG data collection (Luca, 2003).

The sampling rate and gain were set to default settings in the EMG acquisition software used for EMG data recording. EMG data were collected for 30s for all studies pertaining to Chapters 4, 5 and 6. For the study detailed in Chapter 7, EMG data were collected for 20 s during the static squat position for individuals with PFPS to avoid pain and muscle fatigue.

3.3.3 Exercise protocol

All participants recruited for inclusion in analyses detailed in Chapters 4, 5, 6 and 7 were asked to wear sports socks, sports shoes and shorts for all sessions whilst performing the warm-up (see section 3.2.1). Participants were required to stand on the platform while wearing sports socks without shoes. Consistent instructions were communicated to all participants before each trial involving squatting with or without vibration stimuli. Instructions stipulated that participants should first stand on a platform and then perform 65° static squats position (measured by a 360° manual goniometer) with feet shoulder width apart. Weight was instructed to be equally distributed on both legs without leaning forwards or backwards. In all trials involving squatting on a vibration platform, verbal instructions included requesting the participants to place more weight on the heels than toes while upon the Vibe plate platform, whereas for the VibraMachine platform participants were asked to shift their weights on the toes. For both platforms, participants were asked to keep

their heels firmly planted on the vibration platform. This slight procedural difference between the platforms was as a result of exploratory work which compared the effect of weight-bearing between heels and toes on both vibration platforms, which showed EMG signals were higher in selected positions (weight bearing on toes for the VibraMachine and weight bearing on heels for the Vibe plate platform) for each vibration platform.

3.4 Exercises

The studies in Chapters 6 and 7 evaluated VM and VL neuromuscular responses during four variations of a static squat exercise:

Exercise 1 – static squat with 65° knee flexion without WBV or resisted hip adduction

Exercise 2 – static squat with 65° knee flexion and resisted hip adduction

Exercise 3 – static squat with 65° knee flexion on a WBV platform

Exercise 4 – static squat with 65° knee flexion on a WBV platform and resisted hip adduction

The squat position was maintained for 30 s in healthy individuals and for 20 s in individuals with PFPS in order to avoid fatigue or to prevent the provocation of knee pain.

3.4.1 Thera-Band

Thera-Band is a rubber latex material that can be used in resistance training (The Hygenic Corporation, Akron, 2012). The intra-session reliability and validity of calculated resistance forces of Thera-Bands was evaluated by MicroFET2 handheld strength dynamometer (Hogan Health Industries, Inc., West Jordan, USA) in study 3(pilot), and then subsequently used during the squatting exercises in exercises implementation chapters (Chapters 6 and 7) as outlined above. The Thera-Bands employed during exercises was fixed to a plinth using a specific measured distance according to the needed elongation length to produce the required force (Patterson et al., 2001;

Nyberg, 2016; Andersen et al., 2017). Further details of how Thera-Bands used in resisted hip adduction exercise protocol are discussed in Chapters 4 and 6.

Finally, it was necessary to investigate the procedure for application the Thera-Band during static double leg squat positioning, for the purpose of the studies described in Chapters 6 and 7. However, direct contact of the Thera-Band with the skin was found to be uncomfortable and difficult to obtain and maintain effectively, particularly during the higher levels of elongation (200% and 250%). Therefore, a spongy pad was placed around the section of Thera-Band in direct contact with the knee to provide comfortable contact and increase participant safety during squat positioning. This modification increased participant concentration when performing exercises by minimising the unnecessary pressure on the knee joint for both healthy individuals and the PFPS patient population.

3.5 Data analysis

3.5.1 Filtering of raw EMG data

All EMG data in this thesis were processed using a band-pass filter within EMGworks software (Delsys, Inc, Boston, USA), which was downloaded on the UWS data collection PC. The band-pass filter excluded all noise lower than 20 Hz and greater than 450 Hz with a second-order Butterworth filter (passband ripple = 3 dB, attenuation = 40 dB). Following this filtration step, a band-stop filter (notch filter) was applied to all recorded data on vibration platforms. The band-stop frequency was selected based on the respective frequency (30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz or 50 Hz) of the vibration platform setting and for each frequency subharmonics (Fratini, Cesarelli, et al., 2009; Fratini, La Gatta, et al., 2009). For example, for the vibration platform frequency setting of 30 Hz, the corresponding EMG notch filter was applied at $30 \text{ Hz} \pm 1.5 \text{ Hz}$ (hence 28.5–31.5), and also at 60 Hz (58.5–61.5), 90 Hz (88.5–91.5) and 120 Hz (118.5–121.5). An example of the power density

spectra (measures signal power versus frequency) is shown in Figure 3.4, which shows spiking for the centred frequency of 40 Hz and its subharmonics.

Figure 3.4: Example of a power density spectrum collected for the vastus medialis (VM) muscle at a frequency of 40 Hz.

These spikes which indicate at the fundamental and sub-harmonic frequencies, caused by electromagnetic interference during analysis the EMG signals. Also, example of raw data and notch filter for frequency 40 Hz shown in Figures 3.5 and 3.6.

Figure 3.5: Example of a raw EMG signal for the right vastus medialis (VM) at a frequency of 40 Hz.

Figure 3.6: Examples of two notch filters for the EMG signal of the vastus medialis (VM) recorded at a frequency of 40 Hz. 1) notch filter at frequency $40 \text{ Hz} \pm 1.5 \text{ Hz}$ (hence 38.5–41.5). 2) notch filter at frequency 40 subharmonic at $160 \text{ Hz} \pm 1.5 \text{ Hz}$ (hence 158.5–161.5)

For EMG data collected for analysis in Chapter 7, a standardized frequency of 40 Hz was used for all participants. Therefore, a $40 \text{ Hz} \pm 1.5 \text{ Hz}$ band-stop filter was applied and for subharmonics (38.5–41.5, 78.5–81.5, 118.5–121.5 and 158.5–161.5). Following the process of filter application during EMG data analysis, the EMG signal was rectified and the root mean square (RMS) obtained with a window length of 0.125 s, window overlap of 0.0625 s and offset removed (see Figure 3.7).

The RMS approach has been used to evaluate the electrical signals which reflect physiological activity in muscle motor unit during contraction (Fukuda et al., 2010). In that study, the RMS was found to have a linear correlation with the muscle contraction. Therefore, RMS according to the literature can be used to evaluate the effect of exercises on muscle force or muscle activity (Hazell, Jakobi and Kenno, 2007; Krol et al., 2011; Hyong and Ho, 2013), which indicated the main aim of this thesis.

Figure 3.7: Example of root mean squared (RMS) values for the EMG signal generated from the vastus medialis (VM) at a frequency of 40 Hz.

Data were then imported into Excel to normalise the RMS values to the highest RMS value from the MVIC collected during the same session (see section 3.2.2). For the analyses presented in Chapters 4 and 5, the normalisation process was applied to the RMS of the vibration stimuli (frequency or exercise):

$$\text{Normalised RMS} = (\text{RMS of vibration stimuli or exercise} / \text{RMS of MVIC}) \times 100$$

The isometric MVC is commonly used in the literature during normalisation processes to allow the comparison between studies (Hazell, Kenno and Jakobi, 2015; Halaki and Ginn., 2012; Pollock et al., 2010). Therefore, the isometric squat position (knee extension angle 60°-65°) adopted during the EMG recording in this thesis can add further rationale to the selected normalisation approach (knee extension in sitting position with 60°-65°). An illustrative example of the full analysis process applied from raw data to calculation of RMS values on recorded EMG signals is shown in Figure 3.8. For the analyses presented in Chapters 6 and 7, the same protocol was followed for the RMS for all exercise conditions involving vibration stimulus. The electromyography root mean

square (EMG_{rms}) data average was obtained, using only the 10 seconds section of data for further analysis as vibration platform takes some time to reach the desired frequency.

Figure 3.8: Example of the full analysis process applied to raw data, including band-pass filtering (green line), four notch filters (red, light blue, purple, and yellow lines) and root mean square (RMS) (the dark blue line) on EMG data recorded for the vastus medialis (VM) muscle at a frequency of 40 Hz.

3.5.2 Statistical analysis

All data in this thesis were imported to Statistical Package for the Social Sciences SPSS Statistics version 25 (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK) software for further analysis. The Shapiro-Wilk test, visual inspection of box plots, histograms and residual Q-Q plots and Skewness and Kurtosis statistic were used to evaluate the normality of data distribution for the WBV parameters (acceleration, frequency and peak to peak displacement) and normalised EMG_{rms} data in Chapters 4-7.

For normally distributed data, paired sample t-test was used to identify within-group differences at two time points and the one sample t-test was used to evaluate data validity compared to their theoretical values. For not normally distributed data, the Wilcoxon two related-samples test in SPSS version 25 (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK) was used as the non-parametric alternative to a paired t-test, while a one-sample Wilcoxon test was used as the non-parametric equivalent of the one-sample t-test. To compare data across different conditions within the same outcome measure, a two-way ANOVA was used for normally distributed data, while a Friedman ANOVA within subjects was utilised for not normally distributed data. Alpha (p) was set to 0.05 (Field et al., 2016).

The interclass correlation coefficients (ICC), standard error of measurement (SEM) and coefficient of variation (CV) were calculated to assess reliability (Zech, Witte and Pfeifer, 2008). The ICC values were interpreted as: excellent (ICC > 0.9), good (ICC between 0.75 and 0.9), moderate (ICC between 0.5 and 0.75) and poor (ICC < 0.5) (Koo and Li, 2016).

The effect size (z) for normally distributed data was evaluated and reported by paired sample t-test, and the effect size (r) for not normally data was calculated and evaluated by Kendall's test via non-parametric test. The effect size r or z counted to be small = 0.1; moderate = 0.3; and large = 0.5) (Field, 2018).

Chapter 4 – Pilot studies

Assessment of equipment validity and reliability

4.1 Introduction

The assessment of the validity and reliability of the equipment used throughout this thesis was paramount to confirm that all readings were accurate and reproducible; this is a key consideration when conducting research (Kimberlin and Winterstein, 2008). Reliability and validity are key measures when evaluating research output validity. The measure of reliability is defined as an evaluation of the consistency of the results, while validity can be defined as the process of evaluating the instrument in measuring what it is supposed to measure and how closely the results mirror the theoretical values (Kimberlin and Winterstein, 2008). Owing to the powerful impact of validity and reliability on research outcome and data interpretation, this chapter will validate and investigate the reliability of three tools pivotal to this thesis: vibration platforms, Thera-Bands and the Trigno Avanti electromyography system. The current literature is lacking investigations on the reliability and validity of the previous tools. Therefore, the present thesis will investigate the reliability and validity of these tools before being used in further research. Firstly, two distinct WBV platforms were identified and their stimuli outputs compared against their reported manufacturer outputs. Evaluation the validity and reliability of the WBV platform outputs can help in identifying the effectiveness of WBV platform for further implication in rehabilitation programmes. The output of each platform was assessed during static squatting positioning in response to changes in body weight and frequency settings. Platforms were tested using 90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg loads across frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz. Secondly, the inter-day reliability across two separate sessions of both platform outputs: acceleration, frequency and peak-to-peak displacement was evaluated, and also compared against the manufacturer's suggested

theoretical output. Thirdly, the forces of two variations of Thera-Band (green and blue) were validated and compared to the values defined by the manufacturer. Finally, an evaluation of the inter-day reliability of EMG-recorded signals of Delsys Avanti system during squat positioning on the WBV platforms was carried out. Each section of this validity pilot work will be discussed in detail in this chapter.

4.2 Pilot 1: Validity of the vibration platforms parameter outputs

4.2.1 Introduction

As mentioned previously, a vibration platform is a piece of equipment that can be used in rehabilitation programmes for different patient populations (Park et al., 2013; Huang and Pang, 2019). Despite the fact that vibration platforms were first introduced approximately 50 years ago, still health care practitioners have been reluctant to incorporate this equipment in strengthening or rehabilitation programmes due to the lack of research evidence or researchers may not knowledge about this evaluation.

Previously, it was suggested that increasing body weight can dampen the vibrations of the WBV platform and cause variation between participants (Marín and Rhea, 2010). This was further confirmed when load conditions which obtained by placing weightlifting bar on participants shoulder with 1/3 of their body weight, were shown to impact upon EMG readings in a study of lower-limb neuromuscular activity in gastrocnemius medialis, soleus, tibialis anterior, biceps femoris, vastus medialis and rectus femoris muscles using a WBV platform (Ritzmann, Gollhofer and Kramer, 2013). These results considered the effect of vibration stimuli on EMG signals (which will be evaluated and discussed in further pilot work) but not on WBV parameters themselves. Indeed, it has been recommended that an accelerometer (see section 4.2.2.1) be used to evaluate WBV platform outputs for each individual separately (Marín and Rhea, 2010; Rauch et al., 2010). This recommendation was supported by the results of a 2009 study which compared the loaded and unloaded conditions of two body weights (62 kg and 81 kg) upon the acceleration of three WBV platforms (Pel et al., 2009). The authors reported that the calculated mean resultant acceleration values were marginally affected by body weight where acceleration was either higher or lower than expected. However, by calculating mean acceleration at two or more locations on

the platform, this effect can be mitigated (Pel et al., 2009). Therefore, the key question addressed initially in this pilot study is whether body weight can affect the platform parameter outputs or effectiveness.

The result of the study by Pel et al. (2009) suggest that the understanding of the impact of body weight on WBV parameters is incomplete and that further work is necessary to validate WBV platforms' parameter outputs (acceleration, peak-to-peak displacement and frequency). In this pilot study, the validity of WBV platform output parameters was undertaken using equivalent body weights of 90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg and frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz. This preliminary work was conducted to investigate two different platforms. It was hypothesised that the change in body weights would influence the vibration platform parameter outputs by reducing the platform acceleration based on a previous study (Pel et al., 2009).

4.2.2 Methods

One participant (male, height 187 cm, weight 87 kg) took part in this pilot work. The Vibe plate and VibraMachine were both evaluated using the same accelerometer. Platform characteristics, accelerometer details and placement location are detailed in sections 3.3.1 and 4.2.2.1.

In order to reach the equivalent body weights, the participant wore a weight jacket to which multiple 0.5 kg weights could be added. The necessary number of 0.5 kg weights were added to reach the 90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg weights. This was monitored using a weight scale (Omron Digital Weight Scale HN-286, Japan). The participant was asked to stand on a WBV platform wearing sports socks and for each trial, perform a static squat for 30 s with 65° knee flexion, measured using a manual goniometer. The participant rested for 2 min between trials to avoid muscle fatigue. The weight jacket was removed during the resting time between trials. The platforms, frequencies and equivalent body weight orders were randomised by a random number

generator. The accelerometers were switched on before the participant performed the squatting position and switched off after the participant stepped off the platform. The accelerometer placement and squatting angle were standardized during all trials regardless of the platform. The VibraMachine platform contained a handrail which the participant could hold if required during squatting (as shown in Figure 3.2). For squat positioning on the VibraMachine platform, the participant could support their hands on the handrail although were requested explicitly not to lean on the handrail and maintain support of body weight on the lower limbs rather than the upper limbs. All included participants used the handrail. Moreover, instructions were standardised for all conducted trials according to the vibration platform utilised as described in section 3.3.1.

4.2.2.1 Accelerometer

An accelerometer (USB Impact Accelerometer, model X250-2, Gulf Coast Data Concepts, Waveland, USA) was used study 1 and 2 (pilots) to evaluate vibration platform force (Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: USB Impact Accelerometer. A) Accelerometer. b) Sensor orientation. Figure is adapted from the manufacturer's product user manual (Coast and Concepts, 2013).

The width of each WBV platform was measured and the accelerometer was placed on middle of measured distance of each platform. The accelerometer which weighs 33 g and measures data in three axes (x-, y-, and z-axes), was calibrated by using the earth's gravity of 1g (9.81 m/s²) (Pel et al., 2009; Lienhard, Vienneau and Nigg, 2015; Huang and Pang, 2019) (see Figure 4.1). The x-

axis was defined as the anterior–posterior axis, the y-axis as the medio–lateral axis and the z-axis as the cranio-caudal axis. Data were collected and stored on a microSD memory card with a sampling rate of 512 Hz and 14-bit resolution.

4.2.2.2 Data analysis

Acceleration data were gathered for a total of 24 trials (3 body weights × 4 frequencies × 2 platforms). The Java-based software program, XLR8R, was downloaded onto a UWS personal computer (PC) and used to visualise the data from accelerometer. Collected data from the three axes (x, y & z axis) were recorded and calculated in blank X805 Excel sheets (version 2016) (Redmond, USA). In blank X805 Excel sheets, acceleration count performed and converted to g units according to the manufacturer’s recommended protocol (Coast and Concepts, 2013). Then, offset correct acceleration performed and the peak acceleration utilised in which the mean was calculated. Then resultant peak acceleration was calculated, along with p-t-p displacement. The process of analysis of resultant accelerometer data included the below formula in calculating all acceleration values specifically pertaining to study 1 and 2 (pilots).

$$\text{Resultant acceleration} = (\text{counts} - 8192) \times \frac{70}{16348} \quad (\text{Coast and Concepts, 2013})$$

The raw data were transferred from the accelerometer USB to a PC. The acceleration data were then analysed using Fast Fourier transform (FFT) in the XLR8R software to investigate the calculated frequency. An example of acceleration raw data at a frequency of 40 Hz (calculated frequency) in the XLR8R software is shown in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Example of acceleration raw data at a frequency of 40 Hz in XLR8R software. X axis presented time (second), y-axis presented G-force (V). x axis is shown by the red line (Ax), y axis shown by the blue line (Ay), z axis shown by the green line (Az). The y-axis does not include the offset corrected. As each axis should centre on 0g.

The resultant acceleration data was obtained for the x, y and z axes by $\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$ equation.

The vibration-calculated peak-to-peak displacement was calculated from the resultant acceleration data and the calculated frequency from the FFT (Displacement = acceleration/($2 \times \pi^2 \times \text{frequency}^2$)) (Rauch et al., 2010; Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005) and according to the earth's gravitational pull, where $g = 9.81 \text{ m.s}^{-2}$ with respect to transforming data from g to acceleration (m.s^{-2}). WBV platform parameters (acceleration, frequency and peak-to-peak displacement) were subsequently

calculated and compared with their theoretical values according to those described previously (Rauch et al. 2010). The theoretical values for all included frequency described in Table 8.

Table 8. Theoretical acceleration values in frequency 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz in Vibe plate and VibraMachine platforms.

Theoretical Frequency (Hz)	Theoretical acceleration value in Vibe plate platform (m.s ⁻²)	Theoretical acceleration value in VibraMachine platform (m.s ⁻²)
30	71	53.3
35	96.7	72.5
40	126.3	94.7
50	197.3	148

An example for the acceleration amplitude data gathered from the test with equivalent weight of 95 kg at 40 Hz frequency for the Vibe plate platform and VibraMachine platform is shown in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Calculated resultant acceleration for participants with an equivalent weight of 95 kg at a 40 Hz frequency with the a) VibraMachine platform and b) Vibe plate platform.

Although the data were collected in each trial over 30 s, data pertaining to the first and last 10 s were excluded from the analysis while the middle 10 s was exclusively employed as a vibration platform takes some time to reach the desired frequency. Thereafter, data were imported to

Microsoft Excel (version 2016) and data were visually inspected to ascertain if a weight of 90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg influenced the parameters.

4.2.3 Results

There were similar outputs in accelerations and peak-to-peak displacement parameters between weight 90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg indicating that the weights appear to have little effect on WBV acceleration and peak to peak displacement for Vibe plate platform and VibraMachine platform shown in Figure 4.4 and Figure 4.5 (a and b).

Figure 4.4: The effect of equivalent weights (90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg) on calculated resultant acceleration compared to theoretical acceleration for the a) Vibe plate platform and b) VibraMachine platform.

Figure 4.5: The effect of different equivalent body weights (90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg) on calculated peak-to-peak displacements compared to theoretical values for the a) Vibe plate platform and b) VibraMachine platform.

4.2.4 Discussion

The main finding of this pilot study was that WBV platform parameters were visually found not to be influenced by the tested body weights (90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg) at the four frequencies tested. This is in contrast to a previous study which reported minimal effects of body weight upon WBV stimuli outputs (Pel et al., 2009). However, that study investigated the outputs of unloaded and loaded conditions on a Power plate, Galileo-fitness and one home-use device which is the

Power-Maxx, whereas this pilot study evaluated the of equivalent body weights of 90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg on Vibe plate platform and VibraMachine platform. As discussed previously (see section 3.3.1), the differences observed between the parameters of each platform may be explained by the individual platform characteristics, which are dependent to an extent upon body weight. Furthermore, the Pel et al. (2009) study reported the impact of loaded and unloaded conditions on all the acceleration axes separately during vibration stimuli regardless of the frequency. In that study, the z-axis values were found to positively correlate with frequency while the x-axis and y-axis values decreased. Therefore, the magnitude of increase or decrease in axis value can vary between platforms depending on platform type, characteristics and manufacturer. In addition, the study by Pel et al. (2009) lacked the relevant total resultant acceleration calculation for the 3 axes and the theoretical acceleration values, therefore it was not possible to evaluate whether that methodological differences could account for the minor difference between Pel et al. (2009) and this present study. Moreover, no additional studies identified the effect of weights on WBV parameter outputs.

The goal of this initial study was to assess the effect of body weight on WBV platform parameters. It is important that the validity of the WBV platforms were assessed prior to neuromuscular evaluation of thigh muscles in the upcoming studies in this thesis. The two platforms did not appear to be affected by the body weights tested here across frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz. However, this study showed that the parameters calculated for the Vibe plate platform (acceleration and peak-to-peak displacements) were considerably lower than the expected theoretical values. Although both platforms showed valid actual frequency compared to theoretical frequency according as shown previously in (Figure 4.3), greater acceleration and peak-to-peak

displacement, which more closely matched expected output based on manufacturer parameters, were observed for the Vibramachine compared to the Vibe plate platform.

Evaluation the effect of body weights on Vibramachine platform had not been evaluated before. However, previously the weights of 45 kg, 68 kg, 91 kg were found to have an influence on Vibe plate platform outputs (acceleration, displacement and frequency) (Alizadeh-Meghrazi et al., 2014). The Vibramachine platform has not been investigated in the literature in EMG studies in relation to reliability or intervention studies, while the Vibe plate platform has been used in evaluation muscle performance (Svetlana Mepocatykh, Gytis Balilionis, 2014). However, the WBV stimuli was found to be ineffective at increasing muscle performance (Svetlana Mepocatykh, Gytis Balilionis, 2014).

There is a possible limitation of this pilot study that concerns the inclusion of only three-body weights, 90 kg, 95 kg, and 100 kg and in one participant on WBV parameter outputs. To resolve this, the effect of weights below 90 kg and above 100 kg need to be further evaluated, as the participants' weights ranged from 50 to 110 kg (Chapters 5 to 7). Also, an evaluation of the weight range between 90 and 100 kg, for example at 92 or 98 kg, warrants further investigation. Initially, in this pilot study, the role of body mass on displacement WBV output was illustrated; however, the platform parameters were limited to peak-to-peak displacements between 1 and 4 mm only. This restriction can be addressed by investigating a WBV platform with high peak-to-peak displacements on EMG signals. Also, a possible limitation of using a single participant with additional weights rather than individuals who have different body masses should be noted. The individual body mass can involve greater muscle size or volume and that may not be presented by using additional weights for a single individual. WBV platform outputs can be possibly influenced differently by body mass compared to single participant with additional weights (data collected in

Pilot 1). Therefore, in pilot 2, 11 participants were included with different body mass to evaluate reliability and validity of WBV platform outputs.

4.2.5 Conclusion

There was no evidence to suggest that body weight affected VibraMachine or Vibe plate platform parameters for the weights and frequencies assessed. Therefore, both platforms were deemed suitable for use in future research including participants of body weight ranging from 90kg to 100kg. However, this preliminary work investigated the effect of weight of 90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg with one participant only, therefore further research is needed to evaluate the influence of body weight less than 90kg and more than 100kg on WBV platforms outputs in a greater number of participants. Despite there being no apparent effect of additional weight on the platform parameters, it was evident that the platforms substantially differed compared to manufacturer outputs (in peak to peak displacement and therefore acceleration). Hence further assessment of the platform's vibe plate and VibraMachine parameters is needed. Thus, these results justified the rationale for **Pilot 2**: test-retest validity and inter-day (intra-tester) consistency of the WBV platform parameters values within the Vibe plate and VibraMachine platforms among healthy individuals.

4.3 Pilot 2: The reliability and validity of WBV platforms

4.3.1 Introduction

Following on from the assessment of WBV platform acceleration in relation to body weight and frequency, a second validity study was performed. Examples exist within the literature which experimentally determined vibration stimuli measurements, although these were not compared with the theoretical values (Pollock et al., 2010, Avelar et al., 2013; Marín and Hazell, 2014; Lienhard et al., 2015; Munera et al., 2016). However, two published studies did compare experimentally determined vibration outputs with theoretical values (Pel et al. 2009; Kiiski et al. 2008). In both of these studies, the calculated acceleration was determined to be significantly lower than the theoretical values; in platforms with peak-to-peak displacement, they ranged from 0.05 to 3 mm (acceleration 7.8 to 73.5 $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) in the Kiiski et al. (2008) study, and 1.4 to 3.5 mm (acceleration 1.4 to 48.6 $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) across three vibration platforms in the Pel et al. (2009) study.

The results from Pilot 1 suggested that WBV stimuli outputs are not what they seem, so warrants further investigation. Moreover, there are no known optimal WBV parameters (e.g. which frequency is best), and because parameter outputs consistency varies between manufacturer, this pilot work was conducted to evaluate the consistency of the parameter outputs for the common frequencies within the two WBV platforms by comparing calculated parameters between two tests performed one week apart. These values were also compared to those reported by the manufacturers. This study was performed as a necessity prior to any subsequent WBV studies in this thesis. In study 2 (pilot), the inter-day consistency and validity of the vibration platform settings were assessed to determine if they accurately reflected the acceleration parameters. Confirmation of validity and reliability in the platform acceleration parameters would ensure that results were not influenced by the time in which any test was performed, while validity tests would

confirm that the platforms were operating as expected. Also, the results of this pilot study will facilitate the decision of selecting which of the two platforms should be used for investigating and comparing the effect of knee exercises in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS (Chapters 6 and 7).

The potential implications of any findings from this pilot work will be contributed on further evaluation of the effect of knee exercises during static double leg squat in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS in further Chapters.

4.3.2 Methods

This experiment consisted of two sessions, where the second session was carried out within one week of the first (minimum of 1 day and maximum of 6 days). Eleven healthy participants volunteered to take part. The participants' demographic data (Mean \pm SD) included age: 33.2 ± 6.1 years, height: 173.2 ± 10.1 cm, weight: 75.9 ± 10.4 kg and BMI: 25.5 ± 4.4 kg/m². Ethical approval was obtained from the UWS School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee (application number:1090, Appendix 3). All participants read the participant information sheet (Appendix 4), signed a consent form (Appendix 5), filled out Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) questionnaire and met the inclusion criteria described in section 3.1. The accelerometer was placed on the middle of measured distance of each platform as described in study 1 (pilot). The experimental procedure began with a warm-up (see section 3.2.1). Then each participant performed a static double leg squat for 30 s during eight different conditions: 4 frequencies (30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) on 2 platforms (Vibe plate platform and VibraMachine platform) with a 2 min rest between trials to avoid muscle fatigue. The order of the platform and frequency was randomised between participants by random number generator, and the experimental procedure was standardised across all 11 participants. The outputs of the Vibe

plate and VibraMachine platforms were both tested on the same visit with total of two visits, performed at the same time of day, to minimise potential diurnal effects. The tested variables for both platforms included acceleration, frequency and peak-to-peak displacement for each of the four frequency settings.

4.3.2.1 Data Analysis

The data on the accelerometer USB impact flash memory were downloaded for further analysis. The process of analysis was conducted as described in section 4.2.2.2.

4.3.2.2 Statistical analysis

Data was subject to tests of normality as described in section 3.5.2. Evaluation of reliability of frequency, acceleration and peak-to-peak displacement was tested between the two sessions using the mean for ICC, SEM, CV, while the median and the interquartile range calculated for not normally distributed data to perform the Wilcoxon two related-samples in SPSS version 25 (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK) to compare the WBV parameters at two time points per platform. The platform parameters validity was assessed via one-sample Wilcoxon test to compare calculated parameters to their theoretical values.

4.3.3 Results

All included data were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$), and this was supported by visual inspection of the associated data plots. An example of calculated acceleration data is shown in Figure 4.6 (panels a and c) and calculated frequency (panels b and d) using z-axis data is shown for a participant at a frequency of 30 Hz for the VibraMachine platform (panels a and b) and Vibe plate platform (panels c and d).

Figure 4.6: Example of calculated acceleration data and calculated frequency by Fast Fourier Transform analysis (Power Spectra Density) for a participant at a frequency of 30 Hz in a) calculated acceleration data/ VibraMachine platform b) calculated frequency by FFT / VibraMachine platform c) calculated acceleration data / Vibe plate platform d) calculated frequency by FFT/ Vibe plate platform.

4.3.3.1 Reliability

All the acceleration, frequency and peak-to-peak displacement data were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$), and this was supported from visual inspection of the associated data plots. The calculated mean for ICC values, 95% CIs, CV% and SEM values for acceleration, frequency and peak-to-peak displacement at frequency 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz of Vibe plate platform and VibraMachine platform are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. The mean values for Interclass correlation coefficients (ICC), 95% Confidence Interval (95% CIs), coefficients of variation (CV%) and standard error of measurement (SEM) for acceleration, frequency and peak-to-peak displacement at frequency 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz of Vibe plate platform and VibraMachine platform cross sessions 1 and 2.

Platform	Vibe plate platform			VibraMachine platform		
	Mean Acceleration (m.s ⁻²)	Mean Frequency (Hz)	Mean Peak-to-peak Displacement (mm)	Mean Acceleration (m.s ⁻²)	Mean Frequency (Hz)	Mean Peak-to-peak Displacement (mm)
ICC value	0.967	0.996	0.881	0.715	0.993	0.659
95% CIs	(0.941, 0.982)	(0.993, 0.998)	(0.791, 0.934)	(0.533, 0.835)	(0.988, 0.996)	(0.449, 0.801)
CV%	8.1	55.8	34.7	27.6	20.1	12.5
SEM	0.23	1.47	0.06	7.57	0.65	0.13

Observed median measurement differences between sessions for the three parameters showed no significant differences since most differences were very small (zero value or close to zero value) ($p > 0.05$), therefore both platforms showed a sufficient consistency in the three parameters (frequency, acceleration and peak to peak displacement) for frequency 30, 35 40 and 50 Hz (Table10.).

Table 10. The median calculated acceleration, Frequency and Peak-to-peak displacement, for Vibe plate platform and VibraMachine platform for sessions 1 and 2. IQR = interquartile range
Alpha value = p value

Vibe plate platform												
Frequency (Hz)	Acceleration (m.s ⁻²)				Frequency (Hz)				Peak-to-peak displacement (mm)			
	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value
	session 1	session 2			session 1	session 2			session 1	session 2		
30	14.3 (0.20)	14.3 (0.40)	0	0.717	32 (0.00)	32 (0.00)	0	0.564	0.71 (0.02)	0.71 (0.09)	0	0.201
35	14.8 (0.40)	14.8 (0.30)	0	0.785	34 (0.00)	34 (0.00)	0	0.317	0.70 (0.10)	0.60 (0.10)	0.1	0.655
40	15.1 (0.30)	15.1 (0.30)	0	0.572	44 (2.00)	44 (0.00)	0	0.317	0.39 (0.01)	0.40 (0.01)	0.01	0.670
50	16.7 (1.90)	17.2 (0.90)	0.5	0.894	56 (0.00)	56 (0.00)	0	0.564	0.30 (0.00)	0.30 (0.00)	0	0.317
VibraMachine platform												
Frequency (Hz)	Acceleration (m.s ⁻²)				Frequency (Hz)				Peak-to-peak displacement (mm)			
	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value
	session 1	session 2			session 1	session 2			session 1	session 2		
30	36.0 (3.40)	35.7 (3.40)	0.3	0.657	30 (0.00)	30 (0.00)	0	0.317	2.0 (0.20)	2.0 (0.20)	0	1.000
35	44.0 (3.70)	43.2 (3.80)	0.8	0.878	36 (2.00)	36 (2.00)	0	0.257	1.80 (0.20)	1.80 (0.20)	0	0.670
40	52.6 (4.40)	52.3 (4.10)	0.3	0.203	40 (0.00)	40 (0.00)	0	1.000	1.70 (0.10)	1.70 (0.10)	0	0.414
50	74.4 (4.30)	71.8 (5.00)	2.6	0.534	50 (0.00)	50 (0.00)	0	1.000	1.50 (0.00)	1.50 (0.10)	0	0.414

4.3.3.2 Validity

The observed acceleration and peak to peak displacement for the vibe plate platform presented greater differences compared to the difference at the same frequencies in the VibraMachine platform. The range of p-values across parameter outputs for both platforms were from 0.001 to 0.003 compared to their theoretical values. The VibraMachine platform outputs were closer to the theoretical values compared to the Vibe plate platform as shown in Table 11.

Table 11. The calculated acceleration, frequency and peak to peak displacement compared to the theoretical values, for Vibe plate platform and VibraMachine platform. IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = p value.

Vibe plate									
Frequency (Hz)	Acceleration ($m.s^{-2}$)			Frequency (Hz)			Peak-to-peak displacement (mm)		
	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	p value	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	p value	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	p value
30	71.1	14.4 (0.20)	0.003	30	32 (1.00)	0.002	4	0.72 (0.05)	0.003
35	96.7	14.8 (0.30)	0.003	35	34 (0.00)	0.002	4	0.65 (0.10)	0.003
40	126.3	15.1 (0.35)	0.003	40	44 (1.00)	0.002	4	0.40 (0.02)	0.003
50	197.4	17.1 (1.20)	0.003	50	56 (0.00)	0.002	4	0.30 (0.25)	0.001
VibraMachine									
Frequency (Hz)	Acceleration ($m.s^{-2}$)			Frequency (Hz)			Peak-to-peak displacement (mm)		
	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	p value	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	p value	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	p value
30	53.3	36.4 (2.85)	0.003	30	30 (0.00)	0.317	3	2.0 (0.25)	0.003
35	72.5	44.5 (3.70)	0.003	35	36 (1.00)	0.132	3	1.7 (0.15)	0.003
40	94.7	52.5 (3.80)	0.003	40	40 (0.00)	1.0	3	1.7 (0.10)	0.003
50	148	73.3 (6.05)	0.003	50	50 (0.00)	1.0	3	1.540 (0.05)	0.003

4.3.4 Discussion

This pilot work aimed to evaluate the inter-day reliability and validity of two vibration platform outputs and examine their consistency and compare the platform outputs to the theoretical values by performing a second, identical test within one week of the first. The results revealed a high level of consistency between days for both platforms. However, the validity was poor for the two platforms as neither produced the expected outputs: The Vibe plate platform produced lower outputs than the VibraMachine platform when compared to each platform's theoretical expected values. These results highlight the importance of preliminary validity work to ensure that each vibration platform produces the outputs expected. Although both platforms yielded the expected frequency compared with theoretical values, there was a large difference in peak-to-peak displacement and therefore likely acceleration output which can be related to platform manufacture issues. Previous studies have suggested that the calculated acceleration value is counted as the main parameter in evaluating the WBV platform output (Rauch et al., 2010; Lienhard et al., 2015). The significant reduction in Vibe plate platform acceleration output relative to the VibraMachine platform may be explained by the low calculated peak-to-peak displacement compared to the theoretical values (Vibe plate: 4 mm, VibraMachine: 3 mm).

Di Giminiani and colleagues (2015) reported the results of an evaluation and a comparison of the outputs of WBV frequencies from 20 Hz to 55 Hz frequencies for WBV platform type that vibrates vertically similar to what was tested in the present pilot study. Although those authors aimed to investigate the effect of WBV stimuli on EMG neuromuscular signals, WBV platform parameter outputs were calculated and evaluated specifically. They had calculated the resultant acceleration and peak to peak displacement; these ranged from 0.987 to 56 m.s⁻² and 0.15 to 1.21 mm respectively which was low compared to calculated values in the present study (acceleration

ranged from 14 to 74 $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$ and peak to peak displacement ranged from 0.6 to 2 mm). Also, Di Giminiani (2015) evaluated the reliability for the WBV platform acceleration only and found high reliability between days.

Work by Pollock et al. (2010) investigated WBV acceleration outputs for a range of frequencies (5 Hz to 30 Hz) on lower-limb EMG signals; those authors reported a positive correlation between the acceleration output and frequency. However, the resultant values were not compared with the theoretical acceleration values. Moreover, Pollock and colleagues (2010) obtained the acceleration values during the unloaded condition on the WBV platform which cannot be strictly comparable to those obtained in this study because the present study evaluated the WBV platform outputs during the body weight loaded condition (participant weight) and the WBV stimuli can be influenced by different loaded condition (Marín and Rhea, 2010). Although the findings from study1 (pilot, Chapter 4.1) suggested that the WBV platform outputs were independent of the body weights tested, no unloaded condition was included in the study 1 (pilot) above.

The literature investigating the effects of the Vibramachine platform during exercises in healthy individuals has been limited. However, the Vibe plate platform has been used to investigate the effect of vibration stimuli on jump performance in trained individuals (Hammer, Linton and Hammer, 2018). Also, it has been used to evaluate the effect of squat on vertical jump in athlete individuals (Benik, 2013). In previous literature, the WBV stimuli found no effects on jump performance and vertical jump. The reliability and validity of Vibe plate platform outputs were not assessed. Therefore, further research is required to investigate the effect of the previous WBV platforms which may illustrate a possible indication for rehabilitation programmes. Moreover, WBV platform outputs need to be evaluated before being used in the literature.

In addition to the above points, one final point that merits discussion is that the calculated acceleration in the present study was lower than expected and which may be a consequence of low peak-to-peak displacement for these platforms. This was reported previously in a study investigating WBV platform vibrated vertically (Zaidell et al., 2019). The results of that study are consistent with the observation that WBV platform outputs, regardless of the parameters, do not necessarily demonstrate the actual WBV platform setting (Zaidell et al., 2019). Further, each platform device can produce different acceleration outputs depending on a multitude of variables: platform type, body weight (Pel et al., 2009), parameters, positioning (Zaidell et al., 2019) and accelerometer measuring location (Pollock et al., 2010).

4.3.5 Conclusion

The VibraMachine platform showed acceptable consistency and although consistency was lower for the VibraMachine than the Vibe plate platform, the output parameters of the VibraMachine platform appeared to more closely match expected values. Therefore, the VibraMachine platform was chosen for utilisation in future studies.

4.4 Pilot 3: Testing Validity of Thera-Band Resistance Bands

4.4.1 Introduction

Thera-Band is a resistance tool can be used in strengthening exercises. The elongation of the Thera-Bands can produce range of tensions/forces, each force labelled by specific colour. The produced forces which ranged from 1.1 to 40.1 Ibs with elongation 25% to 250%, can be used to strengthen muscles in exercise protocols (The Hygenic Corporation, Akron, 2012). Although theoretical forces of Thera-Band are available from the manufacturer, evaluation of the produced forces is necessary to enhance clinical and therapeutic outcomes. Such evaluation requires at the outset an investigation of equipment validity and consistency of equipment effectiveness.

The reliability of the actual forces, and validity were evaluated by comparing the actual forces to the theoretical forces to be conducted before being used in research or rehabilitation programmes. Thera-Bands have been used in knee extension exercises without evaluation the reliability and validity of produced forces (Jakobsen et al., 2012; Miao et al., 2015). However, Andersen et al. (2010) found that Thera-Band produced valid force during upper limb exercises without mentioning the evaluated elongation, and with no reliability evaluation. As the lower limb muscles involve larger muscle cross-sectional area, further evaluation is required using dynamometer to evaluate the reliability and validity of Thera-Bands at 100%, 200% and 250% elongations, regardless the muscle.

Study 3 (pilot) continues with the main theme of Chapter 4: Assessment of the instruments to be used to generate data for the rest of the thesis. Based on the literature in Chapter 2, resisted hip adduction was identified to be commonly used during knee exercises to elicit enhanced VM neuromuscular activity in individuals with PFPS (Coqueiro et al., 2005; Miao et al., 2015). Iterations of Thera-Band have been used as a therapeutic tool in different rehabilitation

programmes for patient populations and for strengthening exercises in healthy individuals (Wallace et al., 2006; Lorenz, 2014; Biçer et al., 2015). Moreover, Thera-Band is suggested to increase muscle activation (Aboodarda et al., 2016). For the purpose of this thesis, validity and reliability of Thera-Band was investigated prior to its inclusion in the remaining studies in this thesis. Therefore, this pilot work will assess the intra-session reliability and validity of calculated forces for green and blue Thera-Band as these specific two colours were selected according to previous similar studies (Jakobsen et al., 2012; Miao et al., 2015).

4.4.2 Methods

Green and blue Thera-Bands (Hygenic Corporation, Akron, USA) were tested in this pilot work. Both tested Thera-Bands were elongated to 100%, 200% and 250% of their original length to compare the resultant force to the theoretical force obtained from the manufacturer's documentation. For a length of 60 cm Thera-Band, 100%, 200% and 250% elongation distances were determined from a fixed point and marked on the floor (elongation distance of 120 cm, 180 cm and 210 cm respectively). The elongation distance previously used in the literature was between 200% and 250% (Miao et al., 2015) which was illustrated to be effective in training programmes (The Hygenic Corporation, Akron, 2012). The two ends of each Thera-Band were tightened together to create a double loop around a fixed point. Figure 4.7 shows an example of 100% Thera-Band elongation. A MicroFET2 handheld strength dynamometer (Hogan Health Industries, Inc., West Jordan, USA) was placed in the middle of the tightened elastic band (Figure 4.10).

Figure 4.7: a) Thera-Band position during rest of 60 cm length. b) Thera-Band during elongation of 100%.

The pounds (lb) unit used in MicroFET2 handheld to measure the Thera-Band force. The MicroFET2 handheld dynamometer is considered a reliable and valid tool to investigate resistance Thera-Band force production (Sung, Yi and Shin, 2019). Each elongation trial was repeated three times during the same testing session and the average of three tests was calculated. The resting time between trials was 2 min to avoid upper limb muscle fatigue for the researcher.

4.4.2.1 Data Analysis

After recording the force readings from the MicroFET2 handheld dynamometer, data were imported into Excel (version 2016). The mean and SD of force was obtained for both the green and blue bands and compared with the theoretical forces found on the Thera-Band resistance website (The Hygenic Corporation, 2012).

4.4.2.2 Statistical analysis

Each elongation of 100%, 200% and 250% completed six times (total of 9 data points for each colour). Data normality was assessed as described in section 3.5.2. Then, the mean difference for the three trials was calculated. A paired sample t-test was performed using SPSS version 25 (IBM

UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK) to evaluate the intra-session consistency of the actual force for each colour and elongation. The experimentally determined readings were compared with the theoretical force readings claimed by the manufacturer, via one-sample t-test using SPSS version 25 (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK). The percentage CV as described below according to Andersen et al., (2017) and ICC (described in Chapter 3) were calculated across the two Thera-Band.

$$CV = \frac{SD \text{ of the 3 trials for required elongation of the required elastic Thera-Band colour}}{\text{Mean of the 3 trials for required elongation of the required elastic Thera-Band colour}} \times 100$$

SD= standard deviation.

The difference between the deviation of the green and the blue Thera-Bands at elongation of 100%, 200% and 250% was tested with by paired sample t-test.

4.4.3 Results

All included data were normally distributed ($p > 0.05$). The green Thera-Band measured force showed high intra-session reliability with ICC = 0.92 and a 95% CI of the mean difference [0.472, 0.998], and CV% ranged between 2.70 and 12.42. For the blue Thera-Band, ICC = 0.91 and a 95% CI of the mean difference [0.459, 0.998], and CV% ranged between 3.29 and 13.57.

Table 12 and Figure 4.8 show that no statistically significant difference in force was observed between actual and theoretical forces for the 100% elongation of the blue Thera-Band, 200% and 250% elongation of the green and blue Thera-Band, while the 100% elongation of the green Thera-Band showed a significant difference in force compared to theoretical force $p = 0.039$.

Table 12. Mean \pm SD of actual vs. theoretical forces for the percentage elongation of 100% (120 cm), 200% (180 cm) and 250% (210 cm) for green and blue Thera-Bands. Alpha value = p value, 95% Confidence Interval of the Difference = 95% CI.

	Green Thera-Band			Blue Thera-Band		
	100% elongation	200% elongation	250% elongation	100% elongation	200% elongation	250% elongation
Mean measurement \pm SD (lbs)	5.47 \pm 0.31	8.87 \pm 1.10	9.80 \pm 0.265	7.80 \pm 1.06	10.67 \pm 0.35	12.73 \pm 0.70
Manufacture theoretical Value (lbs)	4.6	7.9	9.6	7.1	11.1	13.3
p value	0.039	0.268	0.321	0.371	0.166	0.29
95% CI	(0.17, 1.63)	(-1.77, 3.70)	(-0.46, 0.86)	(-1.92, 3.32)	(-1.30, 0.44)	(-2.3, 1.18)

Figure 4.8: Mean \pm SD for the average actual vs. theoretical forces for the percentage elongation of 100% (120 cm), 200% (180 cm) and 250% (210 cm) for green and blue Thera-Bands.

The difference between the deviation of the actual force of the green to their theoretical values was compared to the deviation of the actual force of the blue Thera-Band to their theoretical values, showed the green Thera-Band has higher deviation from theoretical values at 100% and 200%

elongation compared to the Blue Thera-Band. However, none of these reported differences are statistically significant.

4.4.4 Discussion

This pilot work sought to assess the validity and consistency of two strengths of Thera-Bands. The results showed high validity and intra-session consistency for green and blue Thera-Bands except at 100% elongation of the green Thera-Band. The force required to elongate the bands was experimentally determined to be similar to the values attained as part of a study on maximal isokinetic strength in shoulder muscle activation (Nyberg et al., 2014). No differences were found between the Kin-Com dynamometer and the Thera-Band in assessing muscle activity in healthy individuals (Nyberg et al., 2014). These findings were further confirmed in a study on the knee extensor muscle (Lopes et al., 2018). Therefore, these findings agreed with the present study findings although the differences in the type of dynamometer; Kin-Com dynamometer and MicroFET2 handheld strength dynamometer respectively.

Wallace, Winchester and McGuigan (2006) reported on their assessment of the reliability and validity of forces required for elongation of red and blue resistance Thera-Bands. Although they found similar ICC of 0.98 and resultant force values compared with the reported force from the manufacturer, the mean force required to elongate the blue Thera-Band was found to be lower than the theoretical reported force (Wallace, et al., 2006), which is in agreement with the findings of this pilot study. The small difference of lbs between the resultant actual force and the theoretical values can be defined as a safety procedure to avoid muscle tearing (slingshot effect) on lifters or researcher (Wallace, Winchester and McGuigan, 2006). This could occur, for example, during performance of exercises if an individual stretched the Thera-Band with high speed and without caution (Wallace, Winchester and McGuigan, 2006).

Recently published literature has evaluated the validity of Thera-Bands compared to different tools for measurement of muscle strength during evaluating the MVC values (Nyberg, 2016, Andersen et al., 2017). Thera-Band appears to be a valid and reliable tool compared with other techniques, such as isokinetic measurement, used in MVC. Thus, Thera-Band is suggested to be reliable and valid when comparing with theoretical force production (Nyberg, 2016), largely in agreement with the finding of this study.

4.4.5 Conclusion

Green and blue resistance Thera-Band are a valid and reliable tool in a resistance exercise intervention. The green resistance Thera-Band was selected for inclusion in Chapters 6 and 7, due to the force readings being higher than the manufacturer's values compared to the blue band. However, either Thera-Bands colours can be used for further research since there was no significant difference between green and blue Thera-Band and both Thera-Band are following the manufacturer's values.

4.5 Pilot 4: Investigating the test–retest inter-day reliability of the Delsys Trigno Avanti wireless electromyography system.

4.5.1 Introduction

EMG is defined as an investigational method specialised in capturing and evaluating muscle electrical activity (Konrad, 2006). EMG can be used as a tool to evaluate rehabilitation programmes, exercise training and scientific research (Konrad, 2006). The EMG system used in the present study is a non-invasive method with electrodes placed on the skin surface to analyse muscle response. Moreover, it can be used to evaluate muscle activity and muscle fatigue (Nussbaum, 2001, Avelar et al., 2013, Saeterbakken and Fimland, 2013). Although this equipment is safe and easy to use, EMG outputs are prone to high levels of variability between individuals but also within individuals, thus inconsistent superficial neuromuscular outputs within and between sessions can be observed (Oskouei, Paulin and Carman, 2013). In light of this, reliability of EMG systems used should be quantified. Although, inter-day reliability of EMG systems have been investigated and the results reported moderate to excellent reliability in the literature (McKenzie et al., 2010; Bolgla et al., 2010), low ICC values or a high CV were observed between studies (Thuresson et al., 2005; Oskouei et al., 2013). Many factors can lead to low inter-day reliability in EMG experiments, including experiment protocol (skin preparations, electrodes placement and participant positioning) and level of physical activity in the 24 hours preceding testing (Day, 2002, Sorbie et al., 2018). However, good consistency of EMG readings on upper limb muscles (deltoid, biceps and triceps muscles) with ICC ranged from 0.52 to 0.98 was reported in another study utilising stable and unstable surfaces by pushing hard surface and swiss ball respectively during wall press, bench press and push up positions (de Araújo et al., 2009). All previous studies did not use the Delsys Trigno Avanti EMG system which is the focus of the present study 4 (pilot). Also, the presence of conflicting reports of consistency and reliability of

the equipment is illustrative of the need for a thorough evaluation of the EMG system before being used in an experimental study.

Often the assessment of the reliability of neuromuscular responses is not explained sufficiently well in published studies, or sufficient detail of how the intra-day reliability was obtained is lacking (for example: electrode position and statistical methods) (Chester et al., 2008; Qi and Ng, 2007; Avelar et al., 2013). Therefore, a clear protocol to investigate the reliability of neuromuscular activity is indeed necessary to explain EMG response variation within a session or between sessions on multiple days.

Evaluation of the EMG response during vibration stimuli could plausibly affect signal reliability; vibrations can affect the consistency in the obtained posture on a vibration platform. Further, the electromagnetic noise produced from a vibration platform could influence neuromuscular signal accuracy. Therefore, suitable band-pass and notch filtering methods should be applied to the EMG signal according to the selective frequency to avoid oversight in signal recording (see section 3.5.1) (Borges et al., 2017). High intra-session and inter-day reproducibility of EMG output has been reported during WBV stimuli on VM and VL muscles (ICC ranged from 0.92 to 0.98), where filters were not used and a statistical analysis applied by using median regression in identifying the WBV platform noise (Di Giminiani et al. 2015). This method was used because data were not normally distributed, however the method used by Di Giminiani is not commonly used in the literature.

The reliability of Delsys Trigno Avanti wireless system was investigated on normalised deltoid muscle activity during shoulder flexion and abduction (Varghese et al., 2014). High reliability of deltoid EMG output has been reported with ICCs 0.8 during shoulder flexion and abduction (Varghese et al., 2014). Although Varghese et al. (2014) focused on the inter-day reliability of the

upper limb muscles and their findings may not directly applicable to lower limb muscles, hence the aim of pilot study 4 is to investigate the inter-day reliability of VM and VL neuromuscular responses using the Delsys Trigno Avanti wireless system during static squat positioning with vibration stimuli in healthy individuals.

4.5.2 Methods

4.5.2.1 Participants

A total of 26 healthy participants took part in this study. The mean \pm SD age of participants was 35.1 ± 8.3 years, mean height 172.4 ± 6.9 cm, mean \pm SD weight 74.5 ± 13.5 kg and mean \pm SD BMI 25.1 ± 4.4 kg/m². All 26 participants read the participant information sheet (Appendix 4), signed the consent form (Appendix 5) and answered the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) questionnaire. Ethical approval was obtained from the UWS School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee application number 1090 and submission number of 4338.

4.5.2.2 Protocol

This pilot work was a repeated-measure study conducted across two sessions. Session 1 incorporated demographic data collection (height, weight and age). Height was determined using a stadiometer (Leicester Height Measure – Seca, Ltd, Birmingham, UK) and weight recorded using (Omron Digital Weight Scale HN-286, Japan). Following a warm-up (see section 3.2.1), EMG electrodes were placed (see section 3.3.2) and MVIC obtained (see section 3.2.2). Thereafter, participants stood on the WBV platform and performed five trials of static squats, each of 30 s duration and involving five frequencies (0 Hz, 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) in a randomised order by random number generator. Details of position, posture and rest time are illustrated in section 3.3.1. At the end of session 1, electrodes were removed and a cool down of lower-limb-

stretching exercises were carried out. Session 2 was conducted within one week of session 1 under the same experimental protocol.

4.5.2.3 Data analysis

All 26 volunteers completed the two sessions. Data analysis was performed using EMGworks (version 4.5) as described in sections 3.5.1 and 3.5.2. All data were rectified and sampled with band-pass and notch filters applied in the same way as previously described in section 3.5.2 at frequencies of 0 Hz, 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz. All data collected from the squatting trials were normalised to the highest MVIC value for each muscle (as shown in section 3.2.2 and 3.5.1). Data from the middle 10 s of 30 s were retained for analysis, and the initial 10 s and final 10 s were excluded as the vibration platform takes time to reach the desired frequency. Subsequently, data were transferred to Excel (version 2016) and SPSS Statistics IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK; version 25) for further analysis (see sections 3.5.1 and 3.5.2). The CV% and SEM were calculated in Excel (version 2016) and the ICC was calculated in SPSS Statistics (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK; version 25).

4.5.2.4 Statistical analysis

Data normality was assessed on the difference of VM and VL normalised EMG amplitude for dominant and non-dominant limbs at frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz between the two sessions as described in section 3.5.2. Then, the ICC was calculated in SPSS Statistics (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK; version 25). The Wilcoxon two related-samples test was used to evaluate the inter-day reliability of normalised EMG amplitude of VM and VL for dominant and non-dominant limbs over the five vibration frequencies.

4.5.3 Results

The data for dominant and non-dominant limbs over the five vibration frequencies were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$) and this was supported from visual inspection of the associated data plots. The ICC, CV% and SEM for dominant and non-dominant limbs over the five vibration frequencies are summarised in Table 13.

Table 13. Interclass correlation coefficients (ICC), coefficients of variation (CV) and standard error of measurement (SEM) for maximum normalised amplitude of vastus medialis (VM) and vastus lateralis (VL) muscles in dominant and non-dominant limbs between two sessions.

Frequency (Hz)	Dominant limb						Non-Dominant limb					
	VM			VL			VM			VL		
	ICC	CV%	SEM	ICC	CV%	SEM	ICC	CV%	SEM	ICC	CV%	SEM
0	0.71	48.1	16.1	0.71	38.9	12.6	0.67	48.7	18.3	0.76	38.0	11.4
30	0.53	50.7	22.4	0.71	43.1	14.1	0.66	47.4	18.3	0.82	37.0	9.3
35	0.70	48.2	17.2	0.87	47.4	10.4	0.56	56.7	24.4	0.82	37.5	9.5
40	0.57	52.6	22.1	0.82	50.9	13.0	0.72	49.2	15.3	0.86	42.1	9.1
50	0.65	52.5	20.3	0.82	49.1	13.3	0.57	46.3	18.2	0.71	40.2	13.4

The ICCs for maximum normalised amplitude of VM EMG in the dominant and non-dominant limbs ranged from 0.53 to 0.71 and 0.56 to 0.72 respectively. The ICCs for maximum normalised amplitude of VL EMG in the dominant and non-dominant legs ranged from 0.71 to 0.87 and 0.71 to 0.86 respectively.

No significant differences in the VM and VL maximum normalised amplitude for the dominant and non-dominant limbs over the five vibration frequencies were found between session 1 and session 2 (Table 14). Therefore, EMG signals showed a sufficient consistency in the dominant and non-dominant limbs for frequency 0, 30, 35, 40 and 50 Hz.

Table 14. The median values for maximum normalised amplitude of vastus medialis (VM) and vastus lateralis (VL) muscles activity in dominant and non-dominant legs in two sessions. IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = p value.

Dominant limb								
Normalised VM%					Normalised VL %			
Frequency (Hz)	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value
	session 1	session 2			session 1	session 2		
0	60.97 (53.97)	57.69 (38.29)	3.2	0.603	61.22 (38.99)	55.88 (22.45)	5.3	0.159
30	55.42 (52.92)	57.71 (42.89)	2.2	0.990	60.36 (41.83)	53.53 (27.05)	6.9	0.182
35	57.16 (49.16)	58.23(34.29)	1.1	0.790	60.44 (34.54)	53.58 (26.53)	6.8	0.124
40	58.12 (36.79)	64.04 (40.80)	5.9	0.949	55.90 (39.53)	53.70 (24.97)	2.2	0.248
50	56.67 (51.53)	54.17 (40.91)	2.5	0.395	60.25 (36.89)	55.63 (21.59)	4.7	0.137
Non-Dominant limb								
Normalised VM %					Normalised VL %			
Frequency (Hz)	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value	Median (IQR)		Median difference	p value
	session 1	session 2			session 1	session 2		
0	64.82(50.30)	61.65 (48.80)	3.2	0.316	58.02 (37.83)	52.59 (29.92)	5.4	0.174
30	56.61 (29.87)	63.63 (39.01)	7	0.485	58.320 (31.52)	59.09 (28.29)	0.8	0.568
35	58.37 (23.34)	61.48 (40.69)	3.1	0.381	58.68 (33.44)	57.49 (30.02)	1.2	0.809
40	52.48 (37.20)	57.94 (44.14)	5.4	0.032	48.98 (34.23)	54.22 (29.76)	5.3	0.585
50	56.56 (33.84)	60.86 (36.45)	3.5	0.395	59.23 (34.65)	55.62 (32.49)	3.6	0.166

4.5.4 Discussion

This pilot work aimed to investigate the reliability of maximum normalised EMG amplitude for VM and VL muscles obtained during static squat positioning during vibration stimuli. The data suggested that the EMG measurements during WBV taken by the Delsys Trigno Avanti wireless system are reliable. Bolgla et al. (2010), Sorbie et al. (2018) were inconsistent in reporting the

accepted ICC range values on VL neuromuscular activity during static squat and dynamic stair descending. However, the present study ICC values which were assessed similar to Koo and Li, (2016), found moderate to high EMG reliability values for maximum normalised EMG amplitude for VM and VL muscles in static double leg squat positioning on the vibration platform with frequencies of 0 Hz, 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz.

The ICC values determined in this study were comparable to previous reliability studies where the ICC values for both VM and VL muscles found to be greater than 0.65 (Zech et al., 2008; Bolgla et al., 2010). However, those studies measured during isometric knee extension and stairs descending phases across three independent visits, which is different from the present study. Three of the VM ICC values determined in the present study were lower than 0.65 (namely 0.53, 0.56 and 0.57) and this could be as a result of differences in participant sample size, characteristics or study protocols (obtained position, type of movement, resting period between trials and visits, data normalisation method and statistical analysis). However, evaluation of the reliability of EMG signals during static squat with WBV stimuli was reported by Di Giminiani et al. (2015), where VM and VL neuromuscular activity exhibited excellent consistency within the same session and between days with ICCs 0.92 and 0.98 respectively. That study evaluated inter-day reliability by calculating the mean of two readings obtained during the same session (mean intra-day reliability) and no notch was applied (Di Giminiani et al., 2015). By calculating the mean EMG signals, the inter-day reliability may be enhanced (Balshaw et al., 2017). In another publication, ICC values showed high reliability for VM and VL neuromuscular activity with ICCs 0.93 and 0.94 respectively, however no notch filter was applied during data acquisition to exclude the electromagnetic noise (Marín and Hazell, 2014). Di Giminiani and colleagues (2015) used an electro-goniometer to control knee angle while Marín and Hazell, (2014) used manual goniometer.

Visual feedback may enhance the ability of the subject to maintain the joint angle and therefore increase reading consistency (Campenella, Mattacola and Kimura, 2000). The visual feedback method was not applied in the study by Di Giminiani and colleagues (2015) who noted that for consistency during collecting EMG signals, participant feet locations were marked on the vibration platform to increase reliability between trials, including within-session and between days. This method was not applied in the present study to avoid possible bias on EMG signal. Although Marín and Hazell (2014) reported high reliability readings with ICC values 0.93 and 0.94 for VM and VL neuromuscular activity respectively, no details were provided to describe the reliability evaluation procedure (Marín and Hazell, 2014).

Various EMG systems have been used when evaluating the reliability of EMG neuromuscular responses. Lee et al. (2012) used the Delsys Trigno Wireless EMG system to investigate the reliability and validity for MVICs of the quadriceps muscle by three different measurement tools: handheld, stationary dynamometry and manual testing. The reliability at Lee et al. (2012) was determined within-session (ICCs ranged from 0.96 to 0.99) without indicated the distance used between electrode and the electrodes placement were not marked. Also, intra-day reliability investigated with the Myon 230 system was described as excellent within the same session and between days for deltoid and vastus lateralis muscles during front raise exercise and squat exercise respectively (Sorbie et al., 2018). Although the reliability of the Myon 230 system in lower-limb muscles during squat exercise was high (ICC > 0.8), the standard distance between electrodes used for each muscle was 2 cm, which may increase the possibility of cross-talk. In contrast, the inter-electrode spacing in the Delsys Trigno Avanti Wireless EMG system is 10 mm. In Sorbie et al. (2018), electrode placement was marked on the skin, which may result in the high ICC values as

electrode repositioning is likely to be more accurate (Lee et al., 2012) and therefore increasing the EMG reliability.

The consistency of verbal instructions may also influence the reliability and validity of EMG responses during exercises involving the vibration platform. Standardisation of verbal instructions during data collection process and the consistency in maintaining body position to avoid shifting body weight forwards or backwards across trials, is suggested to critically influence the EMG signal and response (Di Giminiani et al., 2013; Perchthaler, Horstmann and Grau, 2013; Calatayud et al., 2016). Verbal instructions can be standardised but body position may still vary somewhat due to participants postural sway or not able to maintain a desired position. Also, the variation in participants' demographics such as BMI can influence the EMG signals. Ten participants in the present study had BMI values recorded above 25 kg/m^2 (25.1 kg/m^2). It has been reported that higher BMI can negatively influence the accuracy of EMG signal response based on muscle thickness and body fat composition (Cho, Kim and Park, 2018). Certainly, EMG signal accuracy can be affected by individual characteristics: muscle size, BMI, physical activity during the 72 hours preceding the test and fat composition (Sorbie et al., 2018). Therefore, in future studies on the consistency and reliability of EMG readings, BMI lower than 25 kg/m^2 should be considered to improve EMG signal accuracy.

Given that VM and VL muscles consist of a large muscle belly, the application of one sensor on a muscle of such large size may influence EMG output by failing to collect EMG data across the whole muscle. Balshaw et al. (2017) investigated the MVC EMG reliability and validity of VM and VL muscles by one sensor on each muscle during knee extension in sitting position using a dynamometer, and compared to two sensors. By using data collected from an average of two sites and sensors showed a small but consistent improvement in ICC values and a significant decrease

in CV for VM (ICC 0.910) and VL (ICC 0.916) muscles versus single-site measurement (ICCs for VM muscle 0.865 and 0.822, VL muscle 0.684 and 0.802) (Balshaw et al., 2017). Moreover, the results indicated that a holistic evaluation of the quadriceps muscles led to increased reliability and consistency of EMG readings compared to separate analyses of each individual quadriceps muscle (Balshaw et al., 2017). Moreover, high density EMG, which adopts many sampling sites over a set grid, showed high reliability between days (ICC >0.6) when used to assess the VM muscle (Martinez-Valdes et al., 2017). Thus, sensor number on VM and VL muscles can influence the accuracy of EMG response as two sensors on one muscle may raise the chance of cross-talk between muscles, which also depends on the distance between the sensors. In the present study, one sensor per muscle was used according to SENIAM guidelines. So, the best method to avoid cross-talk is to select the number of sensors, and inter-electrode distance depending on muscle size, as multiple sensors can be used for large muscles and this needs further research.

Standardisation of the duration of time between visits is an essential point to be considered during testing of EMG reliability because the consistency of time period between visits across the participants can impact upon data consistency (Oskouei, Paulin and Carman, 2013). The length of time between visits in the present study was greater than 24 hours and less than seven days. This point (the length of time between visits) was evaluated by Kollmitzer, Ebenbichler and Kopf (1999), by investigating MVCs neuromuscular responses during knee extension between three intervals (3 min, 90 min and 6 weeks) for quadriceps muscles by a dynamometer. Higher EMG reproducibility was exhibited between tests separated by less time (Kollmitzer, Ebenbichler and Kopf, 1999). This highlights the importance of short time intervals between visits in investigating EMG reliability.

In the present study, trials which occurred within the same visit were separated by a 2 min rest period to avoid the muscle fatigue which can occur in participants (de Araújo et al., 2009). The resting time between trials when experiencing vibration stimuli or recording EMG responses is varied throughout the literature: reports have documented resting times of between 30 s and 5 min or more to avoid muscle fatigue (Di Giminiani et al., 2009; Eftekhari et al., 2012; Giombini et al., 2013). However, no additional benefits regarding the consistency in ICC values and muscle activity signals were observed when participants were given a 4 min rest time compared to a 2 min rest time (Carlucci et al., 2016). A reduction in rest time to 30 s between trials did not negatively influence muscle performance during an evaluation of quadriceps muscle and neuromuscular output, and moderate to excellent consistency was observed between trials (Bolgia et al., 2010). A resting time of 2 min between trials in the present study was thus likely to be sufficient time for muscle recovery.

The effect of different exposure times to vibration stimuli was not evaluated in the present study as all participants were exposed to 30 s of vibration across all trials regardless of the frequency. The effects of different exposure times to the Power plate vibration platform on muscle power performance were previously investigated with 30 s, 40 s, 50 s and 60 s exposure times; no significant effect was described for muscle power outputs and EMG response (Adams et al., 2009). Conversely, a 15 s exposure time to WBV stimuli with a rest of 30 s between trials enhanced VL muscle response during a semi-squat exercise (Borges et al., 2017). Thus, a 30 s exposure to WBV stimulation was considered to be an optimal duration to stimulate and activate EMG signals.

The static and dynamic movements are core component during evaluating the EMG reliability. EMG responses were found to be higher during a dynamic squat compared to a static squat (Hazell, Jakobi and Kenno, 2007). However, the recorded signal consistency was not investigated and

therefore would need further consideration. The results of Bolgla et al. (2010) supported the idea that EMG responses were higher during dynamic movement (descending stairs) in individuals with PFPS, therefore EMG reliability should be assessed further during dynamic movement. Static and dynamic movement may influence neuromuscular activity, particularly during WBV stimulation. A comparison of EMG responses during dynamic movement compared with static movement with WBV stimuli was conducted previously, which suggested EMG responses were significantly higher during dynamic squatting with and without WBV stimuli compared to static squat (Hazell et al., 2007). These results conflicted with a study conducted by Abercromby et al. (2007). They found that EMG signals for lower limb muscles during static squat positioning appeared to exhibit equal EMG signals compared to the dynamic squat. The knee angle obtained during static squat was 20° of knee flexion, which was comparable with the dynamic squatting range between 5° and 40° for knee flexion angle (Abercromby et al., 2007), indicating an advantage for a dynamic squat with large knee angle range than the static squat. Moreover, VM EMG response is presumed to be higher at knee-flexion angles between 65° and 90° during either dynamic or static squat positioning (Tang et al., 2001; Jaberzadeh et al., 2016; Marchetti et al., 2016). However, the consistency of EMG responses in both of the previous studies was not tested. In addition, the dynamic contractions required greater body control than static contractions as body weight shifted forwards and backwards as well as upwards and downwards, which necessitates greater muscle control and contraction force against ground gravity (Bolgla et al., 2010).

4.5.5 Limitations

There are two main limitations of evaluating consistency or reliability of EMG signals during a static squat with WBV stimuli. First, the MVIC was conducted as part of an open kinetic-chain (OKC) exercise and compared with a closed kinetic-chain (CKC) exercise on a WBV platform.

Although OKC exercises are typically used in the evaluation of MVIC (Roelants et al., 2006, Huang and Pang, 2019, Nimphius et al., 2019), determining MVIC during CKC exercises may affect the reliability of calculated normalised EMG signals during WBV stimuli in the present study. Second, study participants did not attend familiarisation visits, which may reduce EMG reliability values across both visits during static squat positioning on the WBV platform. Performing the familiarisation prior to evaluate the required task may increase the participants ability to obtain and maintain their posture (Mileva et al., 2009). However, in the present study, participants performed squatting without vibration as part of their warm-up to allow the research to instruct on the correct squatting posture. As a moderate to high EMG reliability between two visits was identified in this study without prior familiarisation, it can be proposed that the influence of not including familiarisation on EMG reliability was minimal.

4.5.6 Conclusion

The Trigno Avanti Wireless Delsys system was determined to be reliable for the evaluation of VM and VL neuromuscular responses during vibration stimuli in terms of static double leg squat positioning in healthy individuals. Although not the focus of this thesis, further research is needed to evaluate the reliability of the EMG system on quadriceps neuromuscular activity during dynamic squatting during vibration stimuli.

4.6 Chapter Conclusion

This chapter encompassed the description of four studies (pilots). The first study (pilot) investigated the effect of different equivalent body weights (90kg, 95 kg and 100 kg) on the outputs (acceleration and peak-to-peak displacement) of two WBV platforms (vibe plate and VibraMachine platforms) set to the following frequencies: 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz. Both WBV platform outputs found to be consistence for weight conditions of 90 kg, 95 kg and 100 kg.

The second study (pilot) investigated the inter day reliability and validity of the outputs of two WBV platforms (vibe plate and VibraMachine platforms) set at 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz. The VibraMachine platform showed lower consistency in peak-to-peak displacement with ICC of 0.66 compared to the Vibe plate platform with ICC of 0.88 cross four frequencies. However, the VibraMachine platform showed higher level of validity compared to theoretical values than Vibe plate platform. Therefore, the VibraMachine platform was chosen for utilisation in future studies.

The third study (pilot) investigated the intra-session reliability and validity of green and blue Thera-Band forces. The MicroFET2 handheld dynamometer was used to evaluate the force production generated using the green and blue Thera-bands when elongated to 100%, 200% and 250% respectively. The experimentally determined readings were compared with the theoretical force readings claimed by the manufacturer. The green Thera-band was selected the force readings being higher than the manufacturer's values compared to the blue band.

For the last study (pilot), the inter-day reliability of the Trigno Avanti Wireless Delsys electromyography system was evaluated for VM and VL neuromuscular activity obtained during a static double leg squat with WBV stimuli (0 Hz, 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz). The Delsys EMG system was determined to be reliable for the evaluation of VM and VL neuromuscular responses during vibration stimuli with frequency 0 Hz, 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz during a static double leg squat.

Evaluation of equipment is an important consideration which can influence data collection and outcome measures when such equipment is used as experimental tools in scientific research or treatment tools in clinical practice for patient populations, as well as during strengthening exercises for healthy individuals. The overall conclusion of this chapter was that the tools tested in these pilot studies were valid and reliable to be used further on in research.

Chapter 5

Inter-day reliability of individualised WBV stimuli on acute VM neuromuscular activity during static double leg squats in healthy individuals

5.1 Introduction

The effects of exposure to acute and chronic WBV stimulation have been investigated in rehabilitation and strengthening programs in both healthy individuals and in-patient populations (Marin and Rhea, 2010; Osawa, Oguma and Ishii, 2013). Such studies commonly investigate the effect of WBV on muscle outcomes such as muscle activity. In a previous study conducted by Fratini and colleagues (2009), WBV between 10 Hz and 50Hz was found to elicit the VM and VL acute muscle activities during static squat compared to the same squat position without vibration. In that study, the EMG signals were not normalised to MVIC values. However, Lee (2017) found that WBV stimuli which ranged from 10 Hz to 40 Hz increased the normalised VL EMG signal during static standing position compared to static standing position without vibration stimuli. In that study, Lee (2017) evaluated exercises programs involve WBV stimuli in standing position which was not recommended as discussed in Chapter 4; standing with hip and knee flexion angles of 0° may possibly increase transmitting the vibration to the head (Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005; Pel et al., 2009). The exposure to WBV in positions which have muscles lengthened such as squatting with 60°- 90° knee flexion, has been suggested to increase the EMG response (Bosco et al., 1999; Cardinale and Lim, 2003; Cochrane et al., 2009; Avelar et al., 2013; Lienhard et al., 2014). Also, evaluating exercises involving WBV stimuli by EMG signals can be influenced by factors including platform parameters (frequency and peak-to-peak displacement), participant position and exposure time. WBV parameters which can be used in exercises generally, produce consistent stimuli across platforms from different manufacturers. There was limited evidence

based on the effect of the individual body position and body weight on the WBV platform parameters (Di Giminiani et al., 2010; Perchthaler, Horstmann and Grau, 2013; Ritzmann, Gollhofer and Kramer, 2013) and only the effect of body weight has been evaluated and discussed in Chapter 4.

The individualised WBV frequency is a specific frequency that ranges from 5 Hz to 65 Hz and which can elicit individual's muscle activity, was evaluated on VL neuromuscular activity during static squat by Cardinale and Lim (2003) and Nigg and Wakeling, (2001). Cardinale and Lim (2003) investigated the presence of an individualised WBV frequency at 30 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz for VL muscle response during static squat positioning. In that study, vibration stimuli at 30 Hz achieved the highest VL muscle activation for 16 healthy females compared to 40 Hz and 50 Hz. Vibration parameters can stimulate the neuromuscular response via the TVR (Di Giminiani et al., 2010) and these reactions vary according to platform type, muscle size and muscle distance from the vibration platform. Therefore, each muscle in an individual has an optimal frequency to trigger muscle reflex during vibration stimuli (Cardinale and Lim, 2003; Carlucci et al., 2016).

EMG systems have been used previously to evaluate the effect of WBV stimuli on increasing neuromuscular activity (Di Giminiani et al., 2015), and this was evaluated in Chapter 4. Moreover, EMG signals have been used to assess the optimal WBV stimuli conditions in healthy individuals in the squatting position (Cardinale and Lim, 2003; Di Giminiani et al., 2009; Giombini et al., 2013). A comparison of multiple short exposure times (10 x 1 min) of an individualised vibration frequency at a 30 Hz fix frequency appeared to elicit a greater improvement in muscle power and jump heights in the fixed and individualised groups during static squat position (Di Giminiani et al., 2009). The individualised vibration group was evaluated by VL EMG signal during isometric half-squat then used in WBV training programme including three sessions per week for eight

weeks (Di Giminiani et al., 2009). Individual ground contact time and flight times were measured to calculate muscle power and jump heights in the squat jump in 30 Hz fixed vibration compared to individualised vibration group programme (Di Giminiani et al., 2009). Exercises with individualised frequencies increased the jump height and power by 22% and 18% respectively, compared with the same exercise protocol with a fixed frequency of 30 Hz. Di Giminiani et al. (2009) illustrated the role of individualised frequency in the exercise programme, and the inter-day reliability was evaluated for VL EMG signals, power and jump height test, and the evaluated individualised frequency on neuromuscular activity for the performed long-term programmes. Further evaluation is required regarding the following: programme duration, body position, time exposure and muscle distance from the WBV platform. In addition, the intra-day reliability of the individualised frequency, evaluated by EMG responses, requires further evaluation during double leg squat.

The effect of the individualised/optimal WBV frequency was evaluated on the acute VL EMG signal in a single session experiment (Carlucci et al., 2016) and a long-term treatment protocol (Di Giminiani et al., 2009; Giombini et al., 2013) during the static squat position in healthy individuals. A comparison of the results between the acute and long-term treatment protocol of WBV stimuli was difficult to establish due to the differences in exposure time, rest time between trials, frequency range and normalisation methods. Therefore, further research is required to achieve a possible evaluation. Both acute and long-term protocols assessed WBV stimuli on neuromuscular activity triggered by lengthening the muscle spindle (Lienhard, Vienneau, Nigg, et al., 2015). However, the mechanism of how the individualised WBV frequency elicits neuromuscular activity at frequency compared to other needs further investigation. In addition, the role of the individualised

frequency for different WBV platform devices with different types of oscillation directions on neuromuscular activity needs further evaluation.

Both frequencies of 30 Hz and 50 Hz were found to increase the VL EMG signal during a unilateral squat compared to a squat with no vibration stimuli in healthy individuals, without a significant difference between 30 Hz and 50 Hz (Borges et al., 2017). Although Borges et al. 2017 used only 30 Hz and 50 Hz and did not evaluate the individualised frequency, further research is required with a wider frequency range to investigate the possibility of finding the individualised frequencies for each individual's muscle in healthy individuals and patient population.

Implementation of an individualised WBV stimuli in research or rehabilitation programs must still be evaluated to determine the most optimal protocols to be used, including frequency ranges, exercise position and distance from the vibration platform as well as investigating the reliability of obtained individualised frequencies. Therefore, this chapter seeks:

- To evaluate the differences between WBV stimuli at the frequencies 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz on the acute VM neuromuscular response of the dominant leg during a static double leg squat across two visits conducted within one week in healthy individuals.
- To evaluate the inter-day reliability of the individualised WBV stimuli on acute VM neuromuscular activity during a static double leg squat in healthy individuals.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Participants

Twenty-six healthy participants volunteered to participate in the present study. Participants had a mean age (\pm SD) of 35.1 ± 8.3 years, height 172.4 ± 6.9 cm, weight 74.5 ± 13.5 kg and BMI 25.1 ± 4.4 kg/m². The method of recruiting was described in section 3.1. All participants read the participant information sheet (Appendix 4), signed the consent form (Appendix 5) and answered

the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) questionnaire. Ethical approval was obtained from the UWS School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee application number 1090 and submission number of 4338 (Appendix 3).

5.2.2 Protocol

The experiment was a repeated-measure study conducted over two visits. Visit 1 started with collected participant demographic data, defined the dominant leg defined and warm-up performed (see section 3.2.1). EMG electrodes were placed on VM (see section 3.3.2) and the MVC protocol conducted (see section 3.2.2). Then participants performed four trials of squats on the VibraMachine vibration platform with a frequency of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz in randomised order by random number generator. Participants rested for 2 min between trials and standardised verbal instructions were given (see section 3.3.1). Electrodes were removed prior to performing the cool down by stretching the thigh muscles. Visit 2 followed the same protocol and was performed within a minimum of 24 hours and maximum of six days of session 1.

5.2.3 Data analysis

All EMG data were analysed using EMGworks (see section 3.5.2). All data were sampled and rectified with band-pass and notch filters applied for four frequencies (30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) along with their subharmonics (see section 3.5.1). RMS signals were obtained and transferred to Excel for normalisation (see section 3.5.1). The maximum normalised amplitude of EMG was identified for each trial. Then, median and interquartile range were calculated for each frequency. The impact of WBV frequency on neuromuscular response on coefficient of variation percentage (CV%) described in section 3.5.2. The individualised frequency in each visit was identified by the highest normalised VM EMG signal for the dominant limb.

5.2.4 Statistical Analysis

All statistical analysis was performed in SPSS version 25 (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK). The distribution of the maximum normalised EMG data was tested as described in section 3.5.2. A Friedman ANOVA test was performed to evaluate and compare the effect of different frequencies on maximum normalised EMG responses in the dominant limb for visit 1 and visit 2 separately (see section 3.5.2). The effect size was also calculated in SPSS and evaluated by Kendall's in non-parametric test as described in section 3.5.2. To evaluate the reliability of the highest VM muscle activity between visits 1 and 2 regardless the frequency, a paired sample t-test was performed and the effect size (z) calculated by paired sample t-test (see section 3.5.2). The Wilcoxon signed rank test was used to compare the frequency that yielded the highest normalised VM muscle activity between visits 1 and 2. Also, the spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ) is calculated to assess the correlation between the frequency and the maximum VM muscle activity cross visits 1 and 2.

5.3 Results

All 26 participants completed the study protocol. The maximum normalised amplitude of VM EMG signals for the dominant limb in all 26 participants cross the two visits were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$) and this was supported from visual inspection of the associated data plots.

5.3.1 The impact of WBV frequency on neuromuscular response on coefficient of variation percentage (CV%)

Large CV% was observed at frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz with ranged from 44.8 to 57.8 in visit 1 and visit 2. A high CV% was also observed within participants, ranging from 2.8 to 35.6 in visit 1 and 2.1 to 32.9 in visit 2. Table 15 showed the Mean, SD and CV% values of maximum normalised amplitude of neuromuscular response for dominant VM muscle activity during the four frequencies in visit 1 and visit 2.

Table 15. Mean, SD and CV% values of maximum normalised EMG amplitude of participants dominant vastus medialis muscle (VM) muscles during WBV frequencies 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz. Calculated mean values at all previous frequencies in visit 1 and visit 2.

Frequency (Hz)	Mean \pm SD for normalised VM %		CV%	
	Visit 1	Visit2	Visit 1	Visit 2
30	67.2 \pm 37.5	62.38 \pm 28.0	55.8	44.8
35	67.01 \pm 34.6	64.05 \pm 28.8	51.7	45.0
40	66.07 \pm 38.2	62.77 \pm 29.7	57.8	47.3
50	69.45 \pm 38.9	61.62 \pm 29.5	56.0	47.9
Mean	67.44 \pm 37.3	62.71 \pm 29	55.3	46.26

No significant difference in maximum normalised amplitude of VM neuromuscular activity of the dominant limb was found between the four frequencies during a static double leg squat in healthy individuals in visit 1 (Chi-Square $\chi^2 = 0.738$, $p = 0.864$, effect size $z = 0.009$, very small), and visit 2 (Chi-Square $\chi^2 = 1.062$, $p = 0.786$, effect size $z = 0.014$, very small). Presentation for these data illustrates in Figure 5.1 and 5.2.

Figure 5.1: Presentation of maximum normalised amplitude of vastus medialis (VM) EMG neuromuscular responses of the dominant limb during WBV frequencies (30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) at a) visit 1. b) visit 2.

Figure 5.2: Median and interquartile range maximum normalised EMG amplitude of participants' dominant vastus medialis (VM) muscles upon exposure to WBV frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz at visit 1 and visit 2.

5.3.2 The individualised WBV frequencies across the two visits.

There was no consistency in the frequency that yielded the highest normalised EMG amplitude across the two visits for individual participants. Specifically, out of 26 participants, only 6 produced individualised frequencies that yielded consistent the highest normalised EMG amplitude across the two visits. There was no significant difference between the frequency that yielded highest EMG amplitude for the two visits ($z = -0.608$, $p = 0.543$, $r = 0.084$, very small) (Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3: Presentation of all participants normalised vastus medialis (VM) EMG neuromuscular responses at individualised WBV frequencies across the two visits. Note only 6 participants have the same individualised frequency at visits 1 and 2.

Consistency was defined by how the highest normalised EMG amplitude matched on both visits. The data of highest normalised VM muscle activity cross visits 1 and 2 was normally distributed ($p > 0.05$) and this was supported from visual inspection of the associated data plots. No significant difference was found between the highest normalised VM neuromuscular activity for the dominant limb of the two visits ($t = 0.640$, $p = 0.529$, $z = 0.135$, small). No significant association was found between the frequencies of individualised VM between the two visits ($\rho = 0.007$, $p = 0.972$). These results indicate that the maximum VM does not occur at the same frequency at the two visits, supporting the fact that only 6 of the 26 participants had the same individualised frequency in both visits.

5.4 Discussion

The first aim of this study was to assess whether differences existed in the effect of four different WBV platform frequencies on maximum normalised amplitude for VM during static squat positioning across the two visits. An individualised frequency was not present across visits 1 and

2 for the majority of participants as no differences were found between the four different WBV platform frequencies. Thereafter, the highest frequency that obtained by the readings of maximum normalised amplitude for VM neuromuscular responses which was produced during a static squat, were generally found to be inconsistent within the same individual across the two visits. Only six volunteers (4 female and 2 male) out of the 26 healthy volunteers exhibited consistency in the frequency. Therefore, any of the four frequencies tested could plausibly be used to induce VM muscle activity during WBV stimuli in static squat positioning.

The findings of the present study conflict with those of Cardinale and Lim (2003), who compared different frequencies on VL muscle activity. In that study, acute VL EMG activity was measured during a static double leg squat with NEMES WBV frequency of 30 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz at 100° of knee flexion. Although those authors determined a significant enhanced effect on VL muscle activity during a squat at 30 Hz and 40 Hz WBV stimuli compared to 50 Hz and with non-vibration, there is a lack of investigation the presence of the individualised frequency. Therefore, further investigation is required with different frequencies (ranged from 10 Hz to 60 Hz) and muscles to establish the possibility of having the individualised WBV frequency to elicit each muscle activity. Although Cardinale and Lim (2003) recommended that the optimal WBV frequency (stimuli) for each individual muscle should be investigated before being used in a clinical setting, their results of EMG signals were not normalised to MVC values. Furthermore, those authors did not evaluate the consistency of the EMG response as they depended upon results generated during a previous study for their evaluation and calculation of reliability values (Cardinale and Lim, 2003). In contrast, Borges et al. (2017) compared normalised VM responses during unilateral squatting on a vertical platform (Power plate) WBV platform at 30 and 50 Hz at 40° of knee flexion in healthy individuals and found no differences without evaluation the presence of individualised frequency.

This finding reinforces the fact that an individuals' response to similar vibration frequencies are varied (Cardinale and Lim, 2003; Cardinale and Wakeling, 2005) and EMG signals can be influenced by differences in normalisation process, knee flexion angle and WBV platform types. Therefore, the differences in the optimum frequency between individuals, and between muscles within the same individual, can be explained by the disparity in muscle reaction to WBV stimuli (Cardinale and Lim, 2003; Di Giminiani et al., 2009). In addition, even with standardised verbal instructions, participants may not be consistent in their squat positioning or joint angle, or may perhaps shift their weight during vibration on the WBV platform. Therefore, further research is required to explain the possible effect of normalisation process, knee flexion angle and body posture on the optimum WBV stimuli in healthy individuals.

The optimal WBV frequency when investigating the lower-limb neuromuscular responses during squatting position varied between studies (Giombini et al., 2013; Ritzmann et al., 2013; Borges et al., 2017; Lienhard et al., 2017). The inconsistency in these studies results regarding assessing the optimal WBV frequency on muscle responses was largely in agreement with the present findings that EMG muscle responses were independent of different WBV frequencies within the same trial. Giombini et al. (2013) evaluated the individualised WBV stimulation ranged from 20 Hz to 50 Hz for VL neuromuscular muscle activity during static double leg squat during visit 1 in nine females with mean age of 71 years. From visit 3 to 5, the evaluated individualised frequency was employed in a randomised treatment protocol included frequency of 20 Hz or 50 Hz to evaluate the muscle power output during a double leg press by dynamometer in these older females. The individualised frequency increased muscle power by 32% after 5 min of exposure to WBV compared to 20 Hz and 50 Hz with 16.1% and 16.3% respectively (Giombini et al., 2013). However, the reliability of the individualised EMG readings between days was not reported. Lienhard et al. (2014) established

that frequencies between 25 Hz and 40 Hz were the optimal range for maximal VL and VM EMG responses during a static squat. The evaluated frequencies in the current study were similar to those tested previously on neuromuscular muscle response (Lienhard et al., 2014; Giombini et al., 2013), therefore WBV frequency ranging from 25 Hz to 50 Hz appeared to elicit VM muscle neuromuscular activity during double leg squat compared to squat with no vibration stimuli. Conflicting results were found by Ritzmann and colleagues (2013) who investigated the effect of WBV frequency ranging from 5 Hz to 30 Hz on VM EMG neuromuscular response during static squat compared to squat with no WBV stimuli. In that study, the EMG activity increased as the WBV frequency increased (Ritzmann, Gollhofer and Kramer, 2013). This conflict can be justified by the differences in tested muscle characteristics. Despite the inconsistency in the effect of WBV frequency between studies, WBV frequency ranging from 12 Hz to 50 Hz are recommended for use in strengthening of knee extensor muscles (Osawa, Oguma and Ishii, 2013). The consistency of EMG readings across days and sessions for individualised WBV values clearly merits further investigation.

WBV platform characteristics may contribute to the evaluation of individualised frequency on neuromuscular response via the wave direction of WBV platform or WBV parameters (acceleration, frequency and displacement). However, peak-to-peak displacement is suggested to influence vibration platform performance as demonstrated in Chapter 4. The Power plate platform, which provides oscillation in a majority vertical direction but also in a horizontal (tri-planar) direction (Cardinale and Lim, 2003) was found to increase VL muscle activity with an amplitude of 4 mm and frequencies of 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 45 Hz (Hazell, Jakobi and Kenno, 2007). In contrast to this finding, Borges et al. (2017) evaluated VL neuromuscular activity on a WBV platform with peak-to-peak displacement of 4 mm and frequencies of 30 and 50 Hz, determining no differences

in the effect of frequencies on VL EMG signals. Although this result on EMG response conflict with Hazell, Jakobi and Kenno, (2007), the match between platform parameters in Borges et al. (2017) with the present study may explain the similarity in EMG findings across tested frequencies. However, this conflict in terms of the effect of WBV parameters, platform performance and outputs on EMG response, indicates the need for further research to quantify any relationship between WBV platform parameters and EMG signals, which can influence the evaluation of the individualised frequency.

The individualised WBV stimuli are suggested to influence muscle reactive strength significantly evaluated by power during the drop jump test (Di Giminiani et al., 2010). This finding was based on only one same-day measure of individualised frequency for VL muscle, while MVIC data that used during normalisation process, were obtained through isometric half-squatting with no vibration, and only a band-pass filter was applied. Therefore, the results can be influenced by vibration platform noise which may have contaminated muscle signals (Borges et al., 2017; Di Giminiani et al., 2010). Further research with a robust study protocol is required to enhance scientific research and the implications of individualised WBV in clinical practice.

Quadriceps muscle activity has been described to be impacted by foot position (Di Giminiani et al., 2013). The VL and gastrocnemius neuromuscular responses were monitored in four knee and ankle positions during static squat positioning on a WBV platform, with the resulting EMG signals suggesting that the muscles respond differently across joint positions and frequencies (Di Giminiani et al., 2013). These results conflict with the present study regarding how WBV frequencies have different effects on muscle responses at the same knee joint angle, however the present study conducted on VM muscle not VL. The present study involved full feet contact (without a specific ankle angle) on the WBV platform during static squat positioning, with 60–65°

of knee flexion and verbal instruction to shift the weight-bearing forwards to the toes more than the heel. The adoption of a position with raised heels (forefoot stance) is suggested to reduce the transmission of vibrations to the upper body and decrease muscle response to the vibration stimuli compared with a normal stance (Ritzmann, Gollhofer and Kramer, 2013). Therefore, feet contact on the floor was maintained to maximise activation and stimulation of VM muscle.

As discussed in Chapter 3, knee angle is critical in increasing the number of activated motor units. Caldwell, Jamison and Lee (1993) suggested that joint position and angle may specify preferential motor unit recruitment. In the literature, there appears to be some debate about the optimal knee angle required to activate the VM muscle. While there is a general agreement on an optimal knee-angle range between 60° and 90°, Jaberzadeh and colleagues (2016) suggested a knee angle between 50° and 80° induced optimal VM activation. Moreover, Lienhard et al. (2015) postulated that VM muscle activity during squatting with 60° of knee flexion was greater than that seen at 20°. Regarding the relation between the individualised WBV stimuli and knee angle, Giombini and colleagues (2013) compared the VL muscle response with knee flexion of 70° in an older female group during exposure to optimal individualised WBV stimuli to fixed WBV stimuli. They recommended that the optimal WBV frequency determined on VL neuromuscular activity during static squat evaluated by exposing the participants to the optimal frequency in visits 3 to 5, was more beneficial at improving participant maximal power output than three visits with exposure to a fixed frequency of 20 Hz or 50 Hz (Giombini et al., 2013). Marchetti et al. (2016) compared VM muscle activity at three different knee-flexion angles (20°, 90° and 140°) and found the greatest VM muscle activity at 90° of knee flexion. All these studies investigated VM response at different knee angles in healthy individuals, therefore the optimal knee flexion angle to elicit the VM muscle activity appears ranged between 60° and 90°. In this present study, a knee angle was selected which

would also be suitable for individuals with PFPS. According to Chen et al. (2018), the greatest VM muscle response can be obtained through a CKC exercise of knee extension at 60° knee flexion in individuals with PFPS. Therefore, squatting with knee flexion angles of between 60° and 65° were considered to be used in individuals with PFPS without causing pain or discomfort (Miao et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2018).

The majority of the WBV studies reported upon the reliability of neuromuscular response on WBV platforms (Marín and Hazell, 2014; García-Gutiérrez, Hazell and Marín, 2016). However, these studies were often lacking details on study procedures and protocols, participant demographics / anthropometrics or information pertaining to data analysis. For example, Marin and Hazell (2014) evaluated the reliability of VM and VL EMG neuromuscular activity with ICCs 0.93 and 0.94 respectively with no details regards the position used for obtaining the reliability and defined if the evaluated reliability was inter-day or intra-day reliability. Therefore, these details may affect the reliability of study findings. Giminiani et al. (2015) investigated the reliability of VM neuromuscular response and WBV stimuli outputs, finding very high consistency in VM signals and platform accelerations between days with ICCs 0.92 and 0.93 respectively, and within-session ICCs 0.97 and 0.97 respectively. However, the study was limited in that it did not investigate the optimal frequency of WBV stimuli as evaluated by neuromuscular output. Therefore, studies conducted on the evaluation of the reliability of individualised frequency by neuromuscular activity are lacking important details about study protocol.

The WBV platform, as described in Chapter 3, includes specific timing options for exposure to WBV stimuli (30 s or 60 s), as explored in Chapter 4. The reported exposure time differs across the literature: ranging from 20 s and 60 s exposure with rest time ranging between 2 min and 4 min between trials (Adams et al., 2009; Di Giminiani et al., 2009). The optimal exposure time for

acute WBV stimulus investigated during counter-movement jumps (CMJ) was found to be 30 s (Adams et al., 2009), however EMG response was not evaluated which is the main outcome measure in this thesis. In the present study, the exposure time was 30 s and the first and last 10 s excluded to give the platform time to reach the acceleration desired. Examples are available for studies analysed all the WBV exposure time and others analysed only a specific time of WBV exposure, however other studies did not detail the process of analysing the exposure time (Perchthaler, Horstmann and Grau, 2013; Lienhard, Vienneau, Friesenbichler, et al., 2015; Lee, 2017). This resulted in discrepancies between findings. Overall, the literature is deficient in terms of investigating the effect of different exposure times to WBV stimuli on muscle response. Therefore, further research is required to evaluate the effect of different timings for WBV stimuli exposure to neuromuscular activity in healthy and patient populations, and that is not the focus of this thesis.

Aside from the optimisation of exposure time, the data handling process is also variable throughout the literature. As described in section 3.5.1, the filtering process was completed after data collection and this is a necessary step, but the data filtering processes can have a significant impact on resultant EMG values. Most studies conducted on EMG signals have applied a band-pass filter to exclude environmental noise (Tang et al., 2001; Perchthaler, Horstmann and Grau, 2013; Lienhard et al., 2015; Carlucci et al., 2016). However, the potential for noise to influence EMG signals is increased when using WBV stimuli and is dependent upon the vibration frequency. Therefore, a notch filter was utilised in the present study to account for the noise combined with EMG signals that were produced from the WBV stimuli (frequency). Borges et al. (2017) investigated the effect of WBV stimuli at frequencies of 30 and 50 Hz on the neuromuscular system and compared filtered EMG signals (band-pass and notch filters) to unfiltered data. They

concluded that EMG signals were overestimated using the unfiltered data; although there was a slight loss of EMG signal with filtering, all noise was eliminated and resulted in the generation of clear EMG signals (Borges et al., 2017). Di Giminiani et al. (2009) did not apply any notch filter while conducting EMG data analysis on knee extensor muscles. Therefore, this limitation is can be controlled by the accuracy of the available EMG systems to researchers. The role of filters is discussed in Chapter 4 by illustrating EMG reliability after the band-pass filter step and notch filter application (Borges et al., 2017). Thus, filters may reduce the motion artefacts produced by the WBV platform on EMG signals.

The normalisation process used while assessing EMG signals is intended to standardise the results between literature and improve reproducibility. The process of normalisation plays an important role in EMG signal determination. The MVICs used in the normalisation process can be obtained using a stationary dynamometer, handheld dynamometer and manual muscle testing, with high reliability and validity reported across the three methods for the measurement of EMG responses in quadriceps muscles during 45° knee flexion (Lee et al., 2012). However, Di Giminiani et al. (2015) normalised VM and VL neuromuscular EMG signals during static double leg squat on WBV stimuli to a static double leg squat with 0 Hz as the reference signal. Also, Marín and Hazell (2014) normalised EMG signals with WBV stimuli to 20 s of MVIC during static squatting without WBV platform while Perchthaler, Horstmann and Grau (2013) used 5 s of EMG signal recorded prior to each trial for normalisation purposes. Avelar and colleagues (2013) investigated EMG signals without applying any normalisation method. In that study, a repeated-measure study protocol during the same visit and on the muscle suggested each participant counted a control for themselves, hence the normalisation process becomes unneeded (Avelar et al., 2013). Moreover, EMG signals can be normalised to those MVICs obtained during squatting (closed kinetic chain

exercises) or sitting positions (open kinetic chain exercises) (Lienhard, Vienneau and Friesenbichler, 2015). Therefore, the MVIC time used in normalisation the EMG signals found inconsistency. In the present study, EMG data were normalised to MVIC obtained during the seated resisted knee extension test as described in section 3.2.2. Based on the limitations regarding the normalisation process and timing as discussed above and, in the literature, further work is required to evaluate, compare and optimise normalisation methods during WBV stimuli.

5.5 Conclusion

The present study appears to be the first to report the investigation of individualised frequency WBV on acute neuromuscular response in VM muscles in the dominant limb. This study evaluated individualised responses across two separate visits. The data suggested that there is no specific or optimal frequency that can be applied generally within healthy population to elicit the highest VM neuromuscular response during a static double leg squat on a WBV platform, nor is there a frequency specific to an individual. Therefore, all the evaluated frequency may be used with same effectiveness in clinical setting. A frequency of 30 Hz was previously described to be the optimal individualised frequency for VL EMG response (Cardinale and Lim, 2003). However, there is inconsistency in individualised WBV frequency findings owing to various factors that include study protocol (position, normalisation method, population and type of filters used), muscle evaluation and investigation of the reliability of the individualised frequency. Thus, a robust protocol is needed to describe and evaluate the existence and effectiveness of individualised WBV stimuli protocols in acute and chronic treatment programs compared with a fixed frequency or other rehabilitation tools in a clinical setting. Moreover, further research in healthy individuals and patient populations is necessary to reinforce the implication of WBV stimuli being counted as effective interventions in a clinical setting. Although the individualised EMG response may not be

presence and participants may vary in EMG response during WBV, it would be wise not to select a pre-determined frequency to all participants. Therefore, the presence of individualised frequency cross the two visits from the present study was used in evaluating the effect of exercise with WBV stimuli in healthy individuals in Chapter 6. If the individualised frequency for highest recorded neuromuscular activity of VM was not present cross the two visits, then the frequency with the highest value across the two visits was selected.

Chapter 6

Evaluation and comparison of WBV and resisted hip adduction exercises on VM and VL neuromuscular activity during static squatting in healthy individuals

6.1 Introduction

Weakness or dysfunction of the quadriceps muscle which is a factor can be found in various neuromuscular pathological conditions, either as a specific muscle a part of quadriceps or as a whole quadriceps muscle group (Kary, 2010; Nar, 2013). Weakness of the VM muscle can be related to patella mal-tracking, which is an underlying problem commonly found in individuals with PFPS (Coqueiro et al., 2005). Uncertainties remain regarding the optimal strengthening exercises that target the VM muscle, for example no consensus has been reached on which exercise may be optimal to correct patella mal-tracking by addressing the balance between VM and VL muscle activities, and the effectiveness of these exercises in short and long term programmes are not yet known (Bolgla, Shaffer and Malone, 2008). The squatting exercise is traditionally used to strengthen lower limb muscles in healthy individuals (Gullett et al., 2009) and patients with PFPS (Dixit et al., 2007) and is effective across various hip, knee and ankle angles (Marchetti et al., 2016; Slater, Abillitylab and Hart, 2017). Squatting alone may be sufficient to strengthen a particular lower limb muscle; however, additional levels of complexity can be added to the squat exercise through external loaded weights and altered hip positioning either in open kinetic chain exercises (OKC) or closed kinetic chain exercises (CKC) (Jang et al., 2013; Tang et al., 2001; Irish et al., 2010; Lee et al., 2016). Weight-bearing exercises (CKC) play a role in the strengthening of multiple joint-stabilising muscles and proprioceptive reaction and co-contraction (Tang et al., 2001).

It has been suggested that hip adduction can contribute to the strengthening of VM muscles, as there are fibres of the VM that originate from the distal part of the adductor magnus (Jang et al., 2013). In the literature, the adductor magnus is considered a stable origin from which the VM muscle can contract during hip adduction (Hanten and Schulthies, 1990). Subsequently, the literature began to evaluate the link between VM muscle activation and hip adduction exercises in supine and squatting positions (Miao et al., 2015; Adel et al., 2019; Coqueiro et al., 2005; Irish et al., 2010). As of yet, no clear link has been identified regarding the degree of hip adduction or the equipment used to perform resisted hip adduction for the purpose of evaluating the VM muscle activity in healthy individuals and patient populations (Earl, Schmitz and Arnold, 2001; Balogun, Broderick, K., Dolan-Aiello, 2010). Jang and colleagues (2013) investigated VM and VL muscles activation in conventional squat, maximal, 40% and 80% of the maximal hip adduction loads percentage during a static squat exercise in healthy participants. In that study, the conventional squat obtained by squatting with 45° knee flexion for 6 s, and the hip adduction was achieved by compressing an air cushion between the knees for 6 s to reach the maximum hip load. Then, the 40% and 80% hip adduction loads were obtained by EMG biofeedback. The researchers found that higher VM muscle activation was achieved at 40% and 80% hip adduction loads compared to the conventional or maximal adduction squats, while no difference found between four exercises on VL muscle activity (Jang et al., 2013). Therefore, the 40% and 80% hip adduction loads can be used to strength VM muscle in individuals with PFPS who may develop the imbalance in VM and VL muscles ratio (1:2) (VL muscle activate before VM muscle) which normally is found to be 1:1 in healthy individuals (VL muscle activate with VM muscle) (see section 1.4.1.2). However, Adel et al. (2019) found that hip adduction during squatting did not appear to correct the VM to VL ratio in individuals with patellofemoral pain syndrome compared to individual with PFPS

performed traditional exercises. The degree of hip adduction that can be used to activate and strengthen the VM muscle is still a matter of debate among scholars (Hertel et al., 2004; Boling, Padua and Blackburn, 2006; Irish et al., 2010; Miao et al., 2015). Therefore, further research is essential to evaluate the effect of hip adduction on the VM neuromuscular signal during squatting in healthy individuals.

The evaluation of acute and chronic WBV stimuli has been conducted over the last 50 years in various neuromuscular conditions (Brogårdh, Flansbjer and Lexell, 2012; Abbasi et al., 2017; Huang and Pang, 2019). In particular, acute WBV stimuli has been shown to have a positive effect on strengthening the VM muscle during a static squat in healthy individuals (Krol et al., 2011, Marín and Hazell, 2014). Marín and Hazell, (2014) evaluated the VM neuromuscular activity during the static squat exercise on an unstable surface placed above the WBV platform with frequencies 30 Hz and 50 Hz. However, the results of the exercises were not compared to squatting with 30 Hz and 50 Hz vibration in the absence of the unstable surface. The evidence-base which evaluated the effect of acute WBV stimuli on VM neuromuscular activity during a static squat was discussed in Chapter 2. In that Chapter, the VM neuromuscular activity increased during static squat exercises with acute exposure to WBV stimuli. However, the MVICs for the VM and VL neuromuscular activity did not significantly increase in healthy individuals after 10 weeks including various static squat positions on WBV platform with frequency ranged from 20 Hz to 40 Hz, compared to control group who did not perform any exercise (Machado et al., 2010). Also, Osawa and Oguma, (2011) evaluated the effect of WBV stimuli during exercises programme including squat and trunk exercises on VM activity by isokinetic knee extension machine in healthy individuals, compared to a control group which performed the same exercise programme but with no WBV stimuli. In that study, no significant increase was found in VM neuromuscular

activity in individuals who performed exercises with WBV stimuli compared to the control group (Osawa and Oguma, 2011). These results suggest that acute and WBV stimuli training may lack consistency in effect of WBV stimuli on the treatment of VM weakness or the decreased muscle activation in healthy individuals, therefore further evaluation is required to fully evaluate the effectiveness of acute WBV stimuli and WBV training with details of WBV platform types as well as the knee flexion angle, exposure time and squat position. These evaluations should be performed in healthy individuals prior to implementation in the PFPS patient population to avoid any risk that may adversely influence treatment efficacy. The individualised response to WBV stimuli discussed in the literature has led to the theory of evaluating and implementing the optimal frequency independently for individuals' muscle (Di Giminiani et al., 2010; Giombini et al., 2013). The findings presented in Chapter 5 showed that there was no evidence for the presence of an individualised frequency, however the highest normalised VM EMG output across two visits for individual participant was consistent in value between the two visits.

The effectiveness of hip adduction exercises and WBV stimuli on VM neuromuscular activity have each been evaluated separately and have shown to increase VM muscle activity. The acute effect of combination exercises (resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli during squatting) on acute VM neuromuscular activity during static double leg squat position is not yet known. Thus, this research is conducted with the ultimate goal to evaluate combined exercises to improve patient health and develop exercises that strengthen healthy individuals' neuromuscular function. Combining interventions which are already recommended in PFPS treatment (Crossley et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2018), is the overarching rationale of this study. In the clinical setting, combined intervention techniques, including the incorporation of equipment, is often used for strengthening exercises in healthy individuals and the patient population despite enough evidence to endorse such approaches

(Hertel et al., 2004; Argut et al., 2017). In preparation, the validity and reliability of the WBV platform outputs and Thera-Band force used as part of this study were confirmed following their evaluation in Chapter 4. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of single exercises (squat alone, WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction separately) in comparison to combined exercises (WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction together) in static squatting on VM and VL neuromuscular activation in healthy individuals.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Participants

A total of twenty-six healthy participants volunteered to participate in the study. Participants had a mean age \pm SD of 35.1 ± 8.3 years, weight, 74.5 ± 13.5 kg, height, 172.4 ± 6.9 cm and BMI, 25.1 ± 4.4 kg/m². Participant recruitment was described in section 3.1. Healthy participants that showed no history of musculoskeletal injury, neurological, or pain in the lower extremities were recruited. All participants read the participant information sheet (Appendix 4), signed the consent form (Appendix 5) and answered the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) questionnaire. Ethical approval was obtained from the UWS School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee application number 1090 (Appendix 3). This experiment was conducted on the same participants from Chapter 4 and 5. The dominant leg was identified in visit 1 as the leg used to kick a ball (Beling et al., 1998).

6.2.2 Protocol

Visit 3 began with a warm-up (see section 3.2.1). Subsequently, the EMG sensors were placed on the VM and VL muscles (see section 3.3.2), and the MVIC was obtained (see section 3.2.2). All 26 participants performed four exercises: 1) static double leg squat; 2) static double leg squat with resisted unilateral hip adduction; 3) static double leg squat with WBV stimuli using the

participants' individualised frequency; 4) static double leg squat with WBV stimuli using the participants' individualised frequency and unilateral resisted hip adduction (see section 3.4: Figure 6.1). The individualised frequency was identified by evaluating the highest recorded normalised VM activity in the dominant leg during squatting with four WBV frequencies (30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) in Chapter 5. If the frequency for highest recorded neuromuscular activity of VM was not consistent across visits 1 and 2, then the frequency with the highest value across the two visits was selected. The resisted hip adduction exercise was performed unilaterally in the dominant and non-dominant leg. This experiment was conducted within 1 week of data collected in Chapter 5. Each participant performed only one trial of each exercise with a total of six exercises. Only one trial for each exercise was obtained to avoid muscle fatigue. A random number generator was used to randomise the order of the exercises and legs. A two-minute rest was allowed between trials to avoid muscle fatigue. All exercises were performed with a standardised instruction (see section 3.3.1) regardless of whether individuals performed exercises with WBV stimuli or the Thera-Band. The mid-section of a 60 cm piece of green Thera-Band was covered by a sponge pad to avoid skin discomfort as the Thera-Band was placed around the knee joint, and the two ends attached together to a plinth (see Figure 6.1.c, see section 3.4.1). The force exerted from the Thera-Band was validated by MicroFET2 handheld dynamometer as described in Chapter 4. The Thera-Band elongation distance previously used in the literature was 200% (Miao et al., 2015). At the end of visit 3, a cool down was performed as described in section 4.5.2.2.

Figure 6.1: Squat exercise with- a) vibration platform, b) vibration platform and resisted hip adduction using a Thera-Band c) vibration platform and resisted hip adduction using a Thera-Band.

6.2.3 Data analysis

All EMG data gathered from the VM and VL muscles in the dominant and non-dominant legs were analysed using EMGworks software (see section 3.5.1 and 3.5.2). A band-pass filter was applied for all EMG data while a band-stop filter (notch filter) was applied according to the individualised frequency and harmonics (see section 3.5.1). The mean of RMS obtained of each exercise trial (middle 10 s) then exported to Excel software, and EMG data were normalised to the highest MVIC value collected at the beginning of the experiment (see section 3.5.1). The mean

was calculated for the maximum normalised EMG amplitude of the middle 10 s. VM/VL ratios were calculated by the normalised VM and VL muscle activity for dominant and non-dominant legs during each exercise according to the following equation:

$$\text{VM/VL ratio} = \frac{\text{Normalised VM muscle activity during each exercise}}{\text{Normalised VL muscle activity during each exercise.}}$$

6.2.4 Statistical Analysis

Data were imported into SPSS version 25 (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK). Data normality for four exercises as described in section 3.5.2. The median and interquartile range were calculated for each exercise. A Friedman ANOVA test was performed to compare effect of the 4 exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of VM, VL neuromuscular activity and VM/VL ratio between dominant and non-dominant legs (exercises type and limb as factors). A post-hoc Wilcoxon two related sample test was used to investigate significant differences between exercises if a main effect was found. The effect size was also calculated in SPSS by Kendall's test in non-parametric test as described in section 3.5.2. The VM/VL ratios for the dominant and the non-dominant limbs were evaluated and compared to value 1 by a one sample Wilcoxon test. Also, the maximum normalised EMG amplitude of VM and VL muscle activities and VM/VL ratios of the dominant limb were compared to non-dominant for each of the four exercises by Wilcoxon two related sample test.

6.3 Results

All 26 participants completed the full experimental procedure and after visual inspection of EMG data, all trials from all participants were included. Data were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$), and this was supported from visual inspection of the associated data plots.

6.3.1 The VM, VL neuromuscular activities and VM/VL ratio for dominant and non-dominant limbs in individuals with PFPS

No significant difference in maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity was found between the four exercises during static squat positioning in the dominant limb, however a significant difference in maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity was found between the four exercises during static squat positioning in the non-dominant limb (6.2.).

Figure 6.2: Median and interquartile range of maximum normalised EMG amplitude of the dominant and the non-dominant vastus medialis (VM) muscle during four static squat exercises. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration. * = significant $p < 0.05$.

Table 16. illustrates the Chi-square, p value and effect size (z) for the differences four exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of VM for dominant and non-dominant limbs.

Table 16. The difference between four exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of vastus medialis (VM) muscle for dominant and non-dominant limbs. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration, IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = p value, effect size = (z), * = significant $p < 0.05$.

Difference between four exercises in normalised VM muscle activity								
Limb	Dominant limb				Non-dominant limb			
Exercise	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B
Median measurement % (IQR)	54.62 (30.1)	47.08 (25.56)	53.54 (28.25)	51.78 (34.99)	54.38 (31.75)	46.20 (27.35) *	60.77 (41.49) *	55.63 (44.89)
Chi-Square	1.708				9.923			
P value	0.635				0.019			
z	0.022 (very small)				0.127 (small)			

* Static double leg squat with WBV stimuli was significantly higher than static double leg squat with resisted hip adduction ($P < 0.05$).

The maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity in static double leg squat with WBV stimuli was significantly higher than static double leg squat with resisted hip adduction in the non-dominant limb ($z = -2.324$, $p = 0.020$, $r = 0.322$, moderate). In the non-dominant limb, no significant difference in maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity was found between static double leg squat alone and squat with resisted hip adduction ($z = -1.562$, $p = 0.118$, $r = 0.216$, small), between static double leg squat alone and static double leg squat with WBV stimuli ($z = -0.749$, $p = 0.454$, $r = 0.103$, small), in static double leg squat alone and static double leg squat with WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction ($z = -0.622$, $p = 0.534$, $r = 0.086$, very small), between static double leg squat with resisted hip adduction and static double leg squat with WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction ($z = -1.791$, $p = 0.073$, $r = 0.164$, small) and between static double leg squat with WBV stimuli and static double leg squat with WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction ($z = -0.978$, $p = 0.328$, $r = 0.136$, small). No significant difference in maximum normalised amplitude of VL muscle activity was found between the four exercises during static squat positioning in the dominant and non-dominant limbs (6.3).

Figure 6.3: Median and interquartile range of maximum normalised amplitude of the dominant and the non-dominant vastus lateralis (VL) muscle during four static squat exercises. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration.

Table 17. illustrates the Chi-square, p value and effect size (z) for the differences four exercises on normalised VL and for dominant and non-dominant limbs.

Table 17. The difference between four exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of vastus lateralis (VL) muscle for dominant and non-dominant limbs. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration, IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = p value, effect size (z).

Difference between four exercises in normalised VL muscle activity								
Limb	Dominant limb				Non-dominant limb			
Exercise	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B
Median measurement (%) (IQR)	48.80 (33.14)	52.67 (26.59)	46.92 (29.19)	52.57 (36.29)	55.30 (25.94)	49.77 (21.24)	53.43 (28.61)	51.09 (25.74)
Chi-Square	3.738				4.477			
P value	0.291				0.214			
z	0.048 (very small)				0.057 (very small)			

No significant difference in VM/VL ratio was found between the four exercises during static squat positioning in the dominant limb. However, VM/VL ratio in the non-dominant limb was significantly different between the four exercises during static squat positioning (Figure 6.4).

Figure 6.4: Median and interquartile range of VM/VL ratio for the dominant and non-dominant limb during four static squat exercises. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration, * = significant $p < 0.05$.

Table 18 illustrates the Chi-square, p value and effect size (η^2) for the differences four exercises on VM/VL ratio for dominant and non-dominant limbs.

Table 18. The difference between four exercises on VM/VL ratio for dominant and non-dominant limbs. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration, IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = p value, effect size (z), * = significant $p < 0.05$.

Difference between four exercises in normalised VM/VL ratio								
Limb	Dominant limb				Non-dominant limb			
Exercise	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B
Median measurement (%) (IQR)	0.98 (0.32)	0.92 (0.28)	0.95 (0.39)	0.95 (0.32)	0.98 (0.34) *	0.90 (0.40) * + **	1.01 (0.51) **	0.96 (0.35)
Chi-Square	5.911				7.984			
P value	0.116				0.049			
z	0.082 (small)				0.102 (small)			

*static double leg squat was significantly higher than static double leg squat with resisted unilateral hip adduction ($P < 0.05$).

** static double leg squat with WBV stimuli was significantly higher than static double leg squat with resisted unilateral hip adduction ($P < 0.05$).

The VM/VL ratio in the non-dominant limb in static double leg squat was significantly higher than static double leg squat with resisted unilateral hip adduction ($z = -2.258$, $p = 0.024$, $r = 0.313$, moderate), and in static double leg squat with WBV stimuli was significantly higher than static double leg squat with resisted unilateral hip adduction ($z = -2.045$, $p = 0.041$, $r = 0.284$, moderate). Also, in the non-dominant limb, no significant difference in VM/VL ratio in the non-dominant limb in was found between static double leg squat alone and static double leg squat with WBV stimuli ($z = -0.686$, $p = 0.493$, $r = 0.095$, very small), between static double leg squat alone and static double leg squat with WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction ($z = -0.330$, $p = 0.741$, $r = 0.045$, very small), between static double leg squat with resisted hip adduction and static double leg squat with WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction ($z = -1.958$, $p = 0.050$, $r = 0.272$, moderate) and between static double leg squat with WBV stimuli and static double leg squat with WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction ($z = -0.286$, $p = 0.775$, $r = 0.040$, very small).

6.3.2 The VM/VL ratio for dominant and non-dominant limbs compared to the theoretical value in individuals with PFPS

The VM/VL ratios were not significantly differ from theoretical values which is equal to 1, for the dominant and the non-dominant limbs (Table 19).

Table 19. The VM/VL ratios for the dominant and the non-dominant limbs for each of the four exercises compared to 1. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration, IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = *p* value.

VM/VL ratio						
Exercise	Dominant limb			Non-dominant limb		
	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	<i>p</i> value	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	<i>p</i> value
Squat	1	0.98 (0.32)	0.587	1	0.98 (0.34)	0.869
Squat with T.B	1	0.92 (0.28)	0.886	1	0.90 (0.40)	0.559
Squat with WBV stimuli	1	0.95 (0.39)	0.493	1	1.01(0.51)	0.501
Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B	1	0.95(0.32)	0.893	1	0.96 (0.35)	0.501

The maximum normalised amplitude of VM, VL muscle activities and VM/VL ratios of the dominant limb were compared to the non-dominant limb for each of the four exercises and the results showed no significant difference between the dominant and non-dominant limbs as presented in Table 20.

Table 20. The differences in maximum normalised amplitude of vastus medialis (VM) and vastus lateralis (VL) muscles and VM/VL ratios of the dominant compared to the non-dominant limbs for each of the four exercises. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration, Alpha value = p value.

Differences in VM, VL and VM/VL ratios												
Exercises	Squat			Squat with T.B			Squat with WBV stimuli			Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B		
	VM %	VL %	VM/VL ratio	VM %	VL %	VM/VL ratio	VM %	VL %	VM/VL ratio	VM %	VL %	VM/VL ratio
Dominant limb	54.62	48.80	0.98	47.08	52.67	0.92	53.54	46.92	0.95	51.78	52.57	0.94
Non-dominant	54.38	55.30	0.98	46.20	49.77	0.90	60.77	53.43	1.01	55.63	51.09	0.95
Median difference	0.24	6.5	0	0.88	2.9	0.02	7.23	6.51	0.06	3.86	1.49	0.01
p value	0.629	0.603	0.886	0.809	0.869	0.440	0.517	0.454	0.853	0.620	0.292	0.391

6.4 Discussion

This chapter aimed to investigate the effect of four different knee exercises on VM and VL neuromuscular activity during static squatting in healthy individuals. The maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity of the non-dominant limb was significantly greater during squat with WBV compared to squat with Thera-Band. Also, the squat alone can be used to increase VM/VL ratio of the non-dominant limb compared to squat with Thera-Band, and in squat with WBV compared to squat with Thera-Band. However, the four exercises can be used with no difference on median maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL neuromuscular activities of the dominant limb, median normalised VM/VL ratio of the dominant limb and median normalised VL neuromuscular activity of the non-dominant limbs. Also, the four exercises are consistent with the proposed normal ratio of 1 between maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL muscle activity in healthy individuals. This VM/VL ratio determined in the healthy population as part of this study is entirely in keeping with the expected value. Moreover, the four exercises had the same

effect on the median normalised VM, VL and VM/VL ratio in the dominant limb compared to the non-dominant limb.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of strengthening exercises in healthy individuals does not necessarily reflect the exercise effectiveness across a patient population. Moreover, pathological conditions may impact upon this effectiveness. These strengthening exercises can be performed via equipment commonly used like Thera-band and unstable surfaces as illustrated in Chapter 2. Thera-Band is widely used in patient rehabilitation programmes. For example, Sundstrup et al. (2014) evaluated EMG muscle activity for the VM, VL and gluteus muscles in patients with lower back pain compared to a control group of healthy individuals during eccentric and concentric of different dynamic lunges. The findings revealed that greater VM and VL muscle activity was achieved in lunges with dumbbells and leg press than lunges with Thera-Band. The eccentric phase elicits high VM neuromuscular activity in lunges with dumbbells compared to lunges with Thera-Band. However, during the concentric phase the unilateral leg press which was performed by loading device ranged from 10 kg to 200 kg, exerted a greater influence upon the VM muscle compared to the Thera-Band and lunges with dumbbells (Sundstrup et al., 2014). In the present study which was conducted on healthy individuals, no statistically significant difference between four squatting exercises involve WBV stimuli and Thera-Band on VM and VL neuromuscular activity was observed while normalised to the VM and VL muscle activity during the eccentric phase. Also, Sundstrup and colleagues (2014) reported a higher VM EMG signal in the healthy individuals compared to the group of participants with low back pain while normalised muscle activity was performed to MVC during knee flexion and extension position. However, no difference was found in VL EMG signals in healthy individuals compared to individuals with low back pain. Therefore, these results may indicate that strengthening exercises with weights

(dumbbells) would be preferable to the Thera-Band for strengthening of VM and VL muscles, although healthy individuals often do not suffer from VM muscle weakness. Thus, investigating the effectiveness of other strengthening exercises further in healthy individuals may identify a significant increase in EMG muscle signals. Lee et al. (2016) compared squatting with Thera-Band to squat alone and squat on inclined surface on VM muscle signals in healthy individuals. The EMG signal for the VM muscle appeared to be lower in squatting with the Thera-Band compared to squatting alone or with weights (Lee et al., 2016). The Thera-Band in the work of Lee and colleagues (2016) was applied to the unilateral limb at a 45° knee flexion angle for all included participants, with no report of the applied resistance force or justification for the selection of the unilateral limb or the 45° angle used. Also, this consistent use of unilateral limb without explaining whether it is the dominant or non-dominant limb that is measured which can affect the EMG signals. In the present study, the dominant and non-dominant limbs were identified and all exercises were applied for both limbs. The findings suggest that a squat alone can be used to increase normalised VM muscle activity of the non-dominant limb compared to a squat with Thera-Band. Also, the squat exercise alone and the squat with WBV can be used to increase VM/VL ratio of the non-dominant limb compared to squat with Thera-Band. However, the four exercises had the same effect on EMG signals in dominant limb compared to the non-dominant limb. Following this investigation of the effectiveness of Thera-Band during static squatting in strengthening the VM muscle in healthy populations (Lee et al., 2016), the Thera-Band condition appeared not to be significantly different compared to the alternative strengthening tools in healthy individuals as illustrated previously. Thus, the squat exercise illustrated the greatest effect of on EMG signals with or without Thera-Band. Therefore, the squat exercise performed with Thera-Band can be alternatively replaced with a squatting exercise alone in healthy individuals who did

not prefer use Thera-Band during squat exercise as squat exercise alone significantly increase VM EMG activity (Lee et al., 2016). Further research with standardised outcome measures and methods is required to evaluate VM neuromuscular activity in the healthy population and to investigate long-term exercise protocols which incorporate the use of Thera-Band in comparison with different tools. Moreover, the effectiveness of Thera-Band on acute VM muscle activity in different patient populations needs further investigation to be compared to healthy individuals. A small effect size of the four exercises including Thera-band or/and WBV stimuli were found in the present study, however further research is needed to justify the required effort and time in implementing these exercises in clinical practice in rehabilitation programmes by practitioners.

The Thera-Band used in the present study during the static squat was recommended by Miao et al. (2015). Earl and colleagues (2001) evaluated hip adduction during squatting which, when applied to both legs simultaneously via a supportive tool to obtain the hip adduction position, was found to elicit higher VM muscle activity when compared to the conventional squat. Meanwhile, Felício et al. (2011) presented evidence of a hip adduction exercise on VM neuromuscular activity by adding a load of 25% of the participant's body weight during static squats with hip adduction exercises. The load of 25% was obtained by holding a bag that filled up with weight equal to 25% of participants' body weight, to their chest with both hands. The result of this study showed an increase in the VM EMG muscle signal during squats with hip adduction compared to traditional squats and squats with hip abduction (Felício et al., 2011). The element of adding load of 25% of the participant body weight during squat with hip adduction exercise in Felício et al. (2011) may result in the difference in the effect of squat with hip adduction on VM EMG signals compared to the present study. Also, resisted hip abduction and resisted hip adduction exercises were assessed during bridging exercises on the biceps femoris neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals

previously by Hwang et al. (2017), who found that the biceps femoris muscle activity was higher in resisted hip adduction than the hip abduction or neutral bridge condition. Thera-Band in the present study was used to induce resisted hip adduction while MVC was used from the OKC position to utilise hip flexion during the static squat. Hwang et al. (2017) utilised a ball to induce resisted hip adduction, before normalising data to MVC obtained during the CKC position and using 0° of hip extension. Moreover, Hwang et al. (2017) used a fixed angle of 30° hip adduction or abduction whereas the hip adduction in the present study was standardised between participants by fixed length and distance from the plinth, as shown in Figure 6.1.

The role of individualised WBV frequency on EMG signals on different muscles was explained in detail in Chapter 5. Therefore, all data generated in this study using WBV stimuli were collected using individualised frequencies for each individual participant. No significant differences in VM neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals were identified between 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz frequencies, evaluated across two separate visits conducted within the same week prior to the present study. The results of individualised frequency on muscle activity conflicted with Di Giminiani et al. (2009), as described in Chapter 5. However, the differences in the inter-day reliability values of the individualised frequency in the present study compared to Di Giminiani et al. (2009), could possibly explain for this difference as demonstrated in Chapter 5. WBV stimuli have been used on healthy individuals in strengthening programmes for VM muscle during static squatting (Roelants et al., 2006, Marín and Hazell, 2014). Despite these results, the effectiveness of WBV stimuli on neuromuscular activity is still uncertain (Lienhard, Vienneau, et al., 2015), therefore further research is needed to investigate the effect of WBV parameters and body position on WBV stimuli.

The next point to consider when evaluating the effectiveness of exercises involving equipment that produces vibration stimuli is the familiarisation effect. Previously, study conducted by Goodwill and Kidgell, (2012) performed a familiarisation session one week before investigating the single leg maximum strength testing in a strength training group compared to a strength training group with WBV stimuli. The familiarisation session involved correcting the participant posture during vibration exercises and it was reported that no significant difference was found between the two tested groups. However, all participants in the present study performed one trial per exercise and they performed the squat exercise with WBV stimuli in two previous visits when data were collected to evaluate the reliability of individualised frequency. Therefore, those first 2 visits can be considered familiarisation for squat with WBV stimuli, however the same can't be applied to the squat exercise with Thera-Band. Also, the effect of familiarisation on EMG signals during exercises with WBV stimuli needs further research in healthy individuals and clinical populations.

Also, the role of the EMG data normalisation process, discussed in previous chapters, must be considered (Chapters 4 and 5). Although the normalisation procedures were standardised across this thesis (MVC in OKC), there is a lot of divergence across other studies (Marín et al., 2011; Avelar et al., 2013). Marín et al. (2011) who compared the acute EMG signals during squat with loads on WBV stimuli to Smith machine, normalised the EMG signals to an unloaded squat position without vibration stimuli and not to the MVC values in OKC or CKC. No difference was found between the vibration stimuli and the Smith machine on VM and VL EMG signals (Marín et al., 2011). However, VM and VL peak EMG signals were normalised to MVCs values during eccentric and concentric dynamic movement (OKC) to evaluate dynamic knee extension exercises in a sitting position with Thera-Band compared to an isotonic strengthen machine (Jakobsen et al., 2012). No difference was found in normalised VM and VL peak EMG signals in dynamic knee

extension during the concentric movement. However, normalised VM peak signal during eccentric movement significantly increased in training machine compared to Thera-Band (Jakobsen et al., 2012). As the above indicates, the outputs from the two studies are divergent. This highlights a requirement for further research to assess the role of normalisation methods during exercise with Thera-Band to evaluate VM neuromuscular activity or the quadriceps muscle as a group, with well-justified and robust methods. Further study is required to evaluate the effect of different normalisation practices, for example, OKC, CKC and MVC conducted in the same exercise position involving WBV stimuli but without vibration stimuli (0 Hz).

The importance of applying appropriate filtering techniques was discussed previously in Chapter 4 and 5. Applying multiple notch filters on EMG data can potentially exclude EMG signals to minimise noise during the evaluation of the exercises. The filters applied to EMG signals can underestimate the recorded EMG signals when assessing the effects of the exercises (Abercromby et al., 2007), although this is usually considered to be an advantage to avoid artifacts in the EMG signals during WBV (Lienhard, et al., 2015). Therefore, the consensus in the literature recommends the application of filters thereby excluding data rather than recording noise, incorporating it into the analysis and overestimating the findings (Konrad, 2006). Implementing exercises involving resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli in clinical practice needs further considerations for the required time, effort, and training of these exercises in rehabilitation programmes specially when a small effect size found in the present study. Therefore, further research is required to investigate effect of these exercises in clinical setting.

Anecdotally, the participants of this study mentioned that exercises involving squats with WBV stimuli were easier to maintain than other exercises. There is as yet no scientific justification in the literature for the difference in comfort between maintaining exercises involving vibration

stimuli and exercises without vibration stimuli in healthy individuals; therefore, further research should investigate this anecdotal report.

6.5 Limitations

A limitation of the present study is that only one trial per exercise was performed. Therefore, further study suggested to be conducted with three trials for each exercise and the maximum or mean should be calculated. Moreover, the chronic effect of the exercise protocols combining the Thera-Band and WBV stimuli is required to be compared to the acute protocols adopted here. Furthermore, the effect of exercise protocols combining resisted hip adduction via Thera-Band and acute WBV on acute VM neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals is required to be compared to individuals with PFPS. Finally, the difference in WBV exposure time has been discussed in previous chapters (Chapter 4) when comparing the exposure time of 30 s and 60 s on muscle power rather than on the EMG signal (Borges et al., 2017; Adams et al., 2009). Therefore, further research is warranted on WBV stimuli exposure times of less 30 s and more than 60 s on EMG signals.

6.6 Conclusions

Although previous studies have shown the significant effect of WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction separately on VM muscle activity in a healthy population (Hertel et al., 2004, Marín and Hazell, 2014), this appears to be the first study that investigates the acute effect of combining WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction by Thera-Band on VM and VL neuromuscular activation during static squatting. This approach investigates squatting with resisted hip adduction, squatting with WBV stimuli, and squatting with resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli did not reveal any differences on the VM for the dominant limb, and VL muscle activities for the dominant and non-dominant limbs in healthy individuals compared to squatting alone. Therefore, the four exercises

would be expected to achieve the similar results in healthy individuals, and any one exercise could be used and this may be down to individual preference. However, squatting alone can be used to increase the normalised VM muscle activity of the non-dominant limb compared to static double leg squat with resisted hip adduction. Therefore, exercises aiming to strengthen the VM muscle in healthy individuals requires further research to compare the acute and chronic effect of variations of static and dynamic movements; squatting, sitting and standing exercises on the VM and VL neuromuscular activity in healthy populations. Finally, the effectiveness of the four tested exercises should be investigated in the PFPS patient population. This question is the focus of the next chapter, which investigates the effectiveness of these exercises in individuals with PFPS.

Chapter 7

Evaluation of VM and VL neuromuscular activity during static squatting with WBV and resisted hip adduction in individuals with PFPS.

7.1 Introduction

PFPS is pain in the anterior part of the knee often experienced during running, static or dynamic squatting and sitting for long time. PFPS is a musculoskeletal condition that may develop in older individuals, peaking in the 50-59 years old age group, and affects approximately 25% of the general population (Glaviano et al., 2015). The aetiology of PFPS is not fully understood despite the consensus that quadriceps weakness is the central risk factor (Neal et al., 2019). Quadriceps muscle weakness may result from the imbalance between the activity of VM and VL muscle which can result in tracking the patella laterally. The imbalance in the quadriceps muscle culminates by activating the VM muscle after VL muscle activation with VM:VL ratio approaching 1:2. Quadriceps weakness as a central risk factor alludes to the possibility that an imbalance in VM/VL ratio could be causative (Kim and Song, 2012).

The efficacy of an exercise approach to correct a VM/VL imbalance is still questionable. Recently, the 2016 and 2018 PFPS consensus recommend combined interventions or exercises in both short- and long-term treatment programs for individuals with PFPS (Crossley et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2018). These combined interventions can include static and dynamic strengthening exercises to promote hip and knee motor control. The effects of these different interventions should be investigated and tailored to individuals with PFPS on each individual alone and according to their symptoms. Combining knee and hip exercises significantly decreased pain level in individuals with PFPS and improved the functional activity measured by VAS and Kujala functional score (Şahin et al., 2016). Combined interventions including foot orthoses and patellar taping on pain

level and individual's functions in individuals with PFPS were evaluated by Willy et al. (2019) and showed range of low to high quality of studies that investigated combined interventions while the combined knee-hip exercises significantly increased physical functioning in individuals with PFPS and decreased their pain. However, the description of combined hip and knee exercises needs further investigation. Physiotherapy treatment may incorporate combined intervention exercises designed to strengthen muscles under various conditions (Lake and Wofford, 2011; Argut et al. 2017). Argut et al. (2017) reported the results of a comparative investigatory study between two interventions for individuals with PFPS. The two interventions involved one group receiving strengthening exercises combined with electrical simulation for 12 weeks, and the second group receiving strengthening exercises only. An isokinetic dynamometer was used to evaluate quadriceps muscle strength in both groups; no significant difference in quadriceps muscle strength was observed between both groups (Argut et al., 2017). The effectiveness of combined intervention approaches remains in doubt for the treatment of PFPS neuromuscular conditions (Argut et al., 2017), therefore further research is needed to elucidate any benefit of combined intervention in individuals with PFPS. Although combined exercises and combined interventions have been investigated in clinical practice in individuals with PFPS (Crossley et al., 2002; Fukuda et al., 2012), the literature is lacking studies on the optimised protocol to be used in the treatment of individuals with PFPS. Therefore, further evaluation is necessary to assess the effectiveness of combined interventions to strengthen the evidence base upon which the PFPS treatment consensus is building.

Recent studies have shown WBV stimuli to be an effective intervention when used in strengthening exercises and rehabilitation programs for different patient populations, for example for those with PFPS, osteoarthritis (OA) and stroke (Corum et al., 2018; Lai et al., 2017; Huang

and Pang, 2019). Also, the role of WBV stimuli on acute VM neuromuscular activity during static squat positioning in healthy individuals has been assessed in the literature despite a limited evidence base (Roelants et al., 2006; Marín and Hazell, 2014). However, this assessment is still considered recent and its effectiveness needs further evaluation in healthy individuals with regards to the optimal WBV parameters for individual's muscles and body position. These were discussed earlier in Chapters 4 and 5, and the effect of squatting exercises involving WBV and resisted hip adduction on acute VM and VL neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals was investigated in Chapter 6.

Exercise with WBV stimuli has been evaluated on hamstring muscle. WBV stimuli was found to significantly increase hamstring peak power during a bridge exercise compared to a decline bench press exercise in healthy individuals (García-Gutiérrez, Hazell and Marín, 2016). Moreover, activity of the VL and rectus femoris muscles increased by 8.7% and 2.0% respectively during a dynamic squat with WBV compared to a static squat in healthy individuals (Hazell, Jakobi and Kenno, 2007). Also, activity of the biceps brachii and triceps brachii muscle increased during dynamic bilateral bicep curls with WBV by 0.8% and 1.0% respectively (Hazell, Jakobi and Kenno, 2007). WBV stimuli may best serve the lower limb muscles during static, double-leg squats compared to the upper limbs because the lower limbs are closer to the WBV platform (Pollock et al., 2010). Studies investigating the effectiveness of WBV stimuli on lower limbs have done so in relation to different pathological conditions (Lai et al., 2017; Corum et al., 2018), muscles (Pollock et al., 2010), WBV parameters (Lienhard et al., 2014), exposure time, position and posture (Carlucci et al., 2016). However, investigating the effect of WBV stimuli parameter outputs in treatment protocols for clinical populations such as individuals with PFPS requires further attention.

The first randomised controlled trial conducted by Corum et al. (2018) evaluated the effectiveness of combining exercises programme including lunge-step, semi-squat, ball- squeeze squat and dynamic squat on WBV platform with 35 Hz frequency for 20-30 minutes with home exercises on the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), Kujala Patellofemoral Score (KPS), and Short Form-36 (SF-36) to determine pain and disability from PFPS, along with knee extensor torque evaluated by isokinetic dynamometer, in an intervention group of individuals with PFPS. This group was compared to a control group of individuals with PFPS who performed home-based exercises only including 10-15 repetitions of isometric quadriceps, knee extensions and double-legged wall squat. These measures were obtained before and after 24 sessions during eight weeks for both the intervention and control groups. In that study, the WBV exposure time was increased gradually from 30s to 60s during 8 weeks of a WBV training program. Although that study did not report a change in KPS and SF-36 scores in combined WBV training with home-based exercises protocol, VAS and knee extension torque were significantly improved (Corum et al., 2018). This indicates that WBV stimuli can impact upon objective and subjective outcome measures, however this protocol did not report upon the acute effect of WBV stimuli on muscle EMG signals and included a range of dynamic exercises performed on WBV platform.

Quadriceps weakness was defined as a risk factor for PFPS while the performance of squat exercises was postulated as a method to address the quadriceps imbalance or weakness and correct the VM/VL ratio in individuals with PFPS (Kim and Song, 2012). The role of various squat exercises in the treatment of individuals with PFPS and their impact on VM neuromuscular activity was described in Chapter 2, the meta-analysis. There it was shown that WBV stimuli can significantly increase VM neuromuscular activity in a healthy population during static double-leg squatting and no study has been found in PFPS population. However, the effectiveness of

traditional physiotherapy interventions (open or closed kinetic chain strengthening exercises) were evaluated and reviewed by systematic reviews and meta-analysis previously and found the traditional physiotherapy interventions improved physical activity and decreased the pain level in individual with PFPS (Papadopoulos, Stasinopoulos and Ganchev, 2015; Santos et al., 2015).

Recent literature has been investigated the effectiveness of WBV stimuli in rehabilitation programs for patients with knee conditions such as PFPS or OA (Park et al., 2013; Corum et al., 2018). Also, exercises which target muscle strength, must be explicitly assessed in PFPS populations by collecting valid and informative EMG signal data in evaluating the effectiveness of WBV on muscle activity (Di Giminiani et al., 2015). Given that patients with PFPS often develop OA in the long term (Mills and Hunter, 2014), the effect of WBV stimuli in individuals with knee OA should also consider that OA has been linked to PFPS (Abbasi et al., 2017). The WBV stimuli combined with home-based program effectively improved pain in individuals with OA after 8 weeks compared to the home-based program alone (Park et al., 2013). It is therefore pertinent to investigate WBV stimuli as a possible treatment for individuals with PFPS.

The concept and role of an individualised WBV stimulus was first introduced in a study which described how muscle responds to specific WBV parameters (Di Giminiani et al., 2013). This work followed an investigation by Marín and Rhea (2010) which assessed WBV parameters such as frequency and peak-to-peak displacement, suggesting that specific combinations of these parameters can produce greater effects on individuals' muscles activity and strengthening exercises. Therefore, the inter-day reliability of an individualised frequency for VM muscle during static double-leg squat was evaluated in this thesis on 26 healthy individuals, and the individualised WBV stimuli did not significantly enhance VM muscle activity compared to other WBV frequencies ranging from 30 Hz to 50 Hz (see Chapter 5). This finding conflicted with previous

reports where the authors suggested that each muscle in an individual has a specific and optimal frequency that will stimulate a maximal response (Cardinale and Lim, 2003; Giombini et al., 2013). However, no reports as yet have tested the individualised frequency theory in individuals with pathological knee conditions. Further, the effect of individualised WBV stimuli has not yet been tested in PFPS treatment protocols. Further research is needed to investigate the effect of individualised WBV frequency in combination with other interventions on PFPS during short- and long-term treatment protocols.

Although the use of conventional equipment such as Thera-Bands in strengthening programs for individuals with PFPS has been investigated by Miao et al. (2015), the literature did not adequately investigate Thera-Band exercises in individuals with PFPS. The validity and inter- and intraday reliability of green and blue Thera-Band forces and the utility in strengthening exercises on the VM muscle was determined in Chapter 4 and Chapter 6 respectively. Previous studies have reported the use of Thera-Band during open and closed kinetic chain exercises (Wallace, et al., 2006; Lee, et al., 2016). In general, resisted hip adduction exercise with Thera-band has been introduced in the literature pertaining to PFPS treatment but has not been explored and evaluated sufficiently.

The present study aimed to investigate the effect of WBV stimuli alone, resisted hip adduction alone, and combined WBV stimulation with resisted hip adduction during static double-leg squats on acute VM and VL neuromuscular activity in individuals with PFPS. The static squat posture with 65° knee flexion was recommended to be used in rehabilitation programmes for individuals with PFPS (Miao et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2018). It was hypothesised that combined exercises of resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli increase VM neuromuscular activity and address the

imbalance in VM/VL ratio during static double-leg squatting in individuals with PFPS compared to squat alone, squat with hip adduction and squat with WBV stimuli.

7.2 Methods

A total of 16 individuals with PFPS symptoms volunteered to participate in the study. All participants were recruited as described in section 3.1 (Appendix 6). All included participants were adults diagnosed with PFPS aged 18 or over. The mean \pm SD age was 35.1 ± 14 years; weight 72.6 ± 9.6 kg; height 173.3 ± 10.2 cm; and BMI, 24.3 ± 3.0 kg/m². Inclusion criteria were: mild-moderate pain in the anterior knee (VAS between 3 and 6 out of 10) which was more than 3 months in duration, and with pain during at least two of the following activities: prolonged sitting, squatting, ascending or descending stairs, running, kneeling, or jumping. Participants who did not have the ability to tolerate the static double-leg squat for 20s without developing further complications were excluded. If participants had bilateral knee symptoms, the most painful limb was counted as the symptomatic limb. All participants read the participant information sheet (Appendix 8), signed the consent form (Appendix 9) and answered the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) questionnaire. Participants were excluded if they answered yes to any question on the PAR-Q. Ethical approval was obtained from the UWS School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee application number 6348 (Appendix 7).

7.2.1 Protocol

Each participant attended one visit that lasted for 45 min in the Biomechanics laboratory at UWS. The data collection sessions started with collecting the height and weight then performing warm-up (see section 3.1). EMG data were collected from the symptomatic and asymptomatic limb for all participants. The EMG sensors placed on the VM and VL muscles of both legs according to SENIAM guidelines (see section 3.3.2). EMG data during a MVC was collected for both limbs

(see section 3.2.2). All 16 participants performed 4 exercises involving WBV stimuli (VibraMachines Ltd., Ledborough, UK) and resisted hip adduction with Thera-Band (Hygenic Corporation, Akron, USA) during squatting for 20s for each trial (see section 3.4). The exercises were 1) static double leg squat 2) static double leg squat with resisted hip adduction 3) static double leg squat with 40 Hz WBV stimuli 4) static double leg squat with 40 Hz WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction. A fixed WBV stimuli frequency was used at 40 Hz which, as shown in Chapter 5, found no difference between WBV stimuli frequencies of 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz in healthy individuals. The frequency range between 35 Hz to 40 Hz is recommended for use in neuromuscular performance (Corum et al., 2018). Each participant performed only one trial of each exercise with a total of six exercises to avoid fatigue and decrease the risk of reproducing knee pain. The rest time between exercises was 2 min. The exercise order was randomised by random number generator. At the end of the experiment, a cool down was performed as described in section 4.5.2.2.

7.2.2 Data analysis

All EMG data were analysed via EMGworks software (Delsys, Inc, Boston, USA) (see 3.5.1). A band-pass filter (20 Hz to 450 Hz) and band-stop filters were applied. at a frequency of 40 Hz and subharmonics at 80 Hz, 120 Hz and 160 Hz. Then, EMG data were rectified, and the RMS was obtained. All EMG data were normalised to MVICs in a sitting position as described in the data analysis section of Chapter 6 (see section 6.2.3). The VM/VL ratio was calculated for each exercise for the symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs in individuals with PFPS during each exercise according to the following equation:

$$\text{VM/VL ratio} = \frac{\text{Normalised VM muscle activity during each exercise}}{\text{Normalised VL muscle activity during each exercise.}}$$

7.2.3 Statistical analysis

Data were imported into SPSS version 25 (IBM UK Ltd, Hampshire, UK). Data normality for four exercises assessed as described in section 3.5.2. A Friedman ANOVA test was performed to compare effect of the 4 exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of neuromuscular activity and VM/VL ratios in symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs. A post-hoc Wilcoxon two related sample test was used to investigate significant differences between exercises if a main effect was found. The effect size was also calculated in SPSS and evaluated by Kendall's test in non-parametric test as described in section 3.5.2. The VM/VL ratios for the symptomatic or asymptomatic limbs were evaluated and compared to value 1 by one sample Wilcoxon test. Also, the maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL muscle activities and VM/VL ratios of the symptomatic limb were compared to asymptomatic limb for each of the four exercises by Wilcoxon two related sample test. The Spearman correlation (ρ) was used to evaluate the correlation between pain level (VAS) and the maximum normalised amplitude of neuromuscular activities, and the VM/VL ratios in symptomatic limb for each exercise conditions. Alpha value with significance level of $p = 0.05$ was used for all performed tests.

7.3 Results

All 16 participants completed the full experimental procedure. Data were visually inspected for quality to check for e.g. signal loss. All participants completed all trials, and data from all trials were included based on visual inspection of the raw data. All participants had only unilateral symptoms. All normalised EMG Data were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$), and this was supported from visual inspection of the associated data plots.

7.3.1 The VM, VL neuromuscular activities and VM/VL ratio for symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs in individuals with PFPS

No significant difference in normalised muscle activity was found between the four exercises during static squat positioning in the symptomatic or asymptomatic limbs for VM (Figure 7.1).

Figure 7.1: Median and interquartile range of maximal neuromuscular activity of the vastus medialis (VM) muscle for the symptomatic and asymptomatic limb during four static squat exercises. TB: TheraBand, WBV: Whole body vibration.

Table 21. illustrates the Chi-square, p value and effect size (z) for the differences in four exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of VM for symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs.

Table 21. The difference in four exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of vastus medialis (VM) for symptomatic or asymptomatic limbs. Thera-Band: TB, Whole body vibration: WBV, IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = *p* value, effect size (*z*).

Difference between four exercises in normalised VM muscle activity								
Limb	Symptomatic limb				Asymptomatic limb			
Exercise	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B
Median measurement % (IQR)	50.61 (30.86)	46.95 (37.38)	49.92 (48.72)	42.61 (57.09)	39.15 (49.05)	45.15 (20.23)	47.71 (38.64)	44.76 (30.61)
Chi-Square	4.500				2.775			
<i>P</i> value	0.212				0.428			
<i>z</i>	0.094 (very small)				0.058 (very small)			

No significant difference in maximum normalised amplitude of VL muscle activity was found between the four exercises during static squat positioning in the symptomatic or asymptomatic limbs (Figure 7.2).

Figure 7.2: Median and interquartile range of maximal neuromuscular activity of the vastus lateralis (VL) muscle for the symptomatic and asymptomatic limb during four static squat exercises. TB: TheraBand, WBV: Whole body vibration.

Table 22. illustrates the Chi-square, p value and effect size (z) for the differences in four exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of VL for symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs.

Table 22. The difference in four exercises on maximum normalised amplitude of vastus lateralis (VL) for symptomatic or asymptomatic limbs. Thera-Band: TB, Whole body vibration: WBV, IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = p value, effect size (z).

Difference between four exercises in normalised VL muscle activity								
Limb	Symptomatic limb				Asymptomatic limb			
Exercise	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B
Median measurement % (IQR)	35.88 (17.72)	41.89 (35.99)	35.73 (25.10)	39.18 (32.48)	37.17 (29.22)	44.58 (18.16)	36.71 (22.56)	41.83 (15.42)
Chi-Square	1.575				0.750			
P value	0.665				0.861			
z	0.033 (very small)				0.016 (very small)			

No significant difference in normalised muscle activity was found between the four exercises during static squat positioning in the symptomatic or asymptomatic limbs for VM/VL ratio (Figure 7.3).

Figure 7.3: Median and interquartile range of VM/VL ratio for the symptomatic and asymptomatic limb during four static squat exercises. TB: TheraBand, WBV: Whole body vibration.

Table 23. illustrates the Chi-square, p value and effect size (z) for the differences in four exercises on VM/VL for symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs.

Table 23. The difference in four exercises on VM/VL ratio for symptomatic or asymptomatic limbs. Thera-Band: TB, Whole body vibration: WBV, IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = p value, effect size (z).

Difference between four exercises in normalised VM/VL								
Limb	Symptomatic limb				Asymptomatic limb			
Exercise	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B	Squat	Squat with T.B	Squat with WBV stimuli	Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B
Median measurement % (IQR)	1.36 (0.67)	1.06 (0.48)	1.29 (0.73)	1.14 (0.58)	0.97 (0.58)	0.94 (0.23)	1.02 (0.53)	1.04 (0.42)
Chi-Square	4.044				4.204			
P value	0.257				0.240			
z	0.084 (small)				0.088 (small)			

7.3.2 The VM/VL ratio for symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs compared to the theoretical value in individuals with PFPS

In the symptomatic limb the median ratio significantly differed from 1 during squatting only ($p = 0.034$) and squat with WBV ($p = 0.028$), and did not significantly differ in the squat with resisted hip adduction exercise and squat with resisted hip adduction and WBV exercise ($p = 0.244$ and 0.121 respectively). In the asymptomatic limb the median ratio was not significantly differ in the four tested exercises (all $p > 0.05$) (Table24).

Table 24. The VM/VL ratios for the symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs for each of the four exercises compared to 1. Thera-Band: TB, Whole body vibration: WBV, IQR = interquartile range, Alpha value = p value.

VM/VL ratio						
Symptomatic limb				Asymptomatic limb		
Exercise	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	p value	Theoretical value	Median measurement (IQR)	p value
Squat only	1	1.36* (0.67)	0.034	1	0.970 (0.58)	0.501
Squat with T.B	1	1.06 (0.48)	0.244	1	0.935 (0.23)	0.349
Squat with WBV stimuli	1	1.29** (0.73)	0.028	1	1.026 (0.53)	0.513
Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B	1	1.14 (0.58)	0.121	1	1.035 (0.42)	0.255

* VM/VL ratio in static double leg squat was significantly higher than theoretical value ($P < 0.05$).

** VM/VL ratio in static double leg squat with WBV stimuli was significantly higher than theoretical value ($P < 0.05$).

There was no significant difference in neuromuscular activity for VM, VL and VM/VL ratios between the symptomatic limb and asymptomatic limbs for each of the four exercises ($p > 0.05$) (Table 25).

Table 25. The differences in maximum normalised amplitude of vastus medialis (VM) and vastus lateralis (VL) muscles activities and VM/VL ratios of the symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs for each of the four exercises. TB: Thera-Band, WBV: Whole body vibration. Alpha value = p value.

Exercises	The differences in VM, VL and VM/VL ratios											
	Squat			Squat with T.B			Squat with WBV stimuli			Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B		
	VM %	VL %	VM/VL ratio	VM %	VL %	VM/VL ratio	VM %	VL %	VM/VL ratio	VM %	VL %	VM/VL ratio
Symptomatic	50.61	35.88	1.36	46.95	41.89	1.06	49.92	35.73	1.29	42.61	39.18	1.14
Asymptomatic	39.15	37.17	0.79	45.15	44.58	0.94	47.71	36.71	1.02	44.76	41.83	1.04
Median difference	11.46	1.29	0.38	1.79	2.69	0.12	2.21	0.98	0.27	2.15	2.65	0.10
p value	0.796	0.469	0.155	0.717	0.756	0.115	0.501	0.796	0.196	0.959	0.569	0.408

7.3.3 Investigation the relationship between neuromuscular activity and pain in individuals with PFPS.

There was no significant association between pain and VM and VL EMG signals and VM/VL ratio of symptomatic limb during all exercise conditions as shows in Table 26.

Table 26. Spearman correlation (ρ) for maximum normalised amplitude of vastus muscle (VM) and vastus lateralis (VL) EMG signals and VMVL ratio of symptomatic limb during four exercise conditions Thera-Band: TB, Whole body vibration: WBV, Alpha value = p value

Exercise in symptomatic limb	Squat			Squat with T.B			Squat with WBV stimuli			Squat with WBV stimuli and T.B		
	VM	VL	VM/VL ratio	VM	VL	VM/VL ratio	VM	VL	VM/VL ratio	VM	VL	VM/VL ratio
Spearman correlation (ρ)	-0.226	-0.461	-0.031	-0.101	-0.232	0.157	-0.329	-0.293	-0.11	-0.159	-0.378	0.098
p value	0.401	0.073	0.911	0.711	0.388	0.561	0.213	0.271	0.681	0.557	0.149	0.719

7.4 Discussion

The present study was the first study that aimed to evaluate and compare the effect of four squat exercises upon acute maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL neuromuscular activity for the symptomatic or asymptomatic limb in individuals with PFPS: 1) static double leg squat 2) static double leg squat with resisted hip adduction 3) static double leg squat with 40 Hz WBV

stimuli 4) static double leg squat with 40 Hz WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction. The results suggested that all four exercises performed equally with regards to muscle activation and can be used in terms of inducing acute maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL neuromuscular activity in the symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs of individuals with PFPS. Furthermore, the four exercises have an equal effect on VM/VL ratio in symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs. However, the squat exercise alone and squatting with WBV stimuli can be used in clinical practice with the aim of increasing VM/VL ratio in a symptomatic limb. This suggests that squatting exercises alone and squatting with the WBV stimuli may help to identify the imbalance in neuromuscular activity between maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL muscles in PFPS patients when compared to the normal VM/VL ratio.

The role of therapeutic hip motor control exercises on knee valgus position for individuals with PFPS was illustrated and discussed in a systematic review carried out by Meira and Brumitt (2011) who evaluated the role of hip position during squatting in individuals with PFPS and found the hip position can influence the knee motor control muscles. Therefore, the increase in knee valgus can result in increasing the lateral contact in the patellofemoral joint and weakens the VM muscle. PFPS is commonly treated by addressing VM muscle weakness, thus the resisted hip adduction exercise can be included in PFPS rehabilitation programs to strengthen the VM muscle. The resisted hip adduction can be achieved by Thera-Band and other tools designed to elicit resistance (Coqueiro et al., 2005; Miao et al., 2015). A review by Meira and Brumitt (2011) highlighted that hip position is important when considering strengthening treatment programs for individuals with PFPS. The primary difference between the Meira and Brumitt (2011) study and the present study, is that Meira and Brumitt (2011) evaluated hip position during dynamic movement, and the present study evaluated muscle activity during various static double leg squat positions. Hip position

(adduction and abduction) was found to have an inconsistent effect in individuals with PFPS (Meira and Brumitt, 2011). Therefore, further evaluation is required for the effect of resisted hip position during static and dynamic movements in individuals with PFPS.

Yen et al. (2009) compared a combined hip adduction and leg press exercise to a leg press exercise alone in individuals with PFPS, as well as a control group with no exercise. Subjective and objective measures were used to evaluate the effect of leg press exercises and hip adduction on individuals pain level and function activities for all groups after performing the selected exercise for three sessions per week for eight weeks. The subjective measures were VAS and Lysholm scale scores which used in evaluating the knee instability, pain level and physical activity, while the objective measure comprised measurement of VM muscle volume by ultrasonography. No significant differences in subjective and objective measures were determined for the combined hip adduction and leg press exercise compared to the leg-press alone exercise in individuals with PFPS. However, both exercises increased the VM muscle volume and improved subjective measures in individuals with PFPS compared to the control group (Yen et al., 2009). The authors from that study suggested that VM muscle atrophy appeared to be an indication of PFPS. In the present study, the role of hip motor control exercises on muscle weakness evaluated by EMG output in individuals with PFPS while Yen et al. (2009) evaluated the muscle volume by ultrasonography which cannot be measured by EMG. Therefore, further research is necessary to compare the effect of exercises with different hip positions on muscle weakness to allow the comparison between EMG outputs in the short- and long-term training programmes.

Chang, Huang and Lai (2015) compared the normalised VM and VL EMG signals and the VM/VL ratio in individuals with PFPS during sling-based exercises in open kinetic chain exercise (OKC), closed kinetic chain exercise (CKC) and hip adduction exercise in supine and side lying non-

weight-bearing positions. VM neuromuscular activity was found to be relatively low during a sling exercise with hip adduction compared to the sling in open and closed chain exercises. The VM/VL ratio was found to be equal to 1 in sling-based exercise during hip adduction and closed kinetic chain exercises and equal to 0.8 in sling exercise during open kinetic chain exercise which indicates VL muscle is activated before VM muscle. The hip adduction position was obtained in OKC exercise in a side-lying position and compared to a sling exercise in CKC, however in the present study, the hip adduction exercise was conducted in CKC and compared to CKC exercises only. Moreover, all the conducted exercises in the Chang et al. (2015) study were obtained in supine which is a gravity minimising position, while the present study evaluated VM EMG signals and VM/VL ratio in a static double leg squat position which is an antigravity position. Also, as discussed in Chapter 4, VM neuromuscular activity increased in the squatting position with knee angle ranging from 65° and 90°. Thus, the closed kinetic chain exercise in Chang et al. (2015) was found to elicit greater VM activity which corroborated the results presented here, regardless of conditions or position. However, this was not compared to standing or supine positions in the present study. Therefore, the closed kinetic chain exercise was found to increase VM neuromuscular activity and correct the imbalance in VM/VL ratio in individuals with PFPS in supine or squat positions.

The combined interventions have been investigated recently in individuals with PFPS (Lake and Wofford, 2011; Argut et al., 2017). The effect of a combined physiotherapy treatment program and a resisted hip adduction exercise which achieved by resisting a ball between the knees of individuals with PFPS during squatting on VM/VL ratio for 4 weeks, compared to a group which performed a physiotherapy treatment program alone (Adel et al., 2019). No significant difference was found in VM/VL ratio between the groups, however a comparison between symptomatic and

asymptomatic limbs was not performed. Giles et al.,(2015) found no significant difference in VM/VL muscle thickness by ultrasound assessment in the symptomatic limb of individuals with PFPS compared to the asymptomatic limb. Also, the VM neuromuscular activity and VM/VL ratio were evaluated during the resisted hip adduction exercises, knee extension exercise with hip external rotation and knee extension with neutral hip position in 11 individuals with PFPS (Singh and Srivastava, 2018). In that study, no significant differences were found in VM/VL ratio for any exercise, however, the VM muscle activity increased during the knee extension exercise with hip external rotation exercise. The authors did not report whether they performed a comparison to asymptomatic limbs or whether the comparison obtained was between the exercises only (Singh and Srivastava, 2018). Therefore, the present study expanded upon these findings by comparing the symptomatic and asymptomatic responses.

The main goal of the present study was to evaluate the ability of exercises to increase VM neuromuscular activity in individuals with PFPS. Combined resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli exercises in CKC including squat alone, squat with resisted hip adduction and squat with WBV stimuli, have an equal effect on VM muscle activity and on the VM/VL ratio in symptomatic limbs of people with PFPS. Willson and Davis (2009) agreed that hip adduction is still not fully investigated in patients with PFPS, due to the possibility of excessive pressure caused by iliotibial band elongation on the lateral side of the patella. Therefore, hip adduction movement was significantly occurred during single leg jumping in individuals with PFPS and compared to healthy individuals (Willson and Davis, 2009). However, the results reported in the present study did not include a comparison with healthy individuals. Also, the effect of a resisted hip adduction exercise during double leg squat increased VM neuromuscular signals in individuals with PFPS compared to double-leg squat alone (Coqueiro et al., 2005). In that study, 10 subjects diagnosed with PFPS

were examined using a specific inclusion criterion which was included participant with no symptoms in the last 3 months. In the Coqueiro et al. (2005) study, the resisted hip adduction exercise was performed by a designed resistance device which is neither in current clinical use, nor were any intra-day or inter-day reliability results reported or validity of the outcome is measured and compared to other instruments typically employed for obtaining hip adduction, like a Thera-Band. Coqueiro and colleagues (2005) used very specific inclusion criteria; individuals were diagnosed with PFPS but were asymptomatic for three months before taking part in the study. At the same time, the resisted hip adduction exercise was performed with 45° knee flexion during semi-double-leg squatting, however the position that used in the normalisation process including MIVC was not clear. Finally, the Coqueiro et al. (2005) study reported demographic data where the mean \pm SD age for the PFPS volunteers was 23.2 ± 2.52 years, while in the present study, the age was 35.1 ± 14 years. The incidence of the PFPS condition for individuals aged between 30–39 years is 15% compared to the incidence risk for individuals aged between 20–29 years 10% (Glaviano et al., 2015).

The study conducted by Miao et al. in 2015 compared the effect of resisted hip adduction exercise in individuals with PFPS using green Thera-Band during a double-leg semi-squat on VM and VL neuromuscular activities to double-leg semi-squat alone. A significant effect of resisted hip adduction during a double-leg semi-squat was observed on the VM EMG signal compared to a double leg semi squat alone. Nevertheless, resisted hip adduction in double-leg semi-squat exhibited no effect on VL muscle activity in individuals with PFPS (Miao et al., 2015). In that study, the validity of the Thera-Band was not explored and no normalisation process was described. Moreover, the authors claimed that by comparing the participant's data to themselves, the need for a normalisation process was eliminated. This process is not commonly utilised in

EMG studies as the normalisation process is typically performed to establish a comparison of results between studies. The normalisation process and evaluation of the equipment validity are key factors when considering study results and drawing conclusions. Furthermore, the possibility of changing the Thera-Band between participants was not considered, as the force produced can be changed/reduced when the same band is used for 30 participants. Although in the present study the Thera-Band was changed between participants, further evaluation is needed to compare the effect of changing the Thera-Band between participants on produced force to the effect of using the same Thera-Band on the produced force for all participants. The green band in the present study was used according to standardised measures of distance, evaluated for intra-day reliability, and placed at a new standardised length before each trial for all included participants. Therefore, the present study sought to address such potential limitations, which could adversely affect the Thera-Band validity and the reproducibility of the results. Although RMS analysis indicated that the VM muscle was activated before the VL muscle during a double leg semi squat with resisted hip adduction (Miao et al., 2015), the limitations described above illustrate the need for further research with accurately diagnosed PFPS individuals and a well-designed protocol and analysis to evaluate the role of resisted hip adduction by Thera-Band in individuals with PFPS. However, the resisted hip adduction should be obtained with caution to avoid the excessive hip adduction which can be risk factor for PFPS condition (Neal, Barton, et al., 2019).

The second intervention used in the present study was the WBV stimuli, which has been investigated in studies including healthy individuals and patient populations (Roelants et al., 2006, Corum et al., 2018). The effectiveness of WBV stimuli on maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL neuromuscular activity during a static double leg squat in healthy individuals was discussed in Chapter 6. The effectiveness of WBV stimuli has been investigated in various patient

populations by subjective and objective outcomes measures (Park et al., 2013; Huang and Pang, 2019). OA is a condition for which PFPS has been identified as a risk factor (Mills and Hunter, 2014). The effects of WBV has been evaluated on VM muscle activity in OA (Abbasi et al., 2017). In that study, the VM muscle activity did not significantly increase in a semi-squat position after 12 sessions of a WBV training program, compared to a control group which performed home-based exercises including static quadriceps muscle contraction and straight leg raising and a placebo group which carried out squatting exercises without WBV therapy (Abbasi et al., 2017). Despite this finding, the protocol included 30° knee flexion semi squat with 30 Hz WBV stimuli and 2 sets of 1 min of WBV stimuli exposure in the first week, which increased by 1 set per week. The fourth week included a total of 5 sets. Moreover, the progression rate, which was defined as the percentage of the differences between the muscle activity value before starting the training programme to the muscle activity value after completing the training programme, was used to evaluate the effectiveness of the training programme during patient's recovery. The progression rate (%) in VM RMS value during semi-squat was significantly increased in the WBV training and placebo groups with 42% and 38.5% respectively compared to 4.2 % in the control group. Therefore, further research is required to investigate the effect of gradual increases in WBV stimuli exposure time in one day treatment protocols for OA and PFPS populations. Another study evaluated the effect of WBV stimuli on OA condition evaluated by Park et al. (2013) who found no significant difference in quadriceps torque measured by isokinetic dynamometer in individuals with OA after eight weeks of a WBV training programme compared to a home-based exercise program. However, the WBV therapy group exhibited a significant decrease in the pain numeric rating scale (NRS) after eight weeks of WBV training compared to home-based exercise program (Park et al., 2013). These two previous studies evaluated the effect of a long-term treatment

protocol of WBV stimuli on individuals with OA. In contrast, the present study assessed the acute and short-term effects of WBV stimuli on VM muscle activity during static double-leg squats in individuals with PFPS. Despite these differences, the findings of the Abbasi et al. (2017) and Park et al. (2013) studies are in agreement with the findings presented here regarding the lack of effectiveness of WBV stimuli on VM muscle activity in OA or PFPS populations, regardless of the differences in outcome measures and demographics data between studies. Therefore, further research is required to evaluate the relationship between pain level and acute VM neuromuscular activity in individuals with PFPS during acute and chronic exposure to WBV stimuli.

This study appears to be the first to have evaluated WBV stimuli in a PFPS population on acute VM neuromuscular activity and VM/VL ratio on the asymptomatic limb for individuals with PFPS during static double-leg squats. Although the squat exercise alone and the squat exercise with WBV stimuli in the symptomatic limb showed a significant difference in VM/VL ratio with small effect size compared to normal VM/VL ratio value of 1, this illustrates the importance of considering the VM/VL ratio during evaluation of exercise on VM neuromuscular activity. Therefore, the effectiveness of these exercises requires further evaluation to justify the time consuming in implementing these exercises in rehabilitation programmes. Moreover, further investigation is required regarding the effect of WBV parameters on the pain level and acute VM EMG signals in individuals with PFPS. This evaluation can be obtained on exercise evaluating the WBV stimuli alone or combined with other equipment/interventions in a strengthening exercise program and compared to strengthening exercises alone.

7.5 Limitations

The main limitation in the present study was the small number of obtained trials for each exercise and exposure duration to WBV stimuli. Although each exercise trial was obtained once only to avoid fatigue and decrease the risk of reproducing knee pain, it may not be the optimal trial and further trials needed to ensure consistency. Also, further research is necessary to assess the different exposure time during acute and longer WBV treatment protocols. The difficulty in recruiting number of individuals with PFPS to participate in the study was the second limitation. The individuals included in the present study with PFPS based on their self-reported symptoms, diagnosed previously with PFPS by physicians and fitted the inclusion criteria, however all participant did not undergo any physical examination during the present study. The diagnosis process for potential participants with PFPS plays an important role in evaluating these exercises for use within the required population. Therefore, the participants must undergo specific physical examination and evaluation by the physiotherapist before further research is conducted to confirm that the included participants do indeed suffer from PFPS.

7.6 Conclusion

Investigating the effect of resisted hip adduction, WBV stimuli and combining both during squat exercises in individuals with PFPS are new areas for research. Although the present study found no significant difference between the four tested exercises involving resisted hip adduction by green Thera-Band and WBV stimuli on maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL muscle activity of symptomatic and asymptomatic limbs during static double leg squat in individuals with PFPS, VM/VL ratio was found to be significant higher than 1 in the symptomatic limb than the normal VM/VL ratio (value of 1:1) during squatting alone and squatting with the WBV stimuli.

This is the first study to evaluate the effect of WBV stimuli combined with resisted hip adduction during squat on acute VM activity in individuals with PFPS. Therefore, further research is required to evaluate combined interventions targeting hip and knee motor control in PFPS populations.

Chapter 8

8.1 Main discussion chapter

This thesis aimed to evaluate the effect of different squatting exercises on VM neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals and individuals with patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS). The thesis had seven objectives: (1) to evaluate existing scientific literature on the effect of different squat exercises on acute VM muscle activity in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS; (2) to explore the reliability and validity of outputs from two WBV platforms; (3) to identify the validity of the force produced from blue and green Thera-Bands; (4) to assess the inter-day reliability of the Delsys Trigno Avanti electromyography (EMG) system; (5) to assess the inter-day reliability of individualised WBV stimuli on acute VM neuromuscular activity during static double-leg squats in healthy individuals; (6) to evaluate the effect of different static double leg-squats involving WBV stimuli (with individualised frequency) and resisted hip adduction with Thera-Bands on acute VM and VL neuromuscular activity in healthy individuals; (7) to evaluate different static double-leg squats involving WBV stimuli with a fixed frequency of 40 Hz, and resisted hip adduction with a Thera-Band on acute VM and VL neuromuscular activity in individuals with PFPS. This thesis may provide insights into how resistance exercises including WBV stimuli and Thera-Band can influence VM muscle activity during static squatting in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS.

8.2 Equipment validity and reliability

Similarly to other studies that evaluated the effectiveness of equipment (Lopes et al., 2018; Sorbie et al., 2018), this thesis evaluated WBV platforms, Thera-Band, and the Delsys EMG system to ascertain their reliability and validity. The validity of WBV platform outputs was evaluated by

testing with equivalent body weights of 90 kg, 95 kg, and 100 kg. Also, the inter-day reliability of WBV platform parameters was evaluated. However, this was not a common approach in other studies involving WBV stimuli, as the WBV platform was usually used without validity or inter-day reliability assessment of its outputs (Krol et al., 2011; Marín and Hazell, 2014). García-Gutiérrez, Hazell, and Marín (2016) reported high intra-day reliability of WBV Power Plate platform outputs, including acceleration and peak-to-peak displacement. Although the present thesis evaluated the inter-day reliability for the VibraMachine platform outputs but not the intra-day reliability, the findings showed high inter-day reliability for VibraMachine acceleration and peak-to-peak displacement. Platform validity was not evaluated in García-Gutiérrez, Hazell, and Marín's (2014) study, and this evaluation in the current thesis highlights the necessity of assessing WBV platform output validity and inter-day reliability before using them in research, as the findings in the present thesis of these evaluations quite different from what the manufacture stated. Chapter 4 showed that the outputs of the VibraMachine platform were closer to the theoretical values when compared to a similar assessment of the Vibe Plate platform. Previous studies have focused on the calculated WBV platform outputs alone, without comparing them to the theoretical values (Pel et al., 2009; Pollock et al., 2010; Marín and Hazell, 2014). Therefore, the evaluation of equipment reliability and validity in research needs more attention, especially for equipment-produced force or acceleration. Moreover, the selection of the type of vibration platform should be developed based on platform characteristics.

Moreover, equipment evaluation can reflect on the quality of the research findings, therefore Thera-Band was the second evaluated tool in this thesis. Miao et al. (2015) found Thera-Band to be a reliable piece of equipment during static squats in individuals with PFPS, but its validity was not assessed in their study. The validity can be ascertained by comparing the calculated force to

the manufacturer's theoretical values. This current thesis evaluated Thera-Band reliability and validity, and found them to be a reliable and valid tool for use during squat exercises. The Trigno Avanti Delsys EMG system was the third piece of equipment to be evaluated in this thesis. Green et al. (2019) investigated lower-limb neuromuscular activity by the Trigno Delsys EMG system during dynamic movement in healthy individuals which showed high reliability between sessions with ICCs ranging from 0.890 to 0.998 whereas low to high ICCs ranging from 0.53 to 0.86 were found during static movement by the same EMG system in this thesis. A study by de Araújo et al. (2009) found EMG inter-day reliability (ICC values) by Lynx EMG system for the upper-limb muscles during stable and unstable push-up exercises to be similar to the findings from this thesis in Chapter 4, however, this differs from Green et al.'s (2019) findings. This conflict may be related to the difference in test conditions (static vs dynamic movements, or upper limb vs lower limb). Also, inconsistency in applying different filters, including band-stop, high-pass and low-pass filters, to EMG signals may result in this variation in EMG reliability. Moreover, exercises with WBV stimuli can decrease EMG reliability by producing platform noise that influences the EMG signals. The CV values and SEM of EMG signals from evaluation of EMG reliability in this thesis were found to be high within each evaluated frequency; however, variability in EMG signals between individuals is expected in EMG studies (Bolgla et al., 2010; Kollmitzer, Ebenbichler, and Kopf, 1999). The literature lacks examination of the consistency of equipment output, such as that of WBV platforms and EMG systems, which can have further implications for the use of such equipment in evaluating the effectiveness of exercise. Also, there is limited literature on the inter-day reliability and validity of WBV platform outputs with different body weights, as discussed in Chapter 4. However, these assessments revealed the importance of evaluating WBV platform outputs before they are used in research.

8.3 Electromyography filters and the normalisation process for exercise with whole-body vibration stimuli

Band-pass and band-stop filters in this thesis were applied to exclude the spikes or motion artefacts produced at each WBV frequency and by their subharmonics. The process of this assessment is reported in Chapter 3. Borges et al. (2017) investigated the implications of applying band-stop filters while evaluating WBV stimuli, and they found that applying band-stop filters on the VL neuromuscular signals is needed while performing squats with 30 and 50 Hz. Supporting this, Lienhard et al. (2015) compared applying the band-stop filters on EMG signals to an alternative method called spectral linear interpolation, to reduce EMG signal bias. Both methods were recommended by Lienhard et al. (2015), with the same effect on EMG signals while evaluating WBV stimuli. Therefore, the band-stop filter has been applied to all EMG signals in this thesis. However, all previous studies were conducted on vertical platforms; thus, a comparison of the effect of these filters on EMG signal spikes in WBV platform types (horizontal or rotational) has yet to be conducted. The EMG signal spikes may have dissimilar influence on WBV platforms oscillate in horizontal or rotational direction. Therefore, further research is required to evaluate the effect of these EMG filters on WBV platform types to illustrate their implementation during exercise.

EMG recording time can influence by evaluation the effectiveness of WBV stimuli as the studies described in Chapters 4 to 7 were consistent with the recording-time procedure. Nonetheless, there is a lack of consistency in the literature regarding the optimal length of EMG signal recording time during squatting tasks, which ranged from 15 sec to 60 sec (Adams et al., 2009; Borges et al., 2017). Also, the optimal method for calculating the excluded or included EMG recording time during WBV stimuli needs further evaluation, to illustrate the effectiveness of WBV stimuli.

Chapters 2 and 3 offer an overview of the justification for the selection of recording time, as described in previous literature; however, this area needs further research to evaluate the estimated required time for each platform to be functional during exercise performance. Moreover, consensus on the optimal recording time should be reached across the research field to determine the minimum time required for data collection during EMG analysis.

EMG data analysis also includes the normalising of the EMG signals during WBV stimuli. This thesis normalised the EMG signals to the highest MVC value obtained during three trials of an open-chain knee extension in a seated position. This method was consistent throughout this thesis and is the same method used previously by others (Perchthaler, Horstmann, and Grau, 2013; Roelants et al., 2006). However, some studies have normalised EMG data obtained during a WBV condition to a non-WBV condition but using the same test position (Marín and Hazell, 2014; Ritzmann, Gollhofer, and Kramer, 2013). In these studies, the EMG signals normalised to a non-WBV condition were found to be higher than the EMG signals normalised to MVC values. Therefore, the effects of these normalisation methods may reflect the evaluation of the effectiveness of exercises by underestimating or overestimating the EMG values. The conclusions drawn from this thesis may be affected by the selected normalisation method, which is performed to the highest MVC value of knee extension in the open kinetic chain. There appears to be no clear comparison between the two methods (normalised to highest MVC or normalised to non-WBV condition) in the literature concerning WBV specifically. Therefore, the current literature shows inconsistency in EMG normalisation approaches during exercises with WBV stimuli. Conducting a comparison between the two types of normalisations is necessary to develop a consistent normalisation process that can be used across studies of WBV and EMG.

8.4 Exercises involving whole-body vibration stimuli on vastus medialis muscle activity

There is extensive evidence in the literature that targeted exercise can strengthen individual muscles (Chang et al., 2014; Kang et al., 2017; Parekh and Gaur, 2015). However, the evidence regarding the effect of exercises on VM muscle activity is not as consistent (Alrshood et al., 2017). This can be explained by the difficulty of isolating the VM muscle during strengthening exercises, and therefore exercises should target the quadriceps muscle without specifically targeting the VM muscle (Smith et al., 2009). However, the motor unit of muscle sub-sections can be recruited effectively using biofeedback exercise with high-density EMG (Martinez-Valdes et al., 2016; Del Vecchio et al., 2020). Moreover, the role of the optimal knee-flexion angle in an activated VM muscle was investigated in previous literature, and it was found to be between 60° and 90° (Jaberzadeh, Yeo, and Zoghi, 2016; Kang et al., 2017). Throughout this thesis, a consistent knee-flexion angle of 65° was selected. Although the selected knee angle during WBV stimuli was based on the angle used in previous literature (Ritzmann, Gollhofer, and Kramer, 2013), no consistent knee angle was used in previous literature, particularly with regard to the process of maintaining the required knee-flexion angle during vibration stimuli. Therefore, this variable must be considered when conducting similar research, and it requires further investigation to ensure a consistent approach across studies and during investigation of exercises targeting VM neuromuscular activity for rehabilitation programmes in clinical populations.

Although this thesis found no difference found in maximum normalised amplitude of dominant VM muscle activity in in static double-leg squat exercises alone compared to that combined with WBV stimuli and Thera-Band in healthy individuals, a previous study conducted by Roelants et al. (2006) found that a single-leg squat, which was not assessed in this thesis, increased VM muscle activity during WBV stimuli, in comparison to a double-leg squat. Although that study used the

same WBV platform type as that used in this thesis (vertical platform), a fixed WBV frequency of 30 Hz was used, which differs from this thesis, which identified the individualised WBV frequency for each individual. Therefore, further research is warranted to evaluate the effect of test positions of the double-leg squat exercise, in comparison to the single-leg squat exercise, on the effectiveness of WBV stimuli for neuromuscular activity. Also, the platform types, which can affect the comparison between exercises' effectiveness due to the differences in platform characteristics, should be investigated during single and double-leg squat exercises performed by healthy individuals.

Targeted exercise forms a core component of muscle strength rehabilitation programmes (Peterson et al., 2010). The effect of VM muscle exercises has been evaluated in both healthy and clinical populations (Adel et al., 2019; Bolgla, Shaffer, and Malone, 2008; Hertel et al., 2004; Hyong and Ho, 2013; Sykes and Wong, 2003; Tang et al., 2001). The studies conducted by Krol et al. (2011) and Roelants et al. (2006) found a significant increase in VM muscle activity in healthy individuals during static squat exercises with acute WBV stimuli compared to standing or static squatting positions without WBV stimuli. However, Chapter 6 demonstrated that healthy individuals performing exercises with WBV stimuli on maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity were found to experience similar effects to squatting without WBV stimuli. This conflict can be explained by the differences in exposure time or normalisation methods, as discussed before in Chapters 6 (healthy individuals) and 7 (clinical population). Therefore, the effect of these exercises should also be further evaluated in clinical populations characterised by VM muscle weakness. Moreover, the literature lacks consensus for evaluation of the effectiveness of WBV stimuli on muscle weakness in asymptomatic individuals and clinical populations with regard to factors such as optimal exposure time and the patient's exposure tolerance depending on pain level

and body position. Therefore, the effectiveness of various WBV parameter outputs on acute VM muscle activity with regard to the effect of EMG filters or normalisation methods needs to be investigated in healthy individuals. Also, WBV stimulation warrants comparison with strengthening interventions/exercises used for healthy individuals and clinical populations.

8.5 Individualised frequency and the vastus medialis muscle

Individualised WBV stimuli were introduced by Cardinale and Lim (2003), who recommended the importance of using an individual frequency for specific muscles and individuals to improve the effectiveness of neuromuscular performance. Di Giminiani et al. (2015) determined the presence of an individualised stimuli between 20 and 55 Hz, at increments of 5 Hz on VL muscle activity of healthy individuals during a static squat position. Another study conducted by Borges et al. (2017) evaluated the individualised WBV stimuli between frequencies of 30 and 50 Hz only on VL muscle activity during static squats and found no differences between these frequencies, suggesting that an individualised frequency did not exist. Due to the uncertainty in the presence of an individualised frequency, the individualised WBV stimuli have been investigated in healthy individuals for maximum normalised amplitude of VM neuromuscular activity of the dominant limb during double-leg squats for 30 sec, with no differences found between frequencies of 30, 35, 40 and 50 Hz, as described in Chapter 5. The study on individualised WBV stimuli in Chapter 5 can be regarded as the first of its kind, as it explored the individualised WBV frequencies by maximum normalised amplitude of VM neuromuscular activity of the dominant limb in healthy individuals. However, the evaluated inter-day reliability (consistency) of the individualised frequency in 26 healthy participants resulted in only six participants showing a consistency in the frequency which yielded the highest EMG output (and thereby individualised frequency) across the two sessions (two males and four females). The evaluated individualised frequency parameter

can be affected by different variables such as muscle volume, muscle location/distance from the WBV platform (Di Giminiani et al., 2010) and consistency in maintaining the required posture between participants (Di Giminiani et al., 2013; Perchthaler, Horstmann, and Grau, 2013b). Due to the divergent findings regarding whether an individualised WBV frequency is indeed present, further investigations in this area are warranted.

WBV stimuli can increase the human body's muscle activity, which may explain the existence of individualised WBV frequencies on individual muscles depending on muscles location, size or volume, and their fibre characteristics (Di Giminiani et al., 2015; Roelants et al., 2006). The individualised WBV stimuli possibly appeared to be obtained on more than one frequency (multiple frequencies), rather than a specific frequency in healthy individuals as seen in Chapter 5; no significant difference was found between frequencies of 30, 35, 40 and 50 Hz in dominant VM neuromuscular activity during a static squat. However, this result contradicts the results by Giminiani et al. (2009), who suggested that each individual's muscles can be optimally stimulated by a specific WBV frequency (individualised frequency to the individual and muscle). This apparent discrepancy can be explained by the fact that the concept of evaluating the individualised WBV stimuli scientifically is relatively new and has only been investigated for specific muscles, and thus, cannot be generalised. Therefore, this new research area requires further investigation regarding body positions, WBV frequencies, muscle volume and distance from the WBV stimulus.

8.6 Vastus medialis neuromuscular activity and Patellofemoral pain syndrome

A lack of consensus on exercises targeting VM neuromuscular activity in PFPS populations has necessitated a systematic review and meta-analysis to evaluate the effect of various squat exercises on VM neuromuscular activity in patients with PFPS (Chapter 2). The findings from the meta-

analysis illustrated the possible roles that different squat exercises, including WBV stimuli in healthy individuals and resisted hip adduction in individuals with PFPS, can have on VM muscle activity. These findings illustrated that the decrease in VM muscle activity can be addressed by various squat exercises in healthy and PFPS populations. Although VM muscle weakness may be linked to the imbalance in VM/VL, it cannot be generalised to PFPS populations. The recent classification of PFPS considered the weakness of the quadriceps muscle as the main risk factor for PFPS regardless of the VM:VL imbalance (Papadopoulos, Stasinopoulos, and Ganchev, 2015; Willy et al., 2019). Also, muscle weakness which related to the lower limbs such as hamstring muscles weakness and all other muscles surrounding the knee joint, can be linked to PFPS (Willy et al., 2019). Therefore, the role of VM muscle activity in PFPS still requires further investigation, particularly on the effectiveness of PFPS treatment. Also, the systematic review and meta-analysis on the effects of various squat exercises on VM muscle activity in this thesis were carried out on only 286 participants across 12 studies (Chapter 2). The main reason for that is the nature of the topic which was very precise and narrow, thus, the role of VM muscle activity in PFPS populations requires further investigation. Previous literature that have evaluated exercises targeting VM muscle activity in the two populations selected for this study is also limited in number. As a result, further research in both populations is needed.

A delay in activation of the VM can be related to the imbalance in the VM:VL ratio. This imbalance may cause lateral tracking of the patella, which has been linked to PFPS as it causes knee pain (Gawda et al., 2019). Chapters 6 and 7 described the VM:VL ratio during various squat exercises in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS, respectively. However, the findings of these two chapters cannot be compared because of the inconsistency in the WBV frequency. In Chapter 5, the WBV stimulus for each participant was evaluated between the frequencies 30, 35,

40 and 50 Hz, and selected according to the highest frequency effect on VM muscle activity of the dominant limb, whereas in Chapter 7, a fixed frequency of 40 Hz was used for all participants. A frequency ranged between 35 Hz to 40 Hz is recommended for use in neuromuscular performance in individuals with PFPS (Corum et al., 2018). Although Chapter 5 revealed no difference between the frequencies 30, 35, 40 and 50 Hz in healthy individuals, this same evaluation needs to be conducted on the PFPS clinical population, as the latter may respond differently due to the VM muscle delay compared to the healthy population. In Chapter 7, the VM:VL ratio was found greater than 1 in a squatting exercise with WBV and the squatting exercise alone as compared to squatting with resisted hip adduction and squatting with resisted hip adduction and WBV. Therefore, further evaluation is needed to determine the effect of frequencies on the VM:VL ratio during the evaluation of exercise effectiveness in individuals with PFPS.

Quadriceps muscle strength may help in tailoring treatment plans for each individual patient (Dixit et al., 2007; Papadopoulos, Stasinopoulos, and Ganchev, 2015). Investigations on the role of VM strengthening exercises in individuals with PFPS have reported that weakness can be addressed by resisted hip adduction exercises; however, excessive hip adduction, which may damage knee-joint cartilage, should be avoided (Coqueiro et al., 2005; Vora et al., 2017). Commonly, CKC exercises illustrated a significant increase in VM muscle activity in individuals with PFPS compared to OKC exercises (Coqueiro et al., 2005; Chang, Huang, and Lai, 2015). However, the findings from the current thesis, which investigated the effect of various CKC exercises only targeting VM muscle activity in individuals with PFPS without comparison to OKC exercises, and found no differences between the four evaluated exercises (Chapter 7). The study conducted in this thesis applied band-pass and band-stop EMG filters, while Coqueiro et al. (2005) and Chang, Huang, and Lai (2015) applied the band-pass filter only, which can lead to overestimation of EMG signals. Therefore,

further research is required to investigate the effect of various EMG filters during CKC exercises on VM muscle activity during tailored exercise programmes for individuals with PFPS.

8.7 Whole-Body vibration stimuli exercise and Patellofemoral pain syndrome

WBV stimuli have been introduced for improving human performance and muscle strength in clinical populations, although it is a new area and needs further investigation. Individuals with PFPS performed home exercises combined with WBV stimuli for eight weeks and were compared to a group that performed home exercises only (Corum et al., 2018). The WBV stimuli were found to be effective in decreasing the pain level and improving the performance of functional tasks, as well as increasing the quadriceps/hamstring ratio, which was obtained by subjective measures (physical activity questionnaires), and isokinetic muscle strength (Corum et al., 2018). However, the data presented in Chapter 7, which focused on measuring VM muscle activity by EMG signals in individuals with PFPS, found no difference in the effect of acute WBV stimuli on maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity compared to squatting alone, squatting with resisted hip adduction and squatting with WBV stimuli and resisted hip adduction. The data in Chapter 7 offered a new perspective regarding exercise including WBV stimuli in specific populations like those with PFPS, based on objective outcome measures like EMG signals. The effectiveness of WBV platform parameters in individuals with PFPS needs to be highlighted. Moreover, the optimal position (e.g. squat) for individuals with PFPS during WBV stimuli should be investigated further, while the study of the effectiveness of WBV stimuli compared to other exercise interventions in individuals with PFPS should also be considered.

Yañez-Álvarez et al. (2020) evaluated the effect of WBV stimuli with frequency of 40 Hz during strengthening exercises in individuals with PFPS for four weeks on pain Scale (VAS) and knee

flexion and extension range of motion (ROM) compared to control group who performed the same strengthening exercises of 12 sessions but without WBV stimuli. In that study, pain level significantly decreased and knee flexion ROM significantly increased in the group performed the WBV exercises compared to the control group (Yañez-Álvarez et al., 2020). However, pain level after each exercise has not been assessed as the current thesis investigated the neuromuscular activity during various squat exercises.

The effect of exercises on the VM:VL ratio in individuals with PFPS is widely investigated in the literature (Miller, Sedory, and Croce, 1997; Kim and Song, 2012), but the VM:VL ratio during the introduction of WBV stimuli was not evaluated in Corum et al. (2018) or other studies. The study reported in Chapter 7 is, therefore, the first, to the author's knowledge, to evaluate the effect of acute WBV stimuli on the VM:VL ratio in individuals with PFPS, finding no significant effect compared to squatting exercises alone. However, the VM:VL ratio differed significantly from 1 during squatting alone and squatting with WBV stimuli. Squat with WBV stimulus was not a superior exercise compared to squat exercise alone, therefore squatting exercises alone or with WBV stimuli can be used interchangeably when evaluating the VM:VL ratio. Considering that an imbalance between the VM and VL muscles may not be present in all individuals with PFPS (Santos et al., 2008, Giles et al., 2015), the VM:VL ratio in this population should decide upon in the inclusion criteria before deciding which participants to include, thus reflecting the required population with imbalance in VM/VL ratio. Moreover, further research is warranted to shed light on the role of WBV stimuli in patients with PFPS who have muscle imbalance in the quadriceps or a VM:VL imbalance. Also, evaluation the combined hip and knee exercises appears to be focused on the patient's symptoms. Therefore, further investigation should consider the effect of

combined exercises on the imbalance in the VM:VL ratio if the physical examination shows imbalance in the quadriceps muscles.

The 2016 and 2018 PFPS consensus recommended combined hip and knee motor control exercises (Crossley et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2018). The literature on this recommendation is focused on combined interventions rather than on combined exercises. A combined intervention was assessed by Argut et al. (2017), who investigated the effect of electrical stimulation combined with strength exercises for the quadriceps muscle as compared to exercises alone for six weeks. This investigation was conducted using an isokinetic dynamometer and the Kujala and Lysholm scores to assess functional activity in individuals with PFPS compared to a group that performed exercises alone. Argut et al.'s (2017) study found no differences between the groups. However, Şahin et al. (2016) conducted a study on individuals with PFPS by comparing combined hip and knee exercises to knee exercises alone. Their study evaluated isokinetic muscle strength during hip and knee movement, and determined pain levels using the VAS scale; subsequently, a function test was carried out with a single-leg squat test and a step-down test. The combined hip and knee exercises significantly improved patients' pain and function test results compared to knee exercises alone (Şahin et al., 2016). These combined exercises were evaluated after a 12-week exercise programme. The previous studies conducted with training programmes, however this thesis focused on the effect of acute exercises only. Therefore, additional research is required to effectively evaluate both acute and training programme effects, and enable comparisons between findings.

8.8 Resisted hip adduction exercise and Patellofemoral pain syndrome

There are conflicting reports in the literature on the effect of hip adduction exercises in PFPS rehabilitation programmes (Jang et al., 2013; Miao et al., 2015; Yen et al., 2009). However, recent recommendations for PFPS rehabilitation suggests that treatment programmes should be tailored according to the patient's symptoms and limitations (Petersen, Rembitzki, and Liebau, 2017). In this thesis, resisted hip adduction was found to have the same acute effect on maximum normalised amplitude of VM neuromuscular activity during a static squat in individuals with PFPS when compared to squats alone, squats with 40 Hz WBV stimuli, and squats with resisted hip adduction and 40 Hz WBV stimuli (see Chapter 7).

Resisted hip adduction exercises in PFPS populations can take different forms, including various tools and positions (Chang, Huang, and Lai, 2015; Coqueiro et al., 2005; Meira and Brumitt, 2011). In Chapter 2, the systematic review illustrated an increase in VM muscle activity during squatting with resisted hip adduction introduced by different tools compared to squatting alone in individuals with PFPS. However, Chapter 7 describes the first study that evaluated the combined acute effect of resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli on maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity in individuals with PFPS; no difference was found when compared to squatting without WBV. The effect of exercise on reducing patient's pain level is a core component for evaluating the exercise effectiveness. Although participant's pain level was evaluated using the VAS scale on each performed exercise including resisted hip adduction exercise and WBV stimuli during evaluation of VM muscle activity was not assessed in this thesis, however, in Chapter 7, no significant correlation found between the participant's pain level which evaluated at the start of experiment, and the maximum normalised amplitude of VM and VL muscle activities for the symptomatic limb. Thus, further studies should assess additional parameters such as pain when

evaluating the effect of resisted hip adduction exercises on acute maximum normalised amplitude of VM EMG signals. Finally, the literature lacks adequate evidence on the effect of different tools and possible positions used to perform resisted hip adduction exercise.

8.9 Further recommendations

WBV introduces additional EMG artefacts or noise, which can lead to overestimation of the EMG signals, and thereby possibly affecting the evaluation of exercises with WBV stimuli. Therefore, the use of band-pass and band-stop filters is required during the evaluation of the effect of exercises with WBV stimuli on neuromuscular activity by EMG response. Selection of a suitable MVC position during normalisation of EMG signals is also recommended, as this also can reflect the evaluation of the effectiveness of exercise with WBV stimuli. Further research is recommended to define the optimal MVC position, whether for OKC or CKC exercises, for normalisation of EMG signals during exercise with WBV stimuli.

Although this thesis supports the proposition that the Trigno Avanti Delsys EMG system is a reliable piece of equipment for use during the application of WBV stimuli by the VibraMachine platform, the reliability of individualised WBV stimuli (evaluated by EMG signals) should be investigated in future research before being used in rehabilitation programmes. This evaluation may highlight the role of individualised WBV stimuli on muscle activity during exercise programmes. Also, further research should focus on evaluating WBV platform outputs in relation to clinical populations before being used in research to indicate further possible use in clinical settings. Although this thesis recommended that WBV frequencies of 30, 35, 40 and 50 Hz for the VibraMachine platform during squat exercises can be used to increase the maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity in healthy individuals, further investigation of these frequencies

is required in clinical populations such as individuals with PFPS. This thesis also recommends that individuals with PFPS use WBV stimuli during static squats as an alternative to squat exercises alone, squats with resisted hip adduction, and a combination of squat, resisted hip adduction and WBV stimuli. However, these exercises were assessed only for individuals with PFPS, without a control group of healthy individuals, and a fixed WBV frequency of 40 Hz was used. Although, no evidence found for the presence of an individualised frequency in healthy individuals (Chapter 5), the individualised frequencies for individuals with PFPS require further investigation and should be compared to healthy individuals with the same demographic data. Also, the subjective experience of pain after each exercise was not evaluated, and this research gap warrants further investigation. Additionally, subjective evaluation of the comfort of individuals with PFPS during each exercise is warranted as only the subjective evaluation of the comfort at the end of experiment protocol was evaluated in healthy individuals (Chapter 6). Although in Chapter 7, only the acute effects of exercises as intervention were evaluated, further evaluation is required for the long-term effects of this protocol in individuals with PFPS.

Finally, the muscle activation time during WBV stimuli was difficult to evaluate. To calculate activation time during exercise, the starting position should be a static stand on the WBV platform during WBV stimuli, which is not recommended when evaluating WBV stimuli, and therefore the squatting position is used. This is because a squat position indicates that muscle activity can be activated before the exercises during which the WBV stimuli are applied and evaluated. Therefore, the muscle's force via RMS values was calculated instead, and further methods should be developed to investigate the muscle activation time during WBV stimuli.

8.10 Practical applications

This thesis illustrated the acute application of WBV stimuli in healthy individuals and individuals with PFPS. The WBV platform type should be selected based on the WBV characteristics. Therefore, in this thesis, vertical platforms are recommended for exercises aiming to induce increased muscle activity. Also, the findings of the thesis showed that the use of 30, 35, 40 and 50 Hz frequencies on maximum normalised amplitude of VM muscle activity for the dominant leg of healthy individuals illustrated no significant differences during the static squat position, and there was no evidence supporting the presence of optimal frequency from inter-day comparisons. Therefore, any of the frequencies tested in this thesis can produce a similar effect on VM EMG activity. As a result, an individual has the option to select the most comfortable frequency with the same results/effectiveness. Another point to be considered by clinicians and individuals when performing exercises with WBV stimuli is that the WBV platform may not produce the values specified by the manufacturers. Also, squat exercises involving WBV stimuli on VM muscle activity can be used as an alternative to squatting alone in individuals who have difficulty maintaining that position, as both have the same effect. Moreover, resisted hip adduction during squats can be used to increase muscle activity with a similar effect to the combined exercise of resisted hip adduction using a green Thera-Band and WBV stimuli during squats. Therefore, an individual can select the most comfortable exercise with the same results/effectiveness.

Finally, this thesis investigated two main activities of the quadriceps during squat exercises. However, the effect of muscle volume in response to individualised/optimal frequency needs further investigation in healthy individuals and clinical populations. This may have implications for the effect of WBV stimuli on muscle strength.

8.11 Conclusion

The present thesis aimed to investigate the validity and reliability of WBV platforms and Delsys EMG system during static double-leg squats assessed in healthy individuals. The reliability and validity of Vibe plate and VibraMachine platform outputs parameters; frequency, acceleration and peak to peak displacement, provided a hypothesis regarding the effectiveness of different vertical WBV platforms which may reflect on the involvement of WBV stimuli in individual's treatment protocols. Also, the neuromuscular activity has been found a reliable outcome measure to evaluate the output of WBV stimuli during static squat exercise in healthy individuals.

Following that, this thesis aimed to evaluate the effect of squat exercise with Thera-Band and WBV stimuli on neuromuscular activity and found squat exercises with Thera-Band and WBV can be alternately on muscle activity with no differences. Therefore, applying WBV stimuli and Thera-Band during squatting exercises can be used alternately to increase the neuromuscular activity amongst healthy individuals and a clinical population. The present thesis found that VM/VL ratio in symptomatic limb in individuals with PFPS significantly greater than the normal VM/VL ratio in squatting exercise alone and squatting with WBV stimuli exercise, therefore the both exercises can be used alternately with the same effect to identify the VM/VL ratio in individuals with PFPS. However, further research is essential to indicate the role of resistance exercises including WBV stimuli and Thera-Band in individual's treatment protocols.

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Chapter 10

Appendices

Appendix 1. Table of included studies only in Chapter 2 (EMG= electromyography, VMO=Vastus Medialis Oblique, VL= Vastus Lateralis, GM= Gastrocnemius, RF= Rectus femoris, RA= rectus abdominis, MF= multifidus, WBV= Whole Body Vibration, HS= high squat, LS= low squat, OL= One leg squat, DS-HA= double leg squat with hip adduction, DS= double leg squat).

Study	Sample size (Age; Mean \pm SD) years	Intervention Group	Control Group	Outcomes measures	Main results
Krol K. et al. 2011 (healthy)	Total 29 female healthy participants: (21.8 \pm 1.2)	Total of 8 trails. The 1 st , 2nd trail without WBV. Remaining 6 trails (20Hz, 40 Hz, and 60Hz) (2 and 4 mm.)	Trail 1 used as controlled trail	EMG of VMO and VL	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. VL and VM EMG signal higher with WBV than non WBV. 2. EMG activity of VM +VL highest in 60 HZ+ 4mm.
Marín & Hazell, 2014 (healthy)	Total 28 healthy participant: (21.7 \pm 1.3) years; Gender (male: female) (23:5)	The 4 different tests are: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- No vibration stable surface 2- No vibration unstable surface 3- 30Hz WBV with unstable surface 4- 50Hz WBV with unstable surface. 	1 st condition (stable surface with 0Hz) can counted as control group.	EMG of GM, VMO, VL, RA and MF	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. VM muscle highest in unstable surface with 30 Hz 2. VM/VL ratio decrease in unstable surface than stable surface.

Roelants et al, 2006 (healthy)	Total 15 healthy participants: (21.2±0.8)	3 isometric exercise on WBV platform: 1. HS→ knee angle 125°, hip angle 140° 2. 2. LS→ knee and hip angle 90° 3. OL→ knee angle 125°+ hip angle 140°.	Static squat without WBV can be counted as the control group.	EMG of VM, VL and RF	1. WBV group has higher mm activation than control. During WBV, mm activity varied between 12.6 and 82.4% of MVC values.
Hertel et al., 2004	Total of 8 healthy participants: 24±2.5 Gender (male: female) (5:3)	Measuring EMG in squat on 1. Straight knee extension 2. Knee extension with hip adduction. 3. Knee extension with hip abduction.	Self-controlled group, squat with straight knee extension as control intervention.	EMG of VM, VL, Gluteus medius and VM/VL ratio	1. VM muscle has higher activity in straight knee extension than knee extension with hip adduction or hip abduction.
Saeterbakken and Fimland, 2013	Total 15 healthy participants: (23.3±2.7)	Measuring EMG in squat on 1. stable surface 2. power board 3. BOSU ball 4. Balance cone	Self-controlled group, can count the squat on the stable surface as control intervention	EMG of VM, VL, RF, BF, Soleus, Erector Spinae, Oblique external and Rectus abdominis	1. VMO activity in stable surface higher than power board, BOSU ball and balance cone.

Park et al., 2015 (healthy)	Total 25 healthy participants: (25.19±2.48)	The 4 conditions defined as: 1. Stable ground surface with vision allowed (SGS) 2. Unstable ground surface (UGS) with vision allowed. 3. SGS with vision blocked 4. UGS with vision blocked.	The control condition can be counted as the stable surface and with vision allowed.	EMG of VM and VL	1. When vision is blocked, the VMO activity was significantly different on both ground surface (p< 0.05).
Lee et al., 2016 (healthy)	Total 20 female healthy: (21.5±1.10)	4 Groups: 1. Conventional squat (knees at 90°) 2. Squatting with a ball 3. Squatting with a wedge (elastic band above the left knee to 45°)	The conventional squat counted as control group.	EMG of VM and VL activity + VMO: VL ratio.	1. VMO: Squat with wedge and conventional > with gym ball and elastic band 2. VL: no differences in VL EMG in all intervention
Miao et al., 2015 (healthy + PFPS)	Total 60 participants. 30 PFPS, 30 control healthy • PFPS: (31.3±6.87) • Healthy: (28.70±5.84)	DS-HA done with a green Thera-Band done in PFPS and Healthy.	DS performed with knee flexed.	EMG VL and VMO	1. In DS-HA the time domain VMO higher than VL 2. No difference in VL in DS + DS-HA.
Hyong and Ho, 2013 (healthy)	14 healthy participants: mean age: (21.4)	Unstable surface: 40×47×7 cm foam pads	The hard surface is the control intervention.	EMG VM, VL & MO/VL ratio	1. The VMO activity highest on the rubber air disc. The VMO/VL ratio highest on the rubber air disc.

	Gender (male: female) (5:9)	Knee joint angle controlled by goniometer. Maintain knee joint flexion angle of 60°.			
Coqueiro et al., 2005 (healthy+ PFPS)	Total 20 participants. 10 sedentary, 10 healthy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PFPS:(23.2±2.65) Gender (male: female) (16:14) healthy: (21.8±2.52) gender (male: female) (14:16) 	The DLSS-HA: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Descend to 45° knee flexion 2- Hold and perform a hip add. for 6 s 3- Ascend to the initial position. 	DLSS was Descend to 45° knee flexion <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Hold for 6 s. 2- Ascend to the initial position. 	EMG VMO and VL	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. VMO and VL activity higher in DLSS-HA than DLSS in both groups. 2. VL activity higher than MVO in DLSS on in PFPS group.
Sain e. Irish et al, 2010 (healthy)	Total 22 participants. (11 men, 11 women, age = 25.06 6 4.67)	Performed 2 exercises t 45°: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Squatting with isometric resisted hip adduction. 2- Lunge exercise. 	Performed open kinetic chain knee extension.	EMG VM, VL and Ratio VM:VL.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lunge exercise can be used in restoring preferential VMO:VL ratio. 2. Isometric resisted hip adduction can be used in strengthening VMO.
Parekh and Gaur, 2015 (healthy)	30 healthy participants.	Squatting 60° on: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Foam surface. 2- Rubber disc. 	Squatting 60° on concrete floor.	EMG VM.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rubber surface increase VMO muscle activity.

Appendix 2. Leaflet used throughout recruitment in healthy individuals.

Participant needed..

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND
UWS

I am looking for **volunteers** to take part in my research investigating **Quadriceps muscles activity** during **squatting & whole body vibration**.

Are you:

- 18 years or older.
- Healthy and free of lower limb injury.
- Wanting to experience whole body vibration!
- Find out what setting of vibration is the best for you.

What you will be asked to do:

- Attend the UWS Biomechanics Lab 3 times for a maximum of 45 minutes.

If you are interesting please contact

[Redacted contact information]

Appendix 3. Ethical approval obtained from the UWS School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee for the studies described in Chapters 4 – 6.

25/10/2018

Dear Dalal Alqaseer,

Your application 1090: Novel Knee Rehabilitation Techniques to increase the timing activation of the Vastus Medialis muscle among healthy people , submission 4338, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 4. Information Sheet for Chapter 4 – 6

Project title: Novel Knee Rehabilitation Exercises to evaluate and compare the acute neuromuscular activity of the Vastus Medialis muscle during squatting among healthy individuals.

Who am I?

My name is Dalal ALQaseer and I am a researcher at UWS. You are invited to participate in a study that will be a part of the PhD thesis I am currently undertaking. As a participant, you have the right to know the purpose of this study and to know more information about it before deciding whether to participate or not. Please take your time to read this sheet and decide if you want to participate or not. You are most welcome to ask any further questions.

Why have I been asked to take apart?

National Health Service (NHS) consumed 4.7£ billion in 2013/14 on musculoskeletal conditions which counted as the 3rd largest area of spending in NHS program. Any dysfunction, pain or injury in knee joint will affect the body mechanism and weight shifting in activity daily living. One of the possible causes of knee injury or pain is the imbalance in muscle activity in two of the thigh muscles. These two muscles named as vastus Medialis (VM) and vastus Lateralis (VL). The imbalance between the thigh muscles is one of the causes of patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS). There are several strengthening exercises used to address the imbalance. The Whole body vibration (WBV) and resistance hip exercise in squatting separately, has been shown to have a slight positive effect on increasing the activation of VM muscle in healthy; however, the effect of combing all of these exercises has not been tested on healthy. Therefore, this study will evaluate and compare the VM muscle activation in the following exercises:

- 1- Squatting on the ground.
- 2- Squatting with resistance hip exercises via elastic band.
- 3- Squatting on WBV platform.
- 4- Squatting on WBV platform with resistance hip exercise via elastic band.

What would I have to do?

If you agree to take part in this study, appointments will be made with a convenient time for you. You will attend three appointments in a laboratory at the University of the West of Scotland. In sessions one and two, you will experience 1) the squatting with 5 different frequencies (0 Hz, 30 Hz, 35 Hz, 40 Hz and 50 Hz) on WBV platform. 2) EMG sensor electrodes. In the third session, you will perform the squatting in 4 different conditions under the selected individualised frequency from the two sessions. In all sessions, the order will be conducted randomly. Upon arrival on the experiment day as part of the experiment preparation, the participant will be asked to:

- 1- Wear short so that your lower legs are exposed.
- 2- Wear light socks.
- 3- A small area close to the knee will be shaved and wiped with an alcohol wipe.

Each participant will take in total 45 min for the full procedure in each session. The assessments should not be associated with any pain or discomfort. If you feel uncomfortable during the experiment, you are free to withdraw. All the relevant information regarding the experiment will

be explained on the experiment days; consent form will be signed. Height and weight will be collected first, and then you will perform cycling for 5 min and 2 min of exercises (10 Rep. of squat and knee to chest exercises as a warm up). The electrode sensors will be placed on your skin (thigh area; VM, VL muscles) to measure iMVC, goniometer will be used around the knee to measure the knee angle. You will receive each of the four exercise in a random order. Each exercise will last 30 s. and the activity of muscles in your thigh (VM, VL muscles) will be measured. You will be given a 2 min. recovery between exercises. Cool down will be performed with stretching the thigh muscles and that will be the end of the test.

Do I have to take a part?

Your participation in this study is voluntary and you can decide to opt out of the study at any time without any consequences. If you have any further questions, I will be glad to answer them, please find my email at the end of this participant sheet

What are the possible risks of taking part?

Like all modalities, The WBV platform can be harmful if used incorrectly. However, you will be given a clear instruction of how to stand on the platform. A member of staff will be supervising the research. All participants are free to withdraw their participation at any time throughout the study without any justification required and warm up given will reduce risk of injury.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The result of this study may help us to improve knee rehabilitation programs. Moreover, once written-up and critically reviewed as part of the PhD thesis, the findings will be available to researchers, healthcare professionals and the public to further the research knowledge. However, it will not be possible to identify you from any of these reports or publications.

Will my participation be confidential?

All data collected will remain confidential. Your name will be made anonymous. All information relating to the study will be kept in locked cabinet in UWS with access for the researcher and the supervisor only. Electronic data collected will be stored on an encrypted laptop / USB stick.

What if I have any concerns?

If you would like any further information before participating, please do not hesitate to contact the researcher using the below contact details.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

All results of this study will attempt to answer the proposed research question. You will be able to obtain a copy of your results on request following the write up of this paper.

What happens next?

If after reading this information sheet, you are interested in participating in the study, please email Dalal ALQaseer, who will respond to offer you a time slot for data collection.

Thank you for taking the time to read this participant information sheet.

Contact for further information

Name: Dalal ALQaseer (PhD student at School of Health and Life Sciences, UWS)

E-mail: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Director of Study:

Dr. Mark Sanderson (Exercise Science Lecture, Chartered Physiotherapy)

Institute of Clinical Exercise and Health Science School of Health and Life Sciences.

University of the West of Scotland,

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Appendix 5. Consent Form for Chapter 4 – 6

Study Number:

Participant Identification Number:

Title of Project: Novel Knee Rehabilitation Exercises to evaluate and compare the acute neuromuscular activity of the Vastus Medialis muscle during squatting among healthy individuals.

Name of Researcher: Dalal ALQaseer

Please initial in box

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated _____ (version _____) for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason. If I do not participate in this project it will not affect my place on the programme.
3. I understand that individuals from University of the West of Scotland or regulatory authorities may look at the anonymised data collected during the above study. I give my permission for this.
4. I Understand that the findings of the above study may be presented at conferences or published in Journals, but my data will be anonymised and will not be possible to identify myself. I give my permission for this.
5. I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of person taking consent (if different from researcher):

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Date:

Appendix 6. Leaflet used throughout recruitment in individuals with PFPS.

<p>Have you been diagnosed with Patellofemoral pain? syndrome?</p>	<p>UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST of SCOTLAND UWS</p>
<p>Would you like to take part in a study investigating the effects of the whole body vibration platform on thigh muscle activity?</p>	
<p>We are looking for participants who</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">→ Are 18 years or older.→ Have pain in the front of the knee in the last 3 months.* The study will involve 1 visit to the UWS Lanarkshire Campus, Hamilton.	
<p>If you are interested please contact [REDACTED]</p>	

Appendix 7. Ethical approval obtained from the UWS School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee study described in Chapter 7.

17/05/2019

Dear Dalal Alqiseer,

Your application 6348: Evaluate and compare the effect of novel knee rehabilitation exercises during squatting on acute VM neuromuscular activation in PFPS populations., submission 6623, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 8. Information Sheet for Chapter 7

project title: an evaluation and comparison the effect of novel knee rehabilitation exercises during squatting on acute vastus medialis neuromuscular activity in patellofemoral pain syndrome populations.

Who am I?

My name is Dalal ALQaseer and I am a researcher at UWS. You are invited to participate in a study that will be a part of the PhD thesis I am currently undertaking. UWS is organizing and funding this research. As a participant, you have the right to know the purpose of this study and to know more information about it before deciding whether to participate or not. Please take your time to read this leaflet and decide if you want to participate or not. You are most welcome to ask any further questions.

Why have I been asked to take apart?

In the United Kingdom, pain in the front of the knee, also known as Patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS) is very common; about 23% of the general population can experience this condition. One of the possible causes of this type of knee pain is the imbalance in muscle activity in two parts of the main thigh muscle. Evidence suggests that strengthening exercises targeting this muscle can address the imbalance. Combining interventions may have a further positive result on improving this muscle imbalance. For example, both whole body vibration (WBV) and resisted hip adduction exercise in squatting have separately been shown to be effective in people without PFPS, however, the effect of WBV alone or combing WBV and resisted hip adduction has not been tested in PFPS populations. Therefore, this study will evaluate thigh muscle activity in PFPS populations during 1) squatting only 2) squatting with resisted hip adduction 3) squatting on the WBV platform 4) squatting on the WBV platform with resisted hip adduction.

What would I have to do?

If you agree to take part in this study, appointment will be made at a convenient time for you. You will attend the appointment at University of the West of Scotland laboratory. You will be asked to bring shorts and trainers.

Appointment will take 40-50 minutes. The session should not cause any pain or discomfort, however if you feel pain or discomfort during the experiment, you are free to withdraw. When you attend your appointment, you will be asked to sign a consent form. Your height and weight will be measured, and you will then complete a warm-up on the static bike for 5 minutes, followed by performing 10 squats. Then two electromyography sensors will be placed on each thigh using sticky tape. After 3 repetitions of resisted knee extension each both legs, you will be asked to perform a 20 second squat on the WBV platform at 4 different exercises involving WBV and resisted hip adduction on both legs. You will have a rest of 2 minutes in between each squat. All exercises will be randomized.

A cool down will be performed with stretching the thigh muscles at the session and short questionnaire will be completed.

Do I have to take a part?

Your participation in this study is voluntary and you can decide to opt out of the study at any time without any consequences. If you do not participate in this study, it will not affect your treatment at the clinic in any way. If you have any further questions, I will be glad to answer them. Please find my email at the end of this participant sheet.

What are the possible risks of taking part?

Like all modalities, the WBV platform can be harmful if used incorrectly. However, you will be given clear verbal instructions from the researcher on how to stand on the platform. You will be able to give the researcher verbal feedback if you experience any pain or discomfort during the exercises. You are free to withdraw at any time throughout the study without any justification required.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The result of this study may help us to improve knee rehabilitation programs. Moreover, once written-up and critically reviewed as part of the PhD thesis, the findings will be available to researchers, healthcare professionals and the public through written reports, online library catalogues, conference presentations and journal publications. It will not be possible to identify you or your personal details from any of these reports or publications.

Will my participation be confidential?

All data collected will remain confidential. Your name will be made anonymous and no identifiable personal information will be disclosed. All information relating to the study will be kept in locked cabinet in UWS with access for the researcher and the supervisor only. Electronic data collected will be stored on an encrypted UWS laptop / USB stick.

What if I have any concerns?

If you would like any further information before participating, please do not hesitate to contact me using the contact details below. Alternatively, you can contact my Director of Studies, Dr Mark Sanderson.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The data will be written up as part of a PhD thesis and will be shared with the wider research community through publications in scientific journals and/or conference presentations. If you wish to obtain the results from this study, you will be able to obtain a copy of your results on request following the write up of this study.

What happens next?

If after reading this information sheet, you are interested in participating in the study, please email me, Dalal ALQaseer. I am happy to answer any other questions you might have. If you are eligible to take part, we will arrange your data collection session with you. Thank you for taking the time to read this participant information sheet.

Contact for further information

Name: Dalal ALQaseer (PhD student at School of Health and Life Sciences, UWS)

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Director of Study:

Dr Mark Sanderson (Exercise Science Lecture, Chartered Physiotherapist)

Institute of Clinical Exercise and Health Science School of Health and Life Sciences.

University of the West of Scotland, E-mail: [REDACTED]

Appendix 9. Consent Form for Chapter 4 – 6

Participant Identification Number:

Title of Project: evaluate and compare the effect of novel knee rehabilitation exercises during squatting on acute Vastus medialis neuromuscular activity in Patellofemoral pain syndrome populations.

Name of Researcher: Dalal ALQaseer

Please initial in box

- 6. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated _____ (version _____) for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- 7. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason. If I do not participate in this project it will not affect my treatment programme.
- 8. I understand that individuals from University of the West of Scotland or regulatory authorities may look at the anonymised data collected during the above study. I give my permission for this.
- 9. I understand that the findings of the above study may be presented at conferences or published in Journals, but data will be anonymised and will not be possible to identify myself. I give my permission for this.
- 10. I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of person taking consent (if different from researcher):

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Date: